

**Influence of employer branding on employer of choice and organisation
performance: a study of service sector employees' perception in Pakistan**

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DECLARATION

I declare that the thesis is my effort. I took reasonable care to ensure that the work is original and, to the best of my knowledge, does not breach copyright law, and has not been taken from other sources except where such work has been cited and acknowledged within the text. The thesis has been carried out under the regulations of the University of the West of Scotland. This thesis has not been submitted to any other institution in the world for any other academic award.

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to extend employer branding research by identifying key elements of employer branding according to perceptions of current employees working in service firms and investigating the impact of employer branding on the employer of choice and organisation performance. The study was based on mixed-method research. Initially, adopting a qualitative method that involves in-depth interviews and focus group discussions to identify key elements of employer branding. The second phase of the research applied the quantitative method to investigate the causal associations between key constructs of the study. A sample of 544 respondents was used to test the measurement model and structural model using the PLS-SEM technique.

The current research found development and growth opportunities, and equality and justice as two new elements of employer branding along with organisation culture, salary and incentives, and Work-life balance. Moreover, employer branding significantly influences employer of choice through organisation commitment and employer brand advocacy. Organisation performance was influenced by employer branding through job satisfaction and employee performance. However, no significant relationship was proved between employer branding and employer of choice through person-organisation fit. In addition, the influence of employer branding on employee performance through employee retention was not significant.

The key contributions of the study were to reveal new elements of employer branding and the direct link between employer branding and employee performance. This study also highlights the importance of employer branding in enhancing employee retention, job satisfaction, and commitment in service firms. This study further guides managers to devise an employer branding strategy with employment benefits highlighted in this study to enhance organisation performance and gain a competitive advantage. Further details are given to encourage future research into employer branding, its elements, and its consequences.

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter of the research study is essential to understand the research background, the research problem, and its importance to the current business scenario. The objectives presented in the chapter provide a detailed explanation of the research problem to readers. This chapter is also important to explore the problem which leads to the development of hypotheses to evaluate the impact of employer branding (EB) on the employer of choice (EOC) and organisation performance (OP). A comprehensive discussion about the research background, justification, and outline of the chapters are essential to developing readers' interest in further chapters.

This chapter begins with a research background highlighting the scope of the study and identifying the gap in the literature of employer branding (Section 1.2). Section 1.3 presented the research problem mentioning gaps in the literature. Moreover, Research questions and objectives are described and explained in section 1.4. After that, the selection of comprehensive methodology to answer research questions is explained in section 1.5. Section 1.6 is all about the significance of the study. Furthermore, section 1.7 outlines the definitions of key concepts, and finally, the structure of the thesis can be seen in section 1.8.

1.2. RESEARCH BACKGROUND

Today's environment is more and more competitive. Organisations are trying to differentiate themselves from competitors in a variety of ways. In this attempt to become unique and superior in a market, communication with stakeholders plays a vital role. The brand is a language that

communicates to stakeholders, independent of verbal information. A brand is a set of perceptions in the minds of consumers (Chawla, 2020; Krishna and Kim, 2021; Schneider,2018). The brand depicts the identity, reputation, and image of products or services. The brand convinces consumers to purchase certain services or products. Moreover, it influences the mindset of potential customers and encourages them to change buying patterns (Chawla, 2020; Foroudi et al., 2020c; Foroudi and Palazzo, 2021; Olins, 2008).

Branding has been used for decades to differentiate one producer's goods from another (Gupta et al., 2020; Hwang et al., 2021; Foroudi et al., 2020c; Foroudi and Palazzo, 2021; Nguyen et al., 2020). In fact, the word brand comes from the old Norse word “brandr”, which means "to burn," because brands are used by livestock owners to identify their animals (Balakrishnan and Foroudi, 2020; Foroudi et al., 2020c; Foroudi and Palazzo, 2021). A brand, according to the American Marketing Association (2018), is a “name, word, sign, symbol, or design, or a combination of them, intended to identify the goods and services of one seller or group of sellers and to distinguish them from those of competitors.” Brand elements are the various components of a brand that identify and differentiate it (Foroudi et al.,2020b; Foroudi et al., 2020c; Hwang et al., 2021; Zha et al., 2020).

Branding entails building mental structures and assisting customers in organising their product and service knowledge in a way that clarifies their decision-making and adds value to the company (Imani et al., 2020; Jerez-Jerez et al., 2021; Krishna and Kim, 2021). Consumers perceive differences among brands in a product category, which is the key to branding. As previously stated, brand differences are frequently related to the product's attributes or benefits. Brand differences,

on the other hand, may be related to more intangible image considerations in some cases (Akbari et al. 2021; Balakrishnan and Foroudi, 2020; Foroudi, 2020).

Employer branding emerged upon the attempt of applying traditional marketing techniques of branding to the area of human resource management (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004; Bharadwaj and Yameen, 2020; Weske et al., 2019; Yadav et al., 2020). EB is a concept that was firstly introduced by Ambler and Barrow in 1996 (Dabrian et al., 2019; Kaur and Shah, 2021, Matongolo et al., 2018) as a set of functional, economic, or psychological benefits that an organisation provides and defines for their employees with the aim to develop a greater employee loyalty and output. Employer branding is the essence of the employment experience, providing touchstones that begin with initial brand awareness and continue throughout the employment tenure, even into retirement (Buchelt et al., 2021; Keppler and Papenfub, 2020; Priya and Raman, 2021). Employer branding is a unique and relevant way for a company to set itself apart from the competition by using its branded factors as its USP, which leads to increased retention, productivity, and efficiency (Dabrian et al., 2019; Kaur and Shah, 2021, Matongolo et al., 2018). What differentiates employer branding from classical branding concept is the target group: branding captures the customer's and the EB captures the employee's attention and loyalty toward a certain brand (American Marketing Association, 2016).

EB was defined by various authors (e.g., Ambler and Barrow, 1996; Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019; Chawla, 2020; Edwards, 2009; Ewing et al., 2002; Gardberg and Fombrun, 2002; Gray and Balmer, 1998; Kaur et al., 2020; Matongolo et al., 2018; Priya and Raman, 2021; Thorne, 2004; Weske et al., 2019) as a source of corporate identity and reputation that influences individual's

perception of a particular organisation. Strong employer branding, according to Hatch and Schultz (2020), is a link between an organization's culture, and its image. EB is a set of distinguishing employment benefits offered to employees that set an organisation apart from its competitors. This means that EB is composed of a set of elements or attributes that organisations used to make them unique employers (Bharadwaj and Yameen, 2020; Kaur et al., 2020; Theurer et al., 2018).

Employer brand and employer branding are used in literature interchangeably for the same meaning—all types of organisation that have employees concurrently aware of the employer brand. Since the 90s, organisations have been taking actions to strategically develop and manage their images to become more appealing to potential and actual employees. Employer branding got the attention of business consultants and practitioners in no time and is considered the hottest strategy in recent times in the world of business (Backhaus 2016; Lievens et al., 2007; Moroko and Uncles, 2008; Sullivan, 1999; Theurer et al., 2018; Thorne, 2004).

Many researchers (Bharadwaj and Yameen, 2020; Chawla, 2020; Kaur et al., 2020) have found positive impacts of employer branding on employees' work-related behaviour. Dessler (2017) noted that employer branding is an essential tool to attract and retain employees. In addition, employer branding helps employees to picture themselves being a part of the company. Employer branding is thus associated with talent retention and overall employee job-related outcomes. Naturally, the advantage of talent management or recruiting is to retain the high-quality talent that the organisation seeks. A successful employer branding policy will assist in communicating positive brand messages that will assist the organisation in attracting the best qualified, talented workers (Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019; Matongolo et al., 2018; Weske et al., 2019). Thus, the aim

is not simply to recruit as much talent as possible but rather to attract high-quality talent with diverse expertise and experience to bring value to the organisation.

Additionally, employers strive to fulfill employees' desires and ambitions through employer branding efforts, and, in return, employees reward organisations with their commitment and performance (Christopher et al., 2019). Many scholars (Ainspan et al., 2001; Ambler and Barrow, 1996; Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004; Barrow and Mosley, 2006; Biswas and Suar, 2014; Fulmer et al., 2003; Sartain and Schumman, 2006; Tumasjan et al., 2020) of employer branding argue that it is not limited to retention and recruitment of talented employees, but it can improve the employee's performance, satisfaction, engagement and commitment, which in return increase the performance of an organisation.

Employer branding helps organisations enhance employee satisfaction, commitment, and retention (Dabrian et al., 2019; Kaur and Shah, 2021, Matongolo et al., 2018) and boost the organisation performance (Biswas and sour, 2016; Tumasjan et al., 2020). Simultaneously, Huang and Liu (2010) argued that a correlation exists between employer branding and employee performance. Employees are dedicated to the best employers and, consequently, their performance brings excellent business results. (Aldousari et al., 2017; Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004). Employer branding is meant to make an organisation attractive and the best workplace, and a "top employer. " This not only means that workers enter and stick with the organisation, but also that they associate with the organisation emotionally.

Furthermore, several studies have supported the significance of attractive employer branding to generate employer of choice (EOC) (Edwards, 2010; Fulmer, Gerhart, and Scott, 2003; Saini and Jawahar, 2019; Wilden et al., 2010). An EOC can be an organisation for which a potential employee desires to join and remain with some unique benefits (Rosengren and Bondesson, 2014; Saini, 2018; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019). Employer of choice denotes that employees consciously choose to work for employers of choice rather than any leading firm in the market (Herman and Gioia, 2000; Hult, 2011). EB encourages employees to be continuously concerned and choose the same organisation again and again for their next stage in the career ladder.

Employer branding, according to Branham (2001), is vital for promoting a company as an employer of choice, and it may be accomplished by providing the right balance of psychological, economic, and functional benefits to current and potential employees (Vercic, 2021). In a subsequent study, Branham (2005) suggested that companies use organisation culture, work-life benefits, and a mix of incentives to gain the moniker of employer of choice in labour market. Employer branding, according to Elving et al. (2013), assists organisations in achieving the employer of choice ranking in the market, resulting in increased employer attractiveness (Rampl, 2014).

This is uncertain how various aspects of the job experience (for example, work-life balance, professional advancement opportunities, and so on) impact an employees' endorsement or recommendation as an employer of choice, which is one of the primary purposes of employer branding. A few researchers in this area have examined employer brand advocacy as an indication of employer of choice, which is likely a stronger predictor of employer brand strength because

workers will have personal knowledge of promises made and maintained (or not) (Edwards, 2010). Given the projected advantages to companies, it is important to find characteristics that will drive workers to promote their organisation as an employer of choice. However, it is unclear the right combination of employment benefits (components of employer branding) that lead to making an employer an employer of choice.

Adding to that, employees increase their job efforts with more dedication and commitment, and contribution to the organisation's performance and long-term competitiveness when they perceive the organisation is offering them what they need (Aldousari et al., 2017; Gaddam, 2008; Saini and Jawahar, 2019, Tanwar and Prasad, 2017). Employer branding is a package of social, economic, and psychological benefits to employers (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004; Rampl, 2014; Saini, 2018). Employee performance is one of the main factors that impact organisation performance (Tamasjan et al., 2020).

Hence, organisation performance can be increased through investment in employer branding. Organisation performance can be measured through actual output against its inputs. It can involve both financial and non-financial aspects. The non-financial performance is qualitative and subjective, while the performance of financial type is specific, quantitative, and objective (Mishra and Suar, 2010). Hence, employer branding helps organisations become the employer of choice and increases employee performance, leading to organisation performance and increasing profits.

1.3. STATEMENT OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

In the late 90s, many organisations worldwide realized a global talent shortage when the demand for talented employees exceeded the supply of talent (Dobrian, 2015; Man Power Group, 2020;

Schuler, Jackson and Tarique, 2011; Tarique and Schuler, 2010). The increasingly global competition for talent severely affected organisations (Claus, 2019; King, 2015). Consequently, acquiring talent had become a great challenge for businesses. The scarcity of talent was viewed as a significant threat to survival and growth, demonstrating that the "war for talent" is brutal to win (King, 2015; McCracken et al., 2016; Tarique and Schuler, 2010).

After three decades, organisations worldwide are still experiencing a talent shortage (Man Power Group, 2020). The demand for competitive and skilled employees has increased drastically (Aslam et al., 2015; Motangolo et al., 2018, Moroko and Uncles, 2008), but such employees' supply decreases in the labor market. At the same time, demographics in certain parts of the world are constantly changing, making the labor market more competitive. In the business context, it has become a challenge to retain and attract a competitive workforce.

Nowadays, the changing environment of businesses has forced an organisation to have highly motivated and qualified employees to get a fast market pace. Competent personnel is constantly needed for critical jobs that require expertise and in-depth knowledge of the respective jobs. Literature on the field reveals that organisations have realized that for them to gain and sustain a global competitive advantage, they have to manage their workforces effectively (Dobrian, 2015; McCracken et al., 2016; Tarique and Schuler, 2010; Weske et al., 2019).

Typically, economies are classified into three broad sectors: primary, secondary, and tertiary. Agriculture is the primary sector, while the secondary sector, including mining, construction, and manufacturing, is inextricably linked to the industrialized. Those commercial operations

comprising mental or physical efforts not classified as agriculture or production are generally referred to as services (Ayaz and Hina, 2009). According to the OECD (organisation for economic co-operation and development), the services sector contributes 47% of the GDP of low-income level economies, 53% to middle income, and 73% to the GDP of high-income countries. Reasons for drastic growth in this sector include easy mobilization of services imports and exports, globalization, and foreign direct investment OECD (2014).

The growth of the services sector in developing countries like Pakistan is increasing steadily and contributes more shares than the industrial and agriculture sector. It contributes 55% of its value-added share to Pakistan's total GDP, with 4.3% annual growth, and employs 35.1% of Pakistan's total labor force (Economic survey report, 2020). Pakistan is struggling hard to make its service sector firms per the world's standard (Khalid, 2017). According to the study of Rehman (2018), service firms can improve their standards with the help of retention and attraction of talented human resources. In the same way, as companies in developed countries, service firms in Pakistan are increasing their focus on retaining and attracting talented employees. However, there is much more to be done in this domain (Aslam et al., 2015; Rehman, 2018). Due to economic conditions in the country, shortage of competent workers, and migration of skilled employees, attraction and retention are significant challenges for service firms in Pakistan.

In the service sector, organisations that have failed to retain and attract their targeted employees usually face hardships like investment loss, retraining, and replacement costs (Abelson and Baysinger, 1984; Becker, 1962; Mlk, A. 2018). Similarly, they have been unable to implement organisational strategies and have low employee morale in motivation and satisfaction (Dabirian

et al., 2019; Hunt, 2009; Phelan, 1991). The services sector plays a major role in the economy but has received less attentiveness than manufacturing and agriculture as a source of growth. In developing countries, policymakers have given much less consideration to service sectors (Kaur and Shah, 2021; Weske et al., 2019).

Employer branding as part of the organisational strategy has emerged within the HRM and Marketing area, as it advocates strategic action towards attracting, developing, and retaining key employees (Grace and Iacono, 2015; Kaur and shah., 2020; King and Vaiman, 2019; Küpper et al., 2019; Scullion et al., 2010; Tarique and Schuler, 2010). Frequently, employer branding is referred to as the organisational method to market what a firm offers to existing and potential personnel to attract and maintain the talented workforce (Biswas and Suar, 2014; Gupta et al., 2019; Motangolo et al., 2018). In recent times, organisations are allocating more efforts and budget to employer branding because the investment which is made on employees brings high returns for the organisations (Berthon et al., 2005; Berry and Martin, 2018; Collins and Stevens, 2002; Grace and Iacono, 2015; Kaur and Shah, 2021; Saks and Gruman, 2014).

In marketing literature, branding is one of the well-developed concepts. However, Major advancements have been made in knowledge related to employer branding, EB is still sprouting (Biswas and Sour, 2014; Carlini et al., 2019; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019). Furthermore, research related to employer branding in the service sector is still relatively limited and need to learn about the purpose and practices of employer branding (Backhaus, 2016; Berry et al., 2018; Christopher et al., 2019; Dabirian et al., 2019; Matongolo et al., 2018, Perepelkin and Di Zhang, 2011; Tumasjan et al., 2020; Vercic, 2021).

While employer branding is not a new field of study, few scholars have defined its elements. This is still important to study elements of employer branding (Berry and Martin, 2018; Dabirian et al., 2019; Hoye et al., 2013; Kaur and Shah, 2021; Matongolo, 2018). Elements such as salaries and Incentives, organisational culture are consistently found to impact employer branding. To gain better insights into the concept of employer branding (Annuar et al., 2021; Saini and Jawahar, 2019; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019) it is necessary to study elements of employer branding across various sectors of the economy.

This body of research on the employer of choice has primarily focused on job seekers who are potential employees leaving a gap to study with existing employees (Saini and Jawahar, 2019). Elving et al. (2013) stated that an organisation's culture could effectively gain employers of choice status. Rampl (2014) has also identified organisational culture as a significant predictor of employer of choice in an empirical study. Moreover, Previous studies highlighted the relationship between few individual dimensions (Organisation culture, salary and incentive) of EB with the employer of choice (Saini and Jawahar, 2019; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019).

However, it is unclear how EB with various dimensions (e.g., work-life balance, development, and growth opportunities) affect an employer of choice. As EB is a whole package with various tools instead of one HRM technique, it needs to check whether EOC is one of the main consequences of EB. However, very few studies are available on the relationship between employer branding and Employer of choice (Saini and Jawahar, 2019; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019). Therefore, it is

pertinent to check whether employer branding helps an organisation become the employer of choice (Rample et al., 2014; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019).

In early studies, employer branding has declared a technique to attract talent in the organisation (Chhabra and Sharma, 2014; Devina et al., 2016; Khan, 2017; Maheshwari et al., 2017). It becomes necessary to examine its linkage to employee retention as there are limited research efforts has been done (Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019; Berthon et al., 2005; Collins and Stevens, 2002; Lievens et al., 2007; Maheshwari et al., 2017; Matongolo et al., 2018; Srivastava, 2010; Tanwar and Prasad, 2017).

Furthermore, Past studies on the consequences of EB have identified person-organisation fit as the primary outcome of EB. Employees assess the degree to which their values align with those of the organisation at varying selection points. However, it is essential to note that these findings examined the perceptions of prospective workers, not actual employees (Chawla 2020; Tanwar and Prasad, 2019), creates a gap to study the relationship between EB and Person organisation fit. Moreover, EB got more popular when the relationship between EB and organisation performance was assumed (Biswas and Sour, 2016). However, this relationship has very little unbiased empirical evidence to prove this reality and generalize it (Tamasjan, 2020).

Although employer branding is a phenomenon that exists at the firm level of analysis, previous research has focused mainly on the consequences of employer branding at in form of employee job outcomes (e.g., Alves, 2021; Eger et al., 2019; Theurer et al., 2018). Thus, there is a significant gap in EB literature to study EB as a detriment of organisation performance because results at one

stage of analysis cannot easily and precisely generalize to other levels of analysis, and therefore "blindly generalizing findings across levels of analysis is a fallacy" (Kozlowski and Klein, 2000, p. 213). Thus, the latest state of research, which indicates that employer branding has a favourable impact on individual-level outcomes, is insufficient. As a result, it remains technically undetermined if employer branding impacts firm-level results (Francis and Reddington, 2012). Hence, this is a topic of great interest for the contemporary researchers of EB, that EB influences organisation performance or not (Tumasjan et al., 2020).

Moreover, Schlager et al. (2011) believe that further investigation is needed across different industries to find similarities and differences among various EB determinants to achieve job outcomes like satisfaction, commitment, and employee performance which further contribute to organisation performance (Tanwar and Prasad 2016). Furthermore, researchers studied the EB from potential employees' perspectives, however, exiting employees were ignored as a significant target audience (Kaur and Shah, 2021; Saini and Jawahar, 2019; Tanwar and Prasad 2016). Thus, employees currently working in service sector firms in Pakistan were the focus of this study.

Another gap in the EB literature is that most of the studies have been conducted on EB and job outcomes like commitment and performance (Tanwar and Kumar 2019) in developed countries, creating enormous scope for its impact in developing countries (Fasih et al., 2019; Kaur and Shah, 2021; Tanwar and Prasad 2016). In developing countries like Pakistan, less work has been conducted related to EB. Pakistan is one of the devolving economies with over 224 million population (Economics Survey Report of Pakistan, 2020). Hence, employees currently working in service sector firms in Pakistan were the population of this study. Hence, this research aims to

extend employer branding research by identifying key elements of employer branding according to perceptions of current employees working in service firms and investigating the influence of employer branding on the employer of choice and organisation performance.

1.4 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Given the significance of employer branding and building upon the evidence discussed, it is valuable to examine the concept of employer branding further to supplement existing studies. Researchers are still refining and building understanding in the area of employer branding (Backhaus, 2016; Berry et al., 2018; Biswas and Sour, 2016; Christopher et al., 2019; Dabirian et al., 2019; Matongolo et al., 2018, Perepelkin and Di Zhang, 2011; Theurer et al., 2018; Tumasjan et al., 2020; Vercic, 2021), its elements and processes (Buchelt et al., 2021; Berry and Martin, 2018; Dabirian et al., 2019; Hoye et al., 2013; Kaur and Shah, 2021; Matongolo, 2018; Moroko and Uncles, 2005; Sullivan, 2007) and consequences (Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019; Keppler and Papenfub, 2020; Maheshwari et al., 2017; Matongolo et al., 2018; Srivastava, 2010; Tanwar and Prasad, 2017; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016; Theurer et al., 2018; Tumasjan et al., 2020). The gaps which were founds in existing literature and practice are summarized as:

1. There are limited studies on employer branding to highlight and define elements of employer branding in the context of service firms (Backhaus, 2016; Berry and Martin, 2018; Christopher et al., 2019; Dabirian et al., 2019; Hoye et al., 2013; Kaur and Shah, 2021; Matongolo, 2018; Tumasjan et al., 2020; Vercic, 2021). Researchers in the past studied the EB from potential employees' perspective; however, exiting employees in service firms were ignored as a primary target audience (Chawla 2020, Kaur and Shah, 2021; Saini and Jawahar, 2019).
2. Very few studies are available on the relationship between employer branding and Employer of choice. Previous studies mainly checked the influence of individual elements of EB on

Employer of choice. Therefore, it is pertinent to check whether employer branding (as a higher-order construct) helps the organisation become an employer of choice (Annuar et al., 2021; Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019; Devina et al., 2016; Maheshwari et al., 2017; Matongolo et al., 2018; Saini and Jawahar, 2019; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019).

3. The literature on marketing and branding lacks empirical evidence about the influence of EB on the organization performance (Aldousari et al., 2017; Biswas and Sour, 2016; Keppler and Papenfub, 2020; Tumasjan et al., 2020).
4. Most of the studies on EB and job outcomes have been conducted in developed countries, creating enormous scope for its impact in developing countries (Fasih et al., 2019; Priya and Raman, 2021; Tanwar and Prasad 2016; Weske et al., 2019).

Based on literature on employer branding and underline gaps in literate and practice, Specific research questions of this study are as follows:

RQ1: What are the key elements of robust employer branding in service firms according to the perception of current employees?

RQ2: Does employer branding influence the employer of choice and organisation performance?

Therefore, the Specific research objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To explore the key elements of robust employer branding in service sector firms according to the perception of current employees.
2. To investigate the influence of employer branding on the employer of choice and organisation performance.

1.5 RESEARCH DESIGN AND ANALYTICAL METHOD

To achieve the objectives of the study researcher applied two paradigms: interpretivism and positivism, which have been greatly emphasized and used in the marketing literature (Foroudi et al., 2014; Foroudi et al., 2021; Gupta et al., 2020; Hauken et al., 2019; Poth & Munce, 2020; Timans et al., 2019). Employer branding is a comparatively underdeveloped research area (Buchelt et al., 2021; Christopher et al., 2019; Dabirian et al., 2019; Tumasjan et al., 2020). There was a need to understand employer branding in the service sector context especially with the perspectives of current employees (Chawla 2020; Eger et al., 2019; Kaur and Shah, 2021; Saini and Jawahar, 2019). Already explored elements of employer branding by previous researchers do not capture the full essence of employer branding because most of them took university students (Potential employees) as the population of their studies (Kaur and Shah, 2021; Keppler and Papenfub, 2020; Priya and Raman, 2021; Saini and Jawahar, 2019).

As part of interpretive research philosophy, the researcher considered the participants' views that effectively answer the question to highlight the employment benefits a service firm uses to differentiate its employer brand (elements of employer branding). This philosophy also enables the researcher to interpret different views and opinions about the concepts and understanding of EB (Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019; Buchelt et al., 2021; Collins, 2010; Poth & Munce, 2020). Hence, the qualitative part helped examine the phenomenon in detail (Berry and Marti, 2018; Bhattacharya and Elsbach, 2002; Fàbregues et al., 2020). Qualitative data was collected in the first phase of the study and newly explored elements of EB were added and amended conceptual model. Moreover, Qualitative data also was used to amend the existing scale to measure employer branding with consideration of newly explored elements of employer branding.

To answer the first research question (what are the key elements of robust employer branding in service firms according to the perception of current employees?), qualitative data was collected to identify and interpret elements of employer branding. A Non-Probability sampling (convenience and purposive sampling) was applied to select participants for ten qualitative in-depth interviews (Semi-structured), and four focus group interviews (6 participants in each group) were conducted. Moreover, middle-level managers working in service firms (Universities, Telecom, Banks, Insurance Firms) in Pakistan were selected for in-depth interviews. First-line managers and non-managerial employees working in service firms in Pakistan were part of focus group interviews. Content analysis was used to analyse interview and focus group data.

The second phase of the research applied the positivist paradigm to investigate the causal associations and proposed hypotheses. At the same time, as a part of positivist philosophy, the researcher collects a wide range of quantitative data so that reliability towards the qualitative data can be enhanced (Foroudi et al., 2020a; Shorten & Smith, 2017; Timans et al., 2019; Wilkinson & Staley, 2019). In addition, the causal relationship between employer branding and employer of choice and organisation performance was tested. The content validity of scales was satisfied through the panel of experts. Academics suggested to remove irrelevant items (De-Vellis, 2003; Foroudi et al., 2019a; Fàbregues et al., 2020; Poth & Munce, 2020) to get accurate items to measure employer branding.

To answer second research question (does employer branding influence the employer of choice and organisation performance?), A self-administered questionnaire with sixty-six items using a

seven-point likert scale was circulated among employees working in a service firm in Pakistan using the snowball sampling technique to get employees' perceptions to test the influence of EB on EOC and organisational performance. This research examined the perceptions of employees working in service sector firms in Pakistan. In total, five hundred and forty-four questionnaires were used for the final quantitative analysis. Cronbach alpha and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted using SPSS 26 to check scale reliability and validity (David et al., 2018; Foroudi et al., 2020i; Linnander et al., 2019). To test the measurement model and structural model, Smart PLS 3 was applied. PLS Structure Equation Modeling (SEM) is the most appropriate technique for the current study (Hair et al., 2014; Ringle et al., 2010).

1.6 SCOPE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study has attempted to get a deep understanding of employer branding. In the service sector, this study has extended the vital application of the concept of EB. Moreover, this research has made considerable managerial, and theoretical contributions. The empirical outcomes of this research have extended the past findings of EB and add value to the literature on EOC and organisation performance. This study has advanced the existing perspective of EB and its consequences on employees and organisations. The key influences of EB on the employer of choice and organisational performance along with exploration of key elements of EB in the perception of current employees of service firms are the major gaps to fill by this particular study.

Changing labour markets, quickly evolving technology, and the openness of markets, all require companies to not just attract new employees, but also to focus more on those already in the workforce. Employer branding is important in today's increasingly competitive employment market as hiring and keeping the finest personnel have become challenging for organisations. To

survive and grow, firms need talented employees, and the best way to recruit potential employees and retain existing employees is to provide them with the idea that your organisation is a wonderful place to work. The organisations need to make themselves attractive to be the first choice of potential employees. The term "attractive employers " should only be applied to organisations whose present and future workers perceive their work environment as conducive to career advancement (Alves, 2021; Buchelt et al., 2021; Keppler and Papenfub, 2020; Priya and Raman, 2021).

Organisation can improve their competitiveness and efficiency in this rapidly changing business environment by developing their human resource management strategy, to make them sufficiently attractive in the labour market. Organisations must adapt to new changes; HRM must be transformed in order to add value through a new approach. The need for robust employer branding is increasingly acknowledged by global corporations as well as small and medium-sized businesses, and its role in effectively managing critical labour market demands is gradually gaining adhesion. This is also necessary in order to develop adaptable, constantly changing capabilities, strategic actions, new trends, and systems in response to rapidly changing market demands, economic conditions, and the struggle to retain talent, all while focusing on maintaining a positive employer brand demonstrated to market players. Beyond manufacturing processes, these novel concepts and methodologies are growing rapidly in other sectors of study, presenting new opportunities for service firms.

Globalisation offered new opportunities and threats to all types of economies. This study is important at this time when service sector firms in developing economies are struggling to increase

retention, satisfaction (Saini and Jawahar, 2019; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019), and performance of employees (Fasih et al., 2019; Tumasjan et al., 2020; Weske et al., 2019). Moreover, Service firms are trying to make themselves attractive and first choice employers for talented workers (Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019; Devina et al., 2016; Maheshwari et al., 2017; Matongolo et al., 2018).

This research study guides how organisations may attract talent more successfully and keep talented employees if their employer brand is strong and regularly improved with special attention to the elements of employer branding highlighted by this study. In addition. The present study includes information on how employer branding may help make a business more attractive and engaging to workers. It will also provide managers and scholars with a better grasp of the subject. It will also touch on the principles that managers must focus on to retain their staff in today's corporate climate. One of the key objectives was to explore the elements of employer branding important to service firms that help improving employee retention and job outcomes.

The theoretical contributions of the present research to the current body of knowledge present another perspective to employer branding. A few empirical studies are available that addressed EB's influence on organisation performance (Biswas and Sour, 2016, Tumasjan et al., 2020). The study will also help reshape and revitalize research in the field of employer branding. Thus, by designing and evaluating a scale specifying the field of influence of the EB, it adds significant value to the literature. In addition to the scale developed for the EB, structural equation modeling (SEM) was used to assess the relations between the constructs and verify the conceptual model. Therefore, this research contributes towards broadening and improving employer branding

awareness to deepen the interaction between EB and its consequences (employer of choice and organisation performance).

In addition, this study gives additional insight into the dimensionality and operationalization of research principles from employees working in the service sector. This study makes a three-fold theoretical contribution: 1) expansion of the theory by empirical testing, 2) conceptualization verification, 3) construct measuring, and theory testing and generalization. Two stages followed a multidisciplinary approach to define and explain employer branding regarding dimensions and consequences: 1) a qualitative approach. 2) A self-administered questionnaire to ensure more detailed procedures for data collection and then structural equation modeling has been carried out as a rigorous data analysis technique.

The findings of this study have a variety of implications for managers. This study indicates first and foremost that managers need to consider employer branding to be a dynamic phenomenon because it is contingent on many factors like the organisation culture, development and growth opportunities, Salaries and incentives, Work-life balance and finally, equality and justice. It implies that managers should be vigilant about the reputation of the company as an employer brand. Theoretical and empirical findings derived from the research have many consequences and provide decision-makers with managerial insights into employer brands and their influence on the employee and organisation performance.

This study's findings suggest that corporations should have clear guidelines about employer branding as a complex process influenced by multiple factors to gain a competitive advantage. The

lesson for top managers in service firms is that to survive and enhance employee productivity and organisation performance, they need to concentrate on communication consistency to understand employees' beliefs, attitudes, impressions, and associations. Furthermore, managers should more emphasize employer branding than the branding of products and services to gain a sustainable competitive advantage.

From a practical perspective, this study provides valuable guidelines for top-level management in service firms. For the firms Operating in the service sector, employees are their primary source of competitive edge in the market (Bapat et al., 2019; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019; Wilkinson & Staley, 2019). Investing in existing employees would result in increased organisation performance which is the ultimate goal. Employer branding is the area to work on to gain positive employees job outcomes. As per findings of the study suggested, for robust employer branding, organisations need to balance existing employees' personal and work life, and offer sufficient personal and professional development and growth opportunities. Moreover, the employee may be offered competitive salaries and incentives and provide an organisational culture supportive and conducive so that the employee's work-life experience becomes tremendous.

Furthermore, the results of this study are essential for decision-makers in service firms because EB can play a significant role in organisation performance. The results of this study showed that EB directly influences job satisfaction, organisation commitment, employee retention, and employee performance. Moreover, HR and marketing managers have implications: to grow and maintain a prominent position in the market, and they should be aware of employee advocacy,

making an organisation an employer of choice through employer branding with the right combination of employment benefits highlighted in this study.

Findings of this study also specifically support investing in "employer branding" (Lievens et al., 2007; Poth & Munce, 2020; Timans et al., 2019; Theurer et al., 2018), promoting the employer brand to current employees through financial, functional, and physiological benefits. Thus, contrary to widely held beliefs in practice that employer branding is solely a recruiting tool used to attract candidates (i.e., "a recruitment-focused strategy"), this research demonstrates that the beneficial results in company success are caused by current employee-related outcomes, instead of applicant-related outcomes. Since research identifies the specific process by which employer branding initiation benefits existing employees' satisfaction and commitment, it helps HR practitioners to grasp the fundamental facts of influence.

As a result of the widespread interest in employer branding among service sector firms, this study can serve as a case for HR practitioners to promote investment in employer branding to improve these critical human resource outcomes. As a result of this study, HRM experts should be mindful that the beneficial impact of employer branding on firm success could be attributed to its effect on existing workers rather than potential employees. In this context, HRM practitioners may use the findings of this study to educate their leadership about the importance of EB and its impact on employee outcomes and firm success.

1.7 DEFINITIONS OF KEY CONSTRUCTS

Table 1.1: Definitions of constructs and concepts

Construct	Definitions	Major References
Employer Branding	Employer branding is a Process of building a recognizable and distinctive employer identity by offering employment benefits (Functional, economic and psychological) that differentiates it from its competitors.	Biswas and Suar, 2016; Rosengren and Bondesson, 2014; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019.
Organisation Culture	A system comprises values shared by each member of an organisation.	Tanwar and Prasad, 2016
Development and Growth opportunities	Possibility of building career and promotion opportunities within the organisation	Rampl, 2016
Salary and Incentives	Overall compensation package including compensation, perks, and other benefits offered by an employer to motivate employee	Tanwar and Kumar, 2019
Work-life balance	Equilibrium between the person's personal and official life	Tanwar and Prasad, 2016
Employer of choice	An EOC can be an organisation for which a potential employee desires to join and remain with to have some unique benefits	Rosengren and Bondesson, 2014; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019.
Employee Performance	Employee performance is the use of time effectively by an employee to achieve desired outcomes	Haynes, 2007; Mohammad, 2019
Organisation Performance	Organisation performance is defined as goal achievement, the behaviour of organisation participants, and the relationship of organisation with its environment	Kim et al., 2017; Gomes et al. 2017
Organisation Commitment	Organisation commitment is a force psychological bond with an organisation and expression of employees to remain a member of an organisation	Bulut and culha, 2010; Christopher et al., 2019; Kim and Gray, 2017
Job Satisfaction	job satisfaction is the employees' attitude and feeling towards their job and other mechanisms of a job at the workplace	Bangwal and Tiwari, 2019; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016
Employer Brand Advocacy	Voluntary favorable communication, promotion, and spreading a positive word of mouth of	Choisa et al. 2018; Men 2014; Tanwar and Prasad 2016

	organization brand by employee to external stakeholders	
Employee Retention	Employee retention is the effort and determination to keep a desirable employee who contributes towards the success of the organisation	Christopher et al. 2019; Govaerts et al., 2011; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016
Person Organisation fit	A match of employee's values, needs, and ideas with that of organisation enhances more attraction of organization.	Tanwar and Kumar, 2019

Source: Researcher

1.8 STRUCTURE OF THE THESIS

Research structure refers to the sketch of the entire research or how the entire research shall be carried out. Research structure usually unfolds the phases to be included by the researcher in effectively executing the research. In this research, the researcher shall conduct the fundamental research based on the following framework.

Chapter 1 Introduction: This is one of the significant chapters of the study. Here the researcher presented his thoughts and the initial process of the research. This section provides comprehensive details about the complete research process, which is followed to accomplish the study. It provides the introduction to the research topic by discussing the research background, justification of the research issue. Moreover, research significance and the research problem are also presented in this chapter. It is an important chapter to discuss the research aims and objectives along with the research questions. The primary purpose of developing this introduction chapter is to develop the understanding of readers about the needs of conducting this study on an issue or research problems and develop their interest in the study.

Furthermore, this chapter is essential to present the scope and significance of the study. A comprehensive discussion about the significance of the study is given in this chapter. Further, relevant impacts of this study for business practices and regulations are also described.

Chapter 2 Literature Review: This chapter involves a systematic review of the existing literary discourse to develop a thorough understanding of the research issue. The researcher follows a critical approach to examine the available information in the context of the research issue. Various secondary sources, including journal articles, books, newspapers, websites, and other authentic online sources, are used to make this section effective.

Chapter 3 Theoretical Framework. In this chapter, a comprehensive overview is presented about the impact of employer branding on the employer of choice and organisation performance. Moreover, in this chapter, hypotheses are described, justified, and supported with the help of relevant literature. The primary purpose of developing this chapter is to provide a theoretical framework to the readers, improve their understanding of the existing literature, and gain an in-depth knowledge of the research issue from the views of different experts and scholars.

Chapter 4 Research Methodology: The fourth chapter is the methodology, which discusses a set of research methods and strategies to draw and collect valid and reliable data. It discusses the selection of a method over others with adequate justification. Conducting a study to solve a research problem requires comprehensive knowledge and information about choosing a research philosophy, approaches, and strategy. It also depends on the nature of the research problem to

select adequate methods to collect credible and authentic data and information to answer the research questions. So, this chapter is developed to provide the rationale behind selecting specific approaches, design, and data collection methods over others, so that the authenticity of the data collection process can be established.

Chapter 5 Qualitative Data Analysis: No data adds value to research until the data is processed into information. The present study collects both qualitative and quantitative data. The qualitative information contributes to solve the research problem and answer research questions. This chapter presents detailed analysis data, which was collected through in-depth interviews and focus group interviews.

Chapter 6 Quantitative Data Analysis: After the chapter on Qualitative data analysis, the next one is significant to present the statistical results of the data collected through the survey with a self-administered questionnaire. In this chapter, results from the data analysis process are explained. The data is analysed by using statistical techniques with SPSS 24 and Smart-PLS 3. All statistical results with tables and figures are presented and interpreted with sufficient detail.

Chapter 7 Discussion of Key Findings: This chapter discusses the analysis and interpretation of the collected data systematically to present reliable research outcomes. The discussion and findings of the study are presented in detail in this chapter. This chapter informs the readers about the answers to the research questions and to what extent the research problem is valid and accepted as a significant social and behavioural science issue.

Chapter 8 Conclusion, Contribution, and Recommendations: This is the last section of the study, which will describe the conclusion, recommendations, and limitations that can affect the scope and reliability of the research outcomes. Further, the limitations discussed in this chapter are also essential to understand the factors, which are uncontrollable and may affect the result to some extent. It also indicates a future scope for further research on the same issue or research problems.

1.9 SUMMARY

The nature of competition in the world calls for a war of talent. It has changed the way of doing business and strategies and enabled businesses to compete globally. However, it has also created challenges for organisations, especially in the service sector. Attraction and retention of talent have become a hot issue nowadays. Employer branding is one of the devices to attract, develop and maintain a talented workforce. There exists literature describing and defining the nature of employer branding, but this study seeks to address gaps in how employer branding can be made more efficient and effective given the conditions that exist in the service sector firms. The research objectives, research problem, and significance of the study are presented in detail in this chapter.

CHAPTER II

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter of the research study comprises an assessment of the literary discourse concerned with employer branding. The literature review is done from a global perspective to understand the technologically fueled phenomenon in employer branding. Several theoretical frameworks are examined to understand how EB is defined and developed. The theoretical framework in this study is based on social exchange and signaling theory to explain the association of hypothesized relationships encompassing employer branding and its outcomes.

The theoretical base for employer branding is presented in section 2.2, which consists of social exchange theory and signaling theory. Moreover, the Definition and domain of EB are in section 2.3. Previous research on EB highlights in section 2.4, whereas section 2.5 talks about the employer branding process. In addition, the Description and explanation of dimensions of employer branding, including organisation culture, corporate social responsibility, work-life balance, and salaries and incentives, are presented in section 2.6.

2.2. THEORETICAL BASE FOR EMPLOYER BRANDING

The theoretical framework in this thesis is built on two theories: social exchange theory and signaling theory. These theories were employed to explore the relationship between the thesis's major concepts: employer branding, its dimensions, and consequences. Companies use signaling theory to signal direct and indirect indications of intentions, ambitions, and motives (Dögl & Holtbrügge, 2014), which can help build a strong employer brand and prevent information

asymmetry between the employer and its present employees (Spence, 2002; Tanwar & Prasad, 2016a). However, reinforcement and contingent reciprocal linkages among performers in interdependent environments are part of social exchange theory (Tsarenko et al., 2018). For some rewards, a social exchange may include personal investment of resources, labour, identity, connection, and commitment. According to recent research, individuals who believe their contributions are valued by their employer create progressive attitudes about their jobs and dispositions toward their employers (Tsarenko et al., 2018).

2.2.1 Social Exchange Theory

The social exchange theory (Blau, 1968) suggests that employer branding results in comprehensive support from both parties engaged in the exchanged process. Social exchange includes strengthening and contingent mutual relations between performers in interdependent contexts. Exchange relationships can be expensive because parties need to invest resources in the process of social exchange (Tsarenko et al., 2018). The social exchange may include individual efforts, resources, identity, engagement, and commitment to certain benefits.

The basic premise of social exchange theory is the norm of reciprocity. According to this norm, employees respond to positive behaviours with positive outcomes and vice versa (Blau, 1968). Thus, when an organisation offers economic, contextual, and psychological benefits to its employees, they consider them a positive exchange, and therefore they reciprocate by being more committed and satisfied (Tsarenko et al., 2018). Recent studies show that personnel who see the organisation's contribution substantially build positive feelings for their jobs and the organisation (Tsarenko et al., 2018). Hence, the social exchange theory and reciprocity are also applicable to employee satisfaction, commitment, retention, and performance. Reciprocal conduct concerning

retention will occur if employees are committed and satisfied and recognize the importance of support from organisations.

Moreover, these employees remain a part of the organisation and engage in positive outcomes. Thus, it can be inferred that organisational branding policies help develop the subjective perceptions of employees and resultant outcomes. When the employees consider that their organisation is offering them value, they will likely be more committed and satisfied, and this strong membership sense helps them to remain part of the organisation (Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019). These job-related outcomes include job satisfaction, and commitment will also increase employee and organisation performance (Tsarenko et al., 2018).

2.2.1.1. Employer Branding as a Social Exchange

Employer branding is a build an image of the workplace manifested via different organisational features such as functional, psychological, and financial benefits offered to its employees (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004). Because Employer Branding lies midway between marketing and human resource management (HRM), there is a lot of literature in the domain of behavioural theory. The Social Exchange Theory appears to be a suitable theory to emphasise in tandem with Employee behavior Advocacy (SET). According to this theory, all promises made by the organisation to their employees in terms of employee perks and other functional components should be honored (Natarajan et al., 2016). When employees think they are being supported by the organisation, “they may strive to reciprocate that support and influence the exchange” (Akgunduz et al., 2017, as in Walden et al, 2018, p. 4). Employees will reciprocate as a result of the organization's fulfillment of promises made to them (Anttila, 2019; Natarajan et al, 2016).

Employer branding is about developing relationships with existing and prospective workers, and this is a two-way avenue. Furthermore, according to social exchange theory, “employees may engage in behaviours such as advocacy to repay organisations since the organisations have added value to the relationship and supported the employee” (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005; Walden et al., 2018). Natarajan et al. (2016) investigated employees' job outcomes as a return of employer branding efforts by the organisation. Other forms of reciprocation, such as employee satisfaction and commitment, work performance, and other positive behaviour, have also been considered as an exchange of employer branding efforts. Reciprocal exchange is repetitive in nature, and scholars (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005; Natarajan et al., 2016) emphasize the importance of organisations continuing to keep their promises by providing positive actions and benefits to employees in order to ensure favourable reciprocation from them in the long run.

2.2.2. Signalling Theory

Organisations use Signaling Theory to signal overt and indirect indications of intentions, objectives, and motivations (Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a), promoting the development of a powerful employer identity and avoiding knowledge asymmetry between employer and existing employees (Spence, 2002). When employees recognize symmetry in the employer's promises and perceptions, employee satisfaction, commitment, and retention can be accomplished (Dögl and Holtbrügge, 2014). Signaling theory is also used as a framework for interpreting employer branding regarding employee satisfaction, commitment, and retention.

Thus, Theory provides an understanding of how organisations may increase employee commitment and satisfaction, and performance by implementing an effective employer branding

strategy (Chen and Choi, 2008; Reis and Braga, 2016). Typically, one party serves as a sender who decides the way and medium to communicate precise information, and the opposite party performs the role of the receiver who chooses how to interpret the signals (Certo et al., 2011).

Moreover, Spence's (2002) underlying idea behind the job market signaling model is that potential employees have attributes that are unobservable to the employer, influencing an individual's productivity and thus the employer's value on the job. Hence, he argued that the employing organisation bases its hiring decisions on signals such as educational certificates of the applicants (Spence, 2002). While Spence (1973, 2002) views the issue of signaling from an employer's perspective, organisational researchers (e.g., Rynes, 1991; Wanous, 1992) extended his work by including the applicant's perspective. Rynes (1991) believed that job applicants strive to reduce the existing information asymmetry between them and the employing company. As a result, they rely on signals from the organisation when concluding corporate values, intentions, and characteristics (Rynes, 1991).

Furthermore, the signals employed for this purpose provide information regarding how the company's working environment can be (Celani and Singh, 2011; Wilden et al., 2010). Companies must provide accurate and precise information (Taj, 2016) to enable future workers to establish an accurate perception of the firm because these signals can influence their decision-making process (Ketchen et al., 2010). While the majority of human resource scholars have based their studies on the signaling theory in the context of talent attraction and recruitment processes (e.g., Celani and Singh, 2011; Ketchen et al., 2010; Suazo et al., 2009), recent research has also applied the theory to employer branding (e.g., Alshathry et al., 2017; Celani and Singh, 2011; Taj, 2016; Wilden et

al., 2010). However, the studies covering employer branding focused more on the potential employee than current employees to consider them crucial workforce retention.

According to Dögl and Holtbrügge (2014), the need for signaling occurs typically in competitive environments where organisations compete for scarce resources. Due to talent scarcity and increased demand for a highly skilled workforce, companies face the challenge of retaining their current employees (Biswas and Suar, 2016; Maheshwari et al., 2017; Theurer et al., 2018), which requires them to acknowledge the relevance of authentic signaling within the employer branding context (Taj, 2016).

2.2.2.1. Employer branding by signaling a solid employer brand

A company aims to create an image of itself as a unique and desirable place to work among its present workers (Ewing et al., 2002; Taj, 2016). As a result, employer branding has evolved as a tactic for businesses to set themselves apart from their competition (Maheshwari et al., 2017; Taj, 2016; Theurer et al., 2018). According to signaling theory, there is an information imbalance between the business and its present staff regarding employer branding (Spence, 2002). As a result, the company acts as a transmitter of brand signals received and interpreted by current personnel. As a result, how workers interpret the signals presented is influenced by personal experiences and preferences, impacting outcomes such as employee behaviour and attitudes toward the company (Taj, 2016).

Furthermore, effective employer branding necessitates the organisation giving distinct and authentic signals to its workers, clearly communicating their unique employment opportunities

and values (Schlager et al., 2011; Taj, 2016). Employees can better internalize and comprehend the brand when they perceive brand signals to be clear, credible, and consistent (Erkmen, 2018; Theurer et al., 2018). Furthermore, organisations can prevent potential ambiguous meanings and misinterpretations by employees, hence unintended results, if the employer brand is openly communicated through a powerful signal (Karanges et al., 2018; Suazo et al., 2011).

As a result, the elements that influence how workers understand signals are critical for businesses, as they aim to optimize the intended interpretation in order to produce desirable employee attitudes and behaviours (Taj, 2016), such as employee commitment and satisfaction, as well as performance (Erkmen, 2018; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a). Even though these attitudes will be molded by direct contact with the brand values, brand signals are likely to impact potential and present workers (Karanges et al., 2018; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a; Wilden et al., 2010). By conveying a business's beliefs, rules, and goals through a strong employer brand, a company may overcome current workers' fears and doubts, resulting in increased employee satisfaction and commitment (Erkmen, 2018; Wilden et al., 2010).

Existing employees can either gather information about the company through internal sources, e.g., supervisors, or external sources such as corporate reputation (Alshathry et al., 2017; Karjaluoto and Paakkonen, 2019; Mlk, 2018). While building this corporate knowledge, employees may increase familiarity with the organisation and create a more comprehensive picture of how others perceive the employer (Alshathry et al., 2017). It is in the company's interest to ensure that the information gathered by employees leads to positive associations with the employer

brand to increase employee retention (Alshathry et al., 2017; Bhasin et al., 2019; Yadav et al., 2020).

However, some associations which existed before entering the company may be confirmed after the experience, whereas others will be modified, and new associations will be created (Alshathry et al., 2017). In order to reduce negative associations with the employer brand, organisations need to ensure that the signals convey information about characteristics that distinguish themselves from their competitors to create a corporate image of a unique employer in employees' minds (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004; Dögl and Holtbrügge, 2014). These signals should always influence employees' decisions and behaviours in favour of the company (Dögl and Holtbrügge, 2014). Signal content that has been found to determine a strong employer brand is characterized by social, economic, reputation, development, and diversity value (Ambler and Barrow, 1996; Schlager et al., 2011; Alniaçik and Alniaçik, 2012; Reis and Braga, 2016; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016b; Slavkovic et al., 2018).

A strong team spirit, skilled coworkers, and a friendly and polite atmosphere among supervisors and subordinates contribute to social value (Matongolo et al., 2018; Schlager et al., 2011). A decent wage, incentives, a reasonable amount of vacation days, and good retirement benefits are all examples of high economic value (Gaylard et al., 2005; Heilmann et al., 2013; Matongolo et al., 2018; Schlager et al., 2011; zçelik, 2015). Development value refers to training and development opportunities and robust mentoring culture (Ito et al., 2013; Reis and Braga, 2016; Schlager et al., 2011). Finally, occupational qualities such as challenging and diverse tasks are included in the diversity value (Biswas and Suar, 2016; Bjerke et al., 2007; Schlager et al., 2011).

By applying the Signalling Theory to the concept of employer branding, awareness of the signal content's relevance was raised, and, additionally, four specific values were identified in the literature. These values can be internally conveyed by a company to build a strong employer brand and therefore influence employees' decisions and behaviours in favour of the organisation, namely employee satisfaction, commitment, and performance (Dögl and Holtbrügge, 2014; Reis and Braga, 2016; Slavkovic et al., 2018).

2.3. EMPLOYER BRANDING

“The concept of employer branding was borrowed from marketing. It assists organisations to focus on how they might locate themselves in their market as an employer of existing employees, and also as a potential employer of new employees ”(Tüzüner et al., 2009, p. 43). Although employer branding is a relatively new concept, some companies have been using it for quite some time. Recently, brand image has started to play a more significant role in employee recruitment and retention (Bhasin et al., 2019; Matongolo et al., 2018; Yadav et al., 2020). The brand image was beneficial not only in luring consumers but also in a competitive employment market.

Ambler and Barrow (1996) provided the first description of employer branding as "the package of functional, economic and psychological benefits offered by employment and identified in the employer business." It advanced the employer brand's three-dimensional conceptualization: functional benefits, financial benefits, and psychological benefits. These benefits are in the same fashion as the benefits offered by a distinctive brand to its consumers. The functional dimension means the developmental programs provided by the organisation, and the economic dimension reflects the organisation's material/monetary benefits, and the psychological dimension applies to

the sense of identity, orientation, and intent (Berry and Martin, 2018; Hoye et al., 2013; Tanwar and Kumar 2019).

In addition to Ambler and Barrow (1996), several other researchers defined the employer brand (Fasih et al., 2019; Kumari and Saini, 2018; Weske et al., 2019). As per the definition of CIPD (2009), "the employer brand is a set of attributes and qualities that makes an organisation distinctive and promises a unique employment experience." Kucherov and Zavylova (2012) define the employer brand as an assemblage of employer top-notch sentiments which attract the target audience. The employer brand defines the company's reputation as an employer.

The concept of employer branding is defined by Sullivan (2004) as producing an image that makes you a "great place to work." Branding was designed to generate a permanent picture of customer perception based on the marketing principle (Sullivan 2004). Employer branding seeks to build an impression to inspire employees to work for the organisation, to promote the creation of a workplace that fits the positive image portrayed by an employer brand (Maurya and Agarwal, 2018; Saini and Jawahar, 2019; Yoganathan et al., 2021).

Furthermore, employer branding is a mixture of tangible and intangible advantages that the firm gives to recruit potential workers and maintain current personnel (Ambler and Barrow, 1996; Chawla, 2020; Moroko and Uncles, 2008). An examination of the literature following Ambler and Barrow's (1996) introduction reveals that it has been a powerful word in marketing and management. According to the CIPD (2007), four key reasons are driving the EB's rise: (1) brand strength, (2) a greater concern for employee interest, (3) the talent war, and (4) greater role of

HRM strategies in organisation success (Fasih et al., 2019; Foster et al., 2010; Moroko and Uncles 2008). Employer Branding focuses on existing and potential employees. A brand's distinguishing feature distinguishes suppliers and service providers from their competitors. EB is also developing a distinct and recognizable employer brand that will set it apart from its competitors (Backhaus and Tikoo 2004; Kim et al., 2012; Saini and Jawahar, 2019).

The idea of "employer attractiveness" described by Berthon et al. (2005) was a similar and connected concept to the employer brand. The employer's attractiveness was described as "the imagination of benefits that a prospective employee can enjoy when working for a particular organisation" (Berthon et al., 2005, p. 152). Dabirian et al. (2017) also claimed that employer branding attempts to demonstrate a thriving workplace for prospective and existing workers. Berthon et al. (2005) discovered that advertising was a critical tool for these practices. It was able to support businesses in identifying, attracting, functioning, and employing.

Employer branding could help businesses stand out as attractive employers among their competitors, but only if it was carefully targeted (Dabirian et al., 2019; Martin et al., 2005; Tumasjan et al., 2020). The job seeker is interested in getting information about the employer brand from experiencers and a range of media (Chawla, 2020; Dabirian et al., 2017; Tanwar and Kumar 2019), which helps him shape an attitude for an available job position in the recruitment process. Several scholars recommended that an employer brand be divided into functional and symbolic characteristics (Katz, 1960; Karjaluoto and Paakkonen, 2019; Locander and Spivey, 1978; Maurya and Agarwal, 2018).

Tangible perspectives of employer brand are categorized into symbolic and functional components (Karjaluo and Paakkonen, 2019; Maurya and Agarwal, 2018; Matongolo et al., 2018; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019). The study of Drury (2016) also divides the notion of employer brand into these categories: 1). Functional attributes; leave allowances, salary, health care coverage, and benefits. 2). Symbolic attributes; the prestige of work, work culture, and career development opportunities for a company.

Employer branding is related to keeping, retaining, and attracting employees. Moreover, Urbancova and Hudakovas (2017) agreed to the advantages of an employer branding strategy, describing EB's importance to enhance the organisation's financial performance. Organisations have identified five benefits of this integration; improving financial performance, public brand awareness, winning talented employees, increasing motivation, and retaining current employees (Tumasjan et al., 2020; Urbancova and Hudakova, 2017). Willock (2005), on the other hand, reported that ninety-five percent of organisations consider employer branding to be essential.

Building and maintaining a brand is currently a primary concern of corporations across every sector. Perhaps more relevant for many international companies, employer branding created a greater incentive for the organisations to capture the interest of more prospective employees, mainly as they wanted to engage more strongly in hiring and recruiting skilled workers from the global marketplace (Martin et al., 2005; Matongolo et al., 2018; Yadav et al., 2020). Furthermore, non-profit organisations, such as universities and banks, gradually realize the importance of branding (Dabirian et al., 2019; Maurya and Agarwal, 2018; Yoganathan et al., 2021). In an era of intensified competitiveness, organisations required high-quality personnel capable of handling

diversified tasks to improve the organisation's success (Mölk, 2018; Sung and Yang 2008; Yadav et al., 2020).

Companies need to formulate methods for hiring the best workers (Martin et al., 2005; Matongolo et al., 2018; Yadav et al., 2020) to gain a competitive advantage in the market. Indeed, organisations could not build excellence or achieve success in other fields if they did not have talented workers. As a result, employers were in a tough competition to attract and retain talented human resources in globalization and advances in technology, drastically affecting employment practices (Berthon et al., 2005; Matongolo et al., 2018).

Employers have typically sought progress with their recruiting outreach campaigns but have not in certain instances recognised the desires, expectations, and interests of potential workers well. Connections with prospects were therefore not created. There is also no way of determining how those who regard such campaign activities count as their "dream job" (Ewing et al., 2002; Fasih et al., 2019; Karjaluoto and Paakkonen, 2019). A significant change in the modern age is the emergence and development of employer branding. Moreover, some scholars (Kaur and Shah, 2021; Moroko and Uncles, 2008; Rampl and Kenning, 2014) claimed that both HRM and marketing were jointly generated the concept of employer branding.

In the past, it was pretty relevant in terms of the benefits that a company receives from good employer branding in terms of attracting and retaining talent (Barrow and Mosley, 2005; Bhasin et al., 2019; Weske et al., 2019). The future and current workers of a company profit from clear employer branding. Ritson (2002) claims that a good employer brand will lead to more substantial

talent and decreased employee retention costs. According to Barrow and Mosley (2011), employer branding increases commitment, retention, and employee satisfaction. In addition, Matongolo et al. (2018) contribute to the value of employer branding by explaining how job satisfaction may be improved through employer brands as employees have more reasons to perform and remain connected with the organisation.

The application of branding ideas to human resource management is known as employer branding (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004). Over time, other definitions have emerged, each emphasizing distinct aspects of employer branding. Some definitions stress the integration of marketing and human resource management domains; others look at the engagement of many stakeholders, yet others link it to objectives like HR and strategic benefits and employer identity. A summary of some of these definitions may be seen in table 2.1. According to the definitions, employer branding is a multi-dimensional concept, which has resulted in the development of many employer branding frameworks, as previously mentioned. Table 2.1 summarizes the definitions of employer branding presented by past researchers.

In addition, EB is a corporate theory that plays a part in all functions of organisation (Minchington 2010; Mlk, 2018). As attraction and leadership acquisition have become a top priority, branding job experience is crucial for existing and potential employees. EB controls several stakeholders' knowledge and expectations, which in turn will promote recruitment, growth, employee engagement, and employee success about "corporate competitiveness" (Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019; Kim et al., 2012; Sullivan 2004). EB reflects on the practical, economical, and psychological

benefits of work and identification with business while developing a picture of an employer (Knox and Freeman 2006).

Furthermore, employer branding has a long-term knowledge management approach (Mosley 2007). The attributes affecting the work experience are (1) employment, (2) the performance of the business, (3) the interpretation of the external picture, and (4) product/service functionality. The desirable qualities include a complex work experience, including financial award bundles, psychological needs satisfaction, and other tangible and intangible incentives (Bangwal and Tiwari, 2019; Edwards, 2010; Yadav et al., 2020). EB is influenced by prospective employees' aspirations, including organisational and desirable choices. If the company's age and place are included, desirable components include advancement, challenge assignments, creativity, business growth, job advancement, pay plan, the work climate, working-life balance, and businesses' credibility (Tuzuner and Yuksel 2009).

According to research, marketing and HRM responsibilities within a company must collaborate creatively to achieve effective employer branding (Ambler and Barrow 1996; Edwards 2010; Mlk, 2018). As a result, the EB should have a more coherent internal mix of three groups: 1) the management community, including vision, leadership, assistance, capability development. 2) the business group includes people, incentives, process improvement, and 3) the cross-functional group, which includes strategic relations, HR, and promotion (Ahmed et al., 2003). This synergy is achieved by consistent communication and promoting businesses and employment (Christian et al., 2018; Moroko and Uncles, 2008; Yoganathan et al., 2021).

The EB can achieve its goals by segmenting age, seniority, kind of work, worker lifecycle, tenure, and physical position using the Segmentation Targeting and Positioning (STP) method (Moroko and Uncles 2009). The EB agrees with the resource-based viewpoint that investing in human resources will result in competitive advantage (Backhaus and Tikoo 2004; Kim et al., 2012; Weske et al., 2019). Resources should be valuable, rare, imperfectly imitable, and difficult to substitute for renewable competitive advantages from the viewpoint of commodities (Chawla, 2020; Christian et al., 2018). Companies live and die based on their desire to draw the best talent (Leonard 2000; Weske et al., 2019). EB has positive impacts on the sustainability of the business by increasing employee satisfaction (Bangwal and Tiwari, 2019; Barrow and Mosley 2005; Edwards 2010; Gaddam 2008; Schlager et al., 2011).

2.3.1 Employer branding: a concept that is still emerging

While employer branding as an approach to human resource management is becoming more popular, there is still a scarcity of published research literature and studies on employer branding (Biswas and Suar 2016; Chawla, 2020; Karjaluoto and Paakkonen, 2019). Employee branding's theoretical foundations/assumptions (Carrington, 2007; Christian et al., 2018; Melin, 2005), as well as the concept's objective, framework, components, methods, and deliverables, remain a mystery to practitioners and management experts (Berry and Martin, 2018; Fasih et al., 2019; Yoganathan et al., 2021). The most widely quoted definition for the employee brand is the original definition of "functional, economic and psychological benefits given by jobs and identified with the corporation" given by Ambler and Barrow (1996, p. 8). This description has led to several additional research and debates about what is or is part of an employer brand.

Since Ambler and Barrow's original offering package or incentives, other analysts and academics have extended their definitions of these packages and introduced new types of offerings. Scholars (e.g., Ainspan et al., 2001; Heger, 2007; Kaur and Shah, 2021) suggested that such ideas are an employee value proposition of the company, an expression used to characterize the collection of qualities and advantages, such as those above, which actual and prospective employees will expect to benefit from their employment with a particular Organisation. However, to create a good and effective employer image, the employee value proposition (EVP) must be meaningful, distinct, and impelling. The endless potential to attract prospective employees and maintain and include current employees is more likely to arise in terms of its global vision, opinion, goals, and desires and describes the employer and separates him from his rivals (Banerjee et al., 2018; Christian et al., 2018; Karjaluo and Paakkonen, 2019).

Finally, the willingness of the company to satisfy the benefit offered to its employees constitutes the experience inside the organisation and the creation of an employer brand picture of the organisation (Eisenberg et al., 2001; Rosenthorn, 2009; Ruchika and Prasad, 2017). Consistent and practical communication of the distinct and essential principles expressed by the employer brand in combination with consistent execution of such values would improve the company's positive image as an employer. A similar interpretation of the term mentioned above is mirrored in a recent description of employer brand by Kaur and Shah (2021). They define the employer brand as a shared awareness among key stakeholders that they have created a quality work experience and a unique corporate identity that workers feel glad to promote. Additionally, adopting the employer branding concept is the need for every organisation because of the sharp surge in labour competitiveness (Berry and Martin, 2018, Dabirian et al., 2019; Karjaluo and Paakkonen, 2019).

2.4. RESEARCH ON EMPLOYER BRANDING

Employer branding includes the synergy of marketing practices and HRM practices, particularly, "science of branding" (Edwards 2010; Urbancova and Hudakova, 2017; Yadav et al., 2020). The study of Cable (2003) and Turban (2001) linked a job to a product advertised by a seller in a traditional situation of marketing, and a job seeker is considered as a potential customer. In this condition, employers (sellers) in the marketplace enhance the features of the product (a job) for its job seekers (consumers). The organisational endeavors attract potential employees, and the marketplace is publicized for talented employees (Dabirian et al., 2019; Molk, 2018).

The main goal of the employer branding process is to introduce a value proposition for an employee that establishes a set trait that organisational members consider attractive or valuable for employment. The decision-making literature suggests that compensatory-based decision-making occurs, in which the potential employee can be "traded-off" searched not to be valuable to examine employment suitability with a specific organisation. The specific employer traits highlighted in past research include job allows for work/life balance, the job allows for autonomy, Secure employment, Opportunity provided for career growth and professional development, Expert colleagues to work with, Culture that is friendly and positive, Performance opportunity and reputation of the organisation (Christian et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2012; Slavkovic et al. 2018).

Analysis in the field ranged from the introductory concepts and philosophical constructs to investigating the connection between employer branding and employee attraction and retention. The topics studied covered included: employer-related and employee characteristics that the applicants consider appealing, recruiting market equity strategy, contrasts of the exterior and

internal representations of the employer branding (Berthon et al., 2005; Collins and Stevens, 2002; Melin, 2005; McKenzie and Glynn, 2001). The reasons for the popularity of EB include employer branding impacts employees and organisation performance (Berthon et al., 2005; Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004; Biswas and Suar 2016; McLaren, 2011; Ogilvie, 2006).

Despite the demands for more study on this topic, relatively little applicable scholarly research on this issue has so far been identified (Backhaus, 2016; Christopher et al., 2019; Matongolo et al., 2018, Tumasjan et al., 2020; Vercic, 2021). A few studies refer, though not explicitly, to the impact of employer branding on organisation performance (Fulmer et al., 2003). Davies (2007) further explores the effect of employer branding on employee performance and organisation performance with mediators such as satisfaction, retention, and commitment. Anecdotal evidence suggests that employer branding positively impacts employee performance (Ainspan et al., 2001; Barrow and Mosley, 2006). However, these instances are uncommon, and the beneficial impacts are frequently self-reported by members of organisations without sufficient proof (Martin, 2007). As employer branding consultants continue to market the 'Stronger Commitment-Higher Engagement-Greater Results' guarantee (e.g., Nigel Wright, 2008), and as some companies across the world continue to buy it, management, academics, analysts have begun to question the presumption that employer branding is effective (Martin, 2007, Rosethorn and Mensink, 2007).

The call and the answer to further exploring the effect of employer branding on employee efficiency and organisational performance were undoubtedly justified. Firstly, the presumption of impact does not always fit the fact of influence; hence, more unbiased observational research is required to better view reality. Backhaus and Tikoo (2004), who conceptualize and study employer

branding, share a similar perspective among many other academics and employer branding subscribers (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004).

Furthermore, much of the existing employer branding literature (e.g., Ambler and Barrow, 1996; Ainspan et al., 2001; Bangwal and Tiwari, 2019; Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004; Barrow and Mosley, 2006; Miles and Mangold, 2005; Sartain and Schumman, 2006; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016) expect the enhancement in employee performance would be accomplished by an improvement in employee satisfaction, trust, and commitment through the effective employer branding. It is worth noting that it is indirect rather than direct to assume a positive relationship between effective employer branding and employee and organisational performance.

Successful employer branding strategies do not have a direct effect on employee and organisation performance. However, they may influence the mediators of employee performance, including satisfaction, retention, and commitment, which are believed to have a beneficial impact on workers' jobs, conduct, and overall performance (Biswas and Suar 2016; Yadav et al., 2020). Although several often believe that the total attitudes and performance of a company are the overall attitude of its workers (e.g., Fulmer et al., 2003; Ostroff, 1992), it is reasonable to think that enhancing the performance of several of its employees will increase the performance and productivity of an organisation (Tumasjan et al., 2020).

These assumptions are not shocking because, over the years, numerous human resource management debates and studies have reinforced the notion that: 1) efficient human resources techniques improve the efficiency and effectiveness of workers, as well as organisational,

productivity, and competitive advantages (i.e., Ghielen et al., 2018; Boxall, 1998; Heneman et al. 2007; Milkovich et al., 1988). However, some researchers believed that improved satisfaction (Cote 1999; Iaffaldano and Muchinsky 1985; Weiss and Cropanzano 1996) or commitment to the employer (Silvestro 2002) do not necessarily contribute to the more vital employee or organisation performance.

Should we support the premise that efficient employer branding will boost the organisation's performance by achieving effective mediators such as satisfaction, commitment, retention, and employee performance, what successful employer branding is in operation, and how these mediators are efficiently enhanced undecided? What criteria and considerations are needed for employer branding such that the targeted applicants can be drawn reliably and employee satisfaction, commitment, and retention actively enhanced? If employers give several kinds of employment incentives or a higher amount of benefits, does it satisfy, or would other reasons allow those employment potential benefits to materialise until they change? Are these causes or circumstances generalizable or unique to the organisation? What kind of problems does an organisation face? These issues are unanswered and need to be examined.

As information and implementation are moved from another area, it can be argued that the dynamic and interrelated essence of the roles of human resources and their relations with business practices such as brand creation and creating a positive image is not well known (Kateon and Macioschek, 2007). One may also specify a disparity in understanding between Marketing-Branding specialists and experts in human resources management regarding who or what the individual is in the organisation. Will an employee be treated as being the same as a client when it comes to enhancing

organisation performance? The Compact Oxford English Dictionary notes that 'customers' are 'persons who purchase products or services from a store or business.' One can infer from this that the newly attracted customers of an organisation had only purchased from the company; their retained customers still buy from the organisation (Stone and Liyanearachchi, 2007).

At the fundamental stage, consumers are inevitable and acknowledged players. Thus, as a company succeeds in recruiting potential consumers and maintaining current customers, it often succeeds in growing revenue and profits without extra effort. As such, companies may reasonably hope to solve the problem of success by solving customer attraction or retention (at least for profits and sales performance). The money from maintaining this great success would enable the company to solve other resource-requiring problems and performance.

When one assumes that retention of consumers increases the sales performance of a company and financial progress (Matongolo et al., 2018; Storbacka et al., 1994; Reichheld. 1996), one may presume that the exact inference should be extended to the retention of employees eventually it enhances organisational performance and competitiveness. However, through careful examination, it can be recognised that while retained consumers will contribute to increased performance for a company (repeat transactions over a longer time imply improved profits and sales), the same cannot be said about retained workers. When an employee works in a corporation, the company where the job is enabled does not immediately boost its revenue or other results.

In terms of achievement, the employee's efficiency will be adversely influenced by a variety of personal inhibitors (e.g., fitness, families, personal morale), technical (e.g., ability and competence

issues), and organisational (e.g., processes and management problems). Therefore, if an organisation is willing to recruit new employees and maintain current employees, it is not inherently effective in increasing revenue, sales, or other results without extra effort. Organisations also cannot hope to resolve the efficiency question merely by solving the attraction or retention of workers. In addition to discussing recruiting and retention, companies that want to address employee and organisational performance should do so.

2.5. EMPLOYER BRANDING PROCESS

Employer branding covers three fields: value proposition, internal marketing, and external marketing (Backhaus and Tikoo 2004; Bondarouk and Olivás-Lujan 2013). The employer value proposition includes insight into the organisation's culture, existing workers, and what the company will deliver. External marketing involves communicating the value proposition and building a distinctive brand to allow prospective applicants to work with the organisation. Internal marketing requires the observance of the commitments rendered and their incorporation into the corporate culture. CIPD describes four phases of employer brand growth. The first phase is to explore how stakeholders perceive the new employer brand.

The next phase is to evaluate, define and establish the workplace value proposition. What the business stands for, what it does and wants as an employer. The third step consists of introduction and coordination, employer brand implementation, final phase assessment, maintenance, and optimization. Mosley and Schmidt (2017) think the branding phase is more of a loop, an ongoing process (Figure 2.1). (Houghton, 2017). This period comprises eight steps. The first step results in understanding the corporate priorities and talent that the organisation requires to accomplish them.

It is then time for the new employer brand to be tested by prospective and current employees. The third stage is the concept of the EVP.

After that, the organisation must develop an employer brand structure, often called an employer brand guideline which, for example, includes corporate logo, artwork, and other visual design elements. The fifth stage involves producing interactive content. Then it is time for prospective candidates, such as business career pages, work boards, and social media, via the chosen channels. The seventh stage includes evaluating the performance and determining what works and what does not. In the final stage, the employer identity plan and recruiting initiatives must be changed to boost employer branding outcomes and perform the same steps. Mosley (2014) notes that the long-term power of the employer brand will execute on and gradually expand on the commitments provided by the employer brand.

Figure 2.1: Employer Branding Process

Source: Mosley and Schmidt (2017)

2.6. DEFINING THE ELEMENTS OF THE EMPLOYER BRANDING

The following section discusses the various dimensions of employer branding as identified through the literature review.

2.6.1. Dimensions of employer branding

During the analysis of the dimensional framework of the employer branding, counted literature on the employer brand centered on "recruitment" aspects for prospective workers when establishing their parameters (Tanwar and Prasad 2016). According to the research undertaken by Maxwell and Knox (2009), Lievens et al. (2007), Edwards (2010), and Tanwar and Prasad (2016), potential and current employees have different views of the employer brand. Maxwell and Knox (2009) proposed that academics could rely on empirical studies when researching aspects of employer branding from current workers' perspectives and acknowledged their effect and influence on employee perceptions, attitudes, and behaviour. In previous literature, different dimensional constructs were illustrated by most studies conducted with potential employees as the population for the study (Berthon et al., 2005; Kucherov and Smokish, 2016; Schlager et al. 2011; Sivertzen et al., 2013).

As Barrow and Mosley (2005) illustrated, an organisation's employer branding may be enhanced by emphasizing the main feature of its culture. Salaries and incentives represent an attractive pay system and a compensation plan. As Barrow and Mosley (2005) have indicated, successful coordination with various types of rewards improves the employer brand. It can be argued that employer branding dimensions, particularly in selecting an employer, include organisational culture, salaries and benefits, opportunities, Corporate social responsibility, and work-life balance.

Agrawal and Swaroop (2009) show that the attractiveness of employer branding across various industry sectors in developing countries is mainly affected by organisational culture and salary.

Berthon et al. (2005) established variables related to employer brand attractiveness, drawing on historical field studies and focus groups, asking participants to define factors they deem significant when evaluating prospective employers. The authors describe vital variables adopting traditional scale-developing procedures: economic benefit (e.g., pay and incentives) and social value (e. g., corporate culture),

Additionally, Srivastava and Bhatnagar (2010) have also established drivers of employer brand attraction from an analysis with participants from developing countries, which identifies eight factors: consideration (e.g., organisation's interest in its workers), the enablement (e.g., enabling employees to contribute their abilities), job development (e.g., prospects for advancement), the integrity and fairness of their jobs (e.g., Several additional studies described career characteristics as a composite metric that were significant for the appeal of employers' brands (e.g., Cable and Turbo, 2003; Collins, 2007; Collins and Stevens, 2002; Gomes and Neves, 2011; Knox and Freeman, 2006).

However, these scales do not authorize specific forecasts for specific organisation characteristics to be attractive employer brands (Tanwar and Prasad, 2017). A variety of studies also show that the organisation culture, incentives, and CSR are a part of company associations and may also influence the appeal of employer brand (e.g., Cable and Turban, 2003; Collins, 2007; Lievens and Highhouse, 2003; Lievens et al., 2007; Rampl and Kenning, 2014). The related studies reveal

various conclusions concerning the impact of employer brand dimensions on employer brand attractiveness.

The extent and importance of employers' brand dimensions have been shown to vary across various sectors (e.g., banking or the military context) or different cultural contexts. It may also be claimed that characteristics related to employer brands can typically be different across different industries. For example, physical exercises may be necessary for industries such as the military environment, although consumer contact would not be crucial. However, the case will most definitely be changed in the financial sector, like banks. This perspective is also expressed in Lievens and Highhouse's (2003) study and Lievens's (2007), who carried out more research on the qualities of their workers in the particular sectors they studied. Table 2.2 summarizes highlights the dimensions of employer branding explored by researchers in the past.

2.6.1.1. Defining Organisation Culture

The organisational culture was defined as "a shared value mechanism that separates one entity from another through representatives of an organisation" (Robbins, 2001). According to Ravasi and Schultz's (2006) report, organizing culture is characterized as a "collection of assumptions regulating what takes place in an organisation by correctly determining suitable actions for various circumstances" (p. 24). Business society draws the interest of academics in terms of human resources management. According to Odom et al. (1990), the company's culture strengthens the actions and conduct of its employees.

The critical challenge for professionals in the organisation is establishing and maintaining a supportive and efficient organisational culture that affects employee quality of work life. Gifford

et al. (2002) concluded that a positive and welcoming workplace culture improves employee involvement and commitment to the employer brand. In the research by Backhaus and Tikoo (2004), corporate culture was an indicator of employer branding, and the favourable association between employer branding and corporate culture was studied. In addition, the organisation culture increases employee commitment and attachment to the employer brand (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004). Thus, the present research integrates the organisational culture as the striking component of the employer branding inspired by Tanwar and Prasad's study (2016).

Employer branding improves an enterprise's organisational culture, and firms with strong internal cultures perform even better (CIPD, 2015; Wheeler et al., 2006). Ind (1997) notes that a company's culture must be successfully conveyed to maximize cultural characteristics by focusing on the market image of an organisation (Hieronimus et al., 2005). Sengupta et al. (2015) advocated this, describing organisations with strong norms and values in their organisation's ethos as a source of inspiration for individual acts, enhancing retention rate and employees' motivation to work (Alvesson, 2013).

In addition, Backhaus and Tikoo (2004) suggested an “Employer Branding framework,” which indicates that employee retention, when they associate with the organisation's ethos, is better if workers have views, behaviours, and values associated with the basic principles of the organisation. The model further stresses that corporate culture depends on the employer's branding, and retention may be influenced by a behavioural dimension that contributes to corporate culture (Backhaus and Tikoo 2004). The behavioural component that ties employee retention to branding and organisational culture also forms how employees act, as employees become interested in an

organisation's culture and begin to adopt culturally related behaviours (Foreman and Argenti, 2005).

Furthermore, its culture is automatically shaped by its market interests to introduce workers to the employer's brand standards and allow them to achieve an exclusive culture, thereby establishing a corporate culture that can not match competitors (Melewar et al., 2012). The marketing of the company identity through company culture is assumed to improve productivity by promoting the idea of exclusivity and the readiness of an individual to continue with an organisation (Inabinett and Ballaro, 2014; Melewar et al., 2012).

Additional research on the culture of an enterprise indicates that culture motivates individuals to follow a citizen's actions (Golden et al., 2002; Tyler and Blader, 2000), encouraging them to behave as a representation of the culture of the organisation, prompting them to participate in the "brand" (Haslam et al., 2000; Ind, 1997; Maxwell and Knox, 2009). The cultural component of an organisation means good ties between employees, job security, and flexible hours. Data shows that people are inclined to join a firm that offers an atmosphere that fits their characteristics (Boon et al., 2011; Harinck et al., 2000).

Brands such as Microsoft, Vodafone, and Reuters have made significant efforts to shape their organisational culture to reflect their core values (Barrow and Mosley, 2011). As Aiken et al. (2000) indicated, organisational culture can affect employee attitude towards the company. Organisational culture is an essential factor in a worker's decision to work for a specific company. Furthermore, Tuzuner and Yuksel's analytical work (2009) showed that the employers' view of

employer attractiveness is distinguished by gender. Women leaned more towards a non-competitive job atmosphere, while men favoured a more brand-oriented workspace (Tuzuner and Yuksel, 2009). In its study on the employer brand and its elements, the Corporate Leadership Council (1999) included organisational culture as an essential component that leads to brand power.

2.6.1.2. Defining Corporate Social Responsibilities

Carroll (1979) defines CSR as "the social responsibility of business, embracing the economic, legal, discretionary, and ethical expectations that society has on the organisation at any particular moment."(p.9). In addition, Corporate Social Responsibility can be defined as an organisation's mandate to respect society's legal and social limits and ensure its operations and products are aimed towards sustainable and equitable development (Haque, 2018). there are certain voluntary or discretionary actions that a society may not demand but expects organisations operating within its jurisdiction.

Additionally, The motivation to perform such actions is based on the reciprocity of the financial power that the society has afforded organisations to have. CSR is seen as giving back to society, not so much in a financial way, but by identifying and assisting in preventing or reducing social ills. These ideas led to the conception of CSR, which has expanded from the “giving back” concept to include the betterment of society and commitment to act in a manner that does not contradict social culture (Ward et al., 2007; Rahim, 2014).

According to the literature, CSR improves the organisation's brand image and reputation among actual and potential employees (Kim et al., 2010; Kotler and Lee, 2008; Suliman and Khatib, 2014). According to Schiebel and Pöchtrager (2003), a growing number of businesses have realized the CSR implementation to boost organisation performance. Backhaus and Tikoo (2004) believed that EB helps recruit top personnel and help organisations make it an "employer of choice." CSR further aids a firm in attracting, motivating, and retaining talented human resources (Greening and Turban, 2000; Rayton et al., 2007). Furthermore, Suliman and Al-Khatib (2014) conducted empirical research that revealed the significance of CSR in molding businesses' brands, with the 'Market Place Policies' component of CSR playing a pivotal role in determining employer brand. As a result, a company's employer brand may be enhanced by including CSR in its structure.

2.6.1.3. Defining the Work-life balance

Organisations have also begun integration into their respective employer branding strategies and Work-Life Balance (WLB) practices. According to literature, WLB tactics will help a company boost its employer brand, contributing to improved retention of workers (Barrow and Mosley, 2005; Hudson, 2005). As Barrow and Mosley (2005) suggested, it would be complicated for an organisation to establish its employer brand without including WLB practices. Research by Hillebrandt and Ivens (2013) has established WLB as an essential component for forming an attractive employer brand.

Over recent years, the work-life balance has gained significant attention as an essential talent management phenomenon. Organisations have also begun to integrate WLB tactics into their brands. Work-life-balancing techniques aid workers in managing and combining work-life and

non-work dimensions (Felstead et al., 2002). WLB techniques have been proposed in the literature to help a company boost its employer image, contributing to further job satisfaction (Barrow and Mosley, 2011; Hudson, 2005). As Barrow and Mosley (2005) suggested, it would be challenging for a company to establish its employer identity without including WLB. McDonald et al. (2005) also described WLB as one of the critical variables leaving pay and reputation aside in terms of factors that affect employer attractiveness.

In addition, research carried out by Hillebrandt and Ivens (2013) claimed that WLB is one of the most important components of an organisation's employer brand policy. They further believe that an organisation can improve its employer's brand image by implementing WLB strategies that help employees to manage their personal affairs other than work. The organisation needs to show concern for employees' family and social setup to offer flexible working hours. Work-life balance, one of the employer branding dimensions, is part of the broader field of the company's moral employee behaviour (Renaud et al., 2016).

Moreover, WLB can be explained as an indirect extrinsic incentive for three subcategories of employment benefits: welfare plans, employee facilities, and time benefits which include breaks, sick days, holiday periods (Firfiray and Mayo, 2017). In reaction to the latest developments and employee expectancies, in the case of time-related compensation organisations, have gradually expanded their bid (Levering and Moskowitz, 2007). Researchers (Firfiray and Mayo 2017; Renaud et al., 2016; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019) proposed that a WLB plan may provide child-related benefits (financial assistance in emergency, maternity leave, and childcare facilities),

time/schedule (such as flexibility time, shortened work week and job sharing), well-being programs with employee counseling services.

Given the tremendous burden of individuals in the workplace today (Podsakoff et al., 2007), the availability of WLB may imply a quality of life and improve the attractiveness of candidates to future employers. Casper and Buffardi (2004) find that work-life activities such as flexible scheduling and dependent treatment are universally attractive to the effects of recruiting. Uggerslev et al. (2012) also shown that WLB systems are a unique aspect of the difference of an applicant's attractiveness to a potential employer.

A research carried out by Firfiray and Mayo (2017) showed that employees are interested in a business that provides excellent WLB policies. In addition, Kerry Schofield (2013) demonstrates that a "fit" between co-workers and superiors is also significant. Job seekers are linked to an organisation that blends their personality with other workers (Kristof-Brown et al., 2005). Culture is an essential element of employer branding by workers regarding their employer preference (Barrow and Mosley 2011).

Similarly, Thompson et al. (2015) stated that mixing high Flex and Flexi-space practices yielded the maximum degree of expected organisational support and organisational attractiveness that individuals work more than just payments and are intrinsically satisfied (Grant and Parker, 2009). Furthermore, supplementary work benefits such as WLB are socially responsible elements that job seekers prioritize (LaPlante, 2004; Turban and Greening, 1996), and organisations that provide WLB are thus expected to be enticing, in addition to standard job benefits.

According to Barrow and Mosley's studies (2011), Hudson (2005) addressed the likelihood of companies improving their employer brand, which leads to the retention of workers. Employer branding activities include work-life balance strategies as a vital element (Barrow and Mosley, 2011). A study by McDonald et al. (2005) found that the work-life balance substantially decides the decision of workers to continue with a company, apart from the reputation and wage aspect. In addition, the Hillebrandt and Ivens report (2013) considered the work-life balance to be an essential aspect influencing employer branding. Tanwar and Prasad (2016) suggested that employer reputation could be strengthened by keeping work hours flexible, and an acceptable work-life balance could affect the employee's intent to remain with the firm. According to Clark (2000), the work-life balance is an acceptable balance between the work and personal lives of the employee.

According to existing literature, employees' performance has been demonstrated to improve when they practice work-life balance at work (Cegarra-Leiva et al., 2012; Wayne et al., 2004; Virick et al., 2007;). Multiple facets of work-life balance were developed in the Hartel et al. research (2007), including flexible working hours, sharing, care services, and parental leave. Any interference between a worker's work and personal life leads to dissatisfaction in the employee-employer relationship (Pasewark and Viator, 2006). According to the Karatepe and Uludag (2007) findings and Namasivayam and Zhao (2007), the various components of the work-life balance significantly influence employee retention commitment and satisfaction.

2.6.1.4. Defining the salary and incentives.

Employer branding is a rainbow with various colours, and one of the most dominant colours is incentives. One of the most obvious reasons to join any job is economic benefits. Organisations with high salary packages and other benefits catch more attraction by potential employees. Organisations with Strong employer branding continually offer high salaries and incentives and match the salary and other incentives with competitors. Employees keep close eyes to market trends and keep on data related to incentives offered by competitors for the same position on which they are currently working (Tanwar and Kumar, 2019).

Salary and incentives are essential aspects of employment. According to previous research, the performance of a specific organisation can be established by an employee with the organisation that provides adequate pay and benefits (Cable and De Rue, 2002; Noe et al., 2003). Research also shows that workers are well connected to companies with fair salaries and benefits. Employees follow a salary-based company (Cable and Judge, 1994). When their desires are satisfied through monetary or non-monetary rewards, they know that the corporation truly trusts its workers, which is often a spiritual boost.

Compensation was the major topic of discussion when it came to economic worth. Individuals who are focused on economic worth were not just concerned with money but also with benefits like healthcare, pension contributions, job stability, and other quantifiable benefits (Dabrian et al., 2019; Rampl, 2014; Tanwar and Prasad 2017). According to employer branding authors (e.g., Maheshwari et al., 2017; Backhaus, 2016; Drury, 2016; Wilden, Gudergan, & Lings, 2010; Näppä,

Farshid & Foster, 2014), money was a reason that makes employees stay, or could be a reason to leave.

2.7 SUMMARY

One of the key objectives of the chapter was to conduct a literature review on employer branding concepts, EB models, and empirical studies in the arena in terms of synthesising literature to support the development of the conceptual framework of the study. The dimensions that the literature has served to examine are within the context of defining employer branding. The literature concerning EB exists as a concept academically and also in industry. The academic concepts are essential in providing a contextual backdrop for how EB practices can be applied and the processes and steps that stakeholders need to take to ensure that the efforts towards EB are beneficial to economic ends and maintain the critical social and environmental balances that exist. Theoretical base, definition, and explanation of the concept of employer branding, with dimensions, were presented in this chapter.

CHAPTER III

THEORATICALFRAMEWORK

3.1. INTRODUCTION

The discussion was summarized as the employer branding is evolving steadily and offers an enormous potential for study based on the findings in the literature review in Chapter II. Employer branding research is challenging, according to the literature, and has a variety of outcomes based on the research context and settings. The dearth of theoretical sources on employer branding was addressed in this work by analyzing employer branding in a broader context and considering its consequences. The review identifies specific areas where more study is needed. The current research focuses on employer branding and its effects on employee choice and organisation performance.

Chapter II highlighted a set of factors as dimensions of employer branding and illustrated the outcomes of the employer branding simultaneously. The thirteen constructs are considered in this study: organisation culture, development and growth opportunities, work-life balance, salary and incentives, equality and justice, employer branding, person organisation-fit, organisation commitment, job satisfaction, employee retention, employer brand advocacy, employee performance, employer of choice, and organisation performance. Section 3.2 to 3.5 consisted of research hypotheses related to employer branding and POF, JS, and ER. Whereas, hypothesis related to person organisation fit and employer of choice POF is in Section 3.6. Section 3.7 to 3.8 includes hypotheses related to organisation commitment and EBA and EP. Sections 3.9 to 3.10 presented a hypothesis related to job satisfaction and employee retention to EP. In addition, hypotheses related to EBA to ECO and EP to OP are in sections 3.11 to 3.12. In the end, the conceptual model is presented (section 3.13).

3.2. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMPLOYER BRANDING AND PERSON ORGANISATION FIT

The person-organisation fit may be defined as a match between an employee's views, values, and culture and the employer's image on the one hand (Christiaans, 2013). The person-organisation fit viewpoint has been widely utilized in conjunction with employer brand research to describe the amount of congruence between employers and workers (Lauver et al., 2001). According to previous research on the person-organisation fit, potential workers evaluate an organisation's brand to their own beliefs, needs, and ideas, and a connection between the two generates more robust attractiveness to the organisation for the individual (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004; Schneider, 1987). According to Backhaus and Tikoo (2004), potential workers evaluate the employer brand's image and relate it to their own beliefs and characteristics.

A strong employer brand can recruit individuals with characteristics that are a good match for the organisation. The employer brand serves as a method for communicating its values to its stakeholders, allowing workers to ensure that they are compatible with its culture (Srivastava and Bhatnagar, 2010; Parmar, 2014). Foster et al. (2010) also claimed that the employer brand could attract employees who share the company's values and culture. As a result, the employer brand aids employees in determining whether or not they are a good fit for an organisation based on their beliefs and personal qualities. It improves their person-organisation fit, and they believe their beliefs and talents align with the ideals and needs of the organisation.

H1: Employer branding has a significant positive effect on person organisation fit.

3.3 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMPLOYER BRANDING AND ORGANISATION COMMITMENT

Although most organisational academics believe that having a committed workforce benefits a company, there is a lack of commitment (Meyer, 2014). Given its relative prominence within the literature on employee commitment, the idea of employee commitment in this study is interpreted through the well-established three-component model proposed by Meyer and colleagues (Allen and Meyer, 1990; Meyer and Allen, 1991). The past researchers identified three essential components of commitment to distinguish between the many mindsets that are thought to constitute commitment: affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuation commitment (Allen and Meyer, 1990; Meyer and Herscovitch, 2001).

By labeling these mindsets as components rather than types of commitment, it was acknowledged that employees could experience all three to different degrees (Meyer, 2014). Likewise, their implications for on-the-job work behaviours can vary due to the specific mindset, even though all three negatively influence voluntary employee turnover (Meyer and Herscovitch, 2001; Meyer et al., 2002). Although the three different commitment components can be measured separately, the present study assesses commitment as one concept and does not distinguish between them. If the context in which employees work meets these needs, employees' intention to remain can be increased, and thus a robust affective commitment to the organisation is created (Meyer, 2014). In contrast, when employees' needs are not satisfied, social obligations (normative commitment) and perceived costs (continuance commitment) may be the only reasons why they stay with their employer (Meyer, 2014).

Another link between SDT and commitment can be drawn based on the evidence that both may be extended to provide explanations for any form of intentional behaviour such as turnover or attendance (Meyer et al., 2004; Meyer, 2014). Meyer et al. (2004) identified that intrinsic and extrinsic motivation might influence commitment and strengthen or weaken the various mindsets. Employees with a solid affective commitment to their organisation tend to experience intrinsic motivation (Gagné et al., 2008; Gagné et al., 2010; Meyer et al., 2004; Meyer et al., 2012). Employees who constantly experience autonomy at work are likely to develop intrinsic motivation and a high level of affective commitment to their employer (Meyer, 2014).

On the contrary, employees who have a strong continuance commitment and only stay with their organisation due to lacking alternatives or other possible costs for leaving tend to experience extrinsic motivation (Gagné et al., 2010; Meyer et al., 2004; Meyer et al., 2012). At the same time, a robust normative commitment of employees is likely to involve intrinsic motivation in their daily tasks (Gagné et al., 2008; Gagné et al., 2010; Meyer et al., 2012). Since literature reveals that the nature and degree of employees' organisational commitment may also impact their motivational states during task performance, the causality between commitment and motivation can be reciprocal (Meyer, 2014).

Previous studies revealed a positive relationship between employer branding and employee commitment (Hanin et al., 2013; Kimpakorn and Tocquer, 2009; Lelono and Martidanty, 2013). Hence, it is stated that the signals of the employer brand have a direct effect on employee commitment (Backhaus, 2016; Schlager et al., 2011; Slavkovic et al., 2018). By considering the five values of employer branding, the following hypotheses on the relationship between employer

branding and employee commitment were developed. Among the five values, Schlager et al. (2011) found that social values positively impact organisational commitment. The nature of social value can determine whether an employee will be committed to or leave the company (Ito et al., 2013; Kashyap and Verma, 2018).

Companies that support a respectful environment, friendly relationships among co-workers, and a people-first attitude can enhance employee commitment (Kashyap and Verma, 2018; Schlager et al., 2011). Furthermore, factors such as having good relationships with superiors and co-workers were crucial for enhancing organisational commitment (Gaylard et al., 2005; Kashyap and Verma, 2018). In turn, employees can feel connected and appreciated by others in the organisation, thus fulfilling their need for relatedness and enhancing their commitment (Greguras and Diefendorff, 2009; Meyer, 2014). Conversely, when experiencing supervisory behaviours such as intimidating subordinates, using aggressive body language, humiliating subordinates publicly, or withholding critical information, employees tend to be less committed to the organisation (Kashyap and Verma, 2018)

Previous studies revealed a positive relationship between employer branding and employee commitment (Hanin et al., 2013; Ito et al., 2013; Kashyap and Verma, 2018; Kimpakorn and Tocquer, 2009; Lelono and Martidanty, 2013). Among the various dimensions of employer branding, Schlager et al. (2011) found that organisation culture has a substantial positive impact on organisational commitment. The nature of culture and social values can determine whether an employee will be committed to or leave the company (Ito et al., 2013; Kashyap and Verma, 2018). Companies that support a respectful environment, friendly relationships among co-workers, and a

people-first attitude can enhance employee commitment (Schlager et al., 2011; Kashyap and Verma, 2018).

Furthermore, factors such as having good relationships with superiors and co-workers were crucial for enhancing organisational commitment (Gaylard et al., 2005; Kashyap and Verma, 2018). In turn, employees can feel connected and appreciated by others in the organisation, thus fulfilling their need for relatedness and enhancing their commitment (Greguras and Diefendorff, 2009; Meyer, 2014). In line with these findings, organisation culture is expected to be positively related to employee commitment.

Another aspect that is considered a predictor of employee commitment is the economic value of an organisation (Berthon et al., 2005; Matongolo et al., 2018; Özçelik, 2015; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016b). A firm's economic value is associated with the economic benefits, including salaries and incentives the employer provides the workforce. The economic value that includes above-average salary, compensation package, job security, and promotional opportunities was found to support higher levels of employee commitment (Heilmann et al., 2013; Matongolo et al., 2018; Schlager et al., 2011). Moreover, a fair number of holidays and appropriate retirement benefits are considered part of an organisation's economic value and enhance organisational commitment (Heilmann et al., 2013; Matongolo et al., 2018; Özçelik, 2015; Schlager et al., 2011).

Since the base salary represents recognizing the employee's value to the organisation, it also reflects its importance to the company (Monteiro de Castro et al., 2016). If companies manage to offer competitive remuneration and recognition to their workforce, they can facilitate employee

behaviours and attitudes favouring the company, such as higher intention to remain with the employer and employee commitment.

Research also argues for a positive relationship between development value and employee commitment (Kashyap and Verma, 2018; Schlager et al., 2011; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a). Development value, which includes development and growth opportunities through training, mentoring, and an empowering environment, is crucial for employee commitment (Hadi and Ahmen, 2008). By providing employees with development value, employees become motivated to remain with the organisation for a longer duration (Hadi and Ahmen, 2018; Kashyap and Verma, 2018).

Armstrong (2009) also highlights the relevance of training and development since they develop a sense of progression among the workforce, enhancing organisational commitment (Kong et al., 2015; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016b). Employees showed a greater willingness to engage themselves in their work, which led to increased commitment to the organisation when they perceive the company to support their careers (Tanwar and Prasad, 2016b). Therefore, opportunities for career growth and the development of a favourable working environment are indicators for employee commitment (Backhaus, 2016; Schlager et al., 2011; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a). Hence, it is stated that employer branding directly affects employee commitment (Kong et al., 2015; Schlager et al., 2011; Slavkovic et al., 2018).

H2: Employer branding has a significant positive effect on organisation commitment.

3.4 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMPLOYER BRANDING AND EMPLOYEE RETENTION

Due to the increasing workforce shortage, companies are working hard to attract, hire and maintain talents (Chhabra and Sharma, 2014; Lievans and Highhouse, 2003). Employer branding is the tool that helps companies to explain how they separate themselves from rivals (Ito et al., 2013). Similarly, employer branding improves organisational performance in the HRM context by assisting organisations in differentiating themselves from competitors in recruiting, commitment, and retention (Chhabra and Sharma, 2014; Russell and Brannan, 2016). Fernon (2008) further argued that employer branding would continue to attract workers if it is adequately done by providing a culture that encourages employees to own the brand.

Moreover, EB raises their loyalty and chances of working with the company for a longer time (Cable and Graham, 2000; Jain and Bhatt, 2015). In Gaddam (2008, p. 47) "Employer Brand Model," which defines satisfaction, commitment, retention, attraction, the significant increase in performance of a company can all be related to the employer brand., In acknowledgment that employer branding boosts employee satisfaction and retention and improves performance, Allen et al. (2010) endorse the model. Employees then compliment the organisation, advise others, and keep true to the company for a longer time (CIPD, 2015; Holbeche and Matthew, 2012; Mosley, 2007).

Organisations must now benchmark themselves against competitors, competitive employers by surveys such as the ISR and the Best Employer Survey (Barrow and Mosley, 2005), which would allow retention levels to rise and build a competitive advantage in order to offset the growth in the broad list of potential employers available for employees in the business world (Love and Singh

2011). Morgan (2008) and Backhaus and Tikoo (2004) advocate using surveys to brand employers themselves and say that surveys can periodically be conducted because they distinguish the right employers and give them an incentive to look at new talents. Nevertheless, Mosley (2007) indicated that benchmarking is a crucial factor in creating a good employer brand to ensure superior job experience. It should not overwhelm organisations by competing with competitors.

It is more critical that meaning is conveyed internally and that the brand is maintained to satisfy employees' expectations and wants, and that the value is interconnected within the company (CIPD, 2015; Foster et al., 2010; Mosley, 2007). The importance of companies acquiring, hiring, and retaining talent has been recognized due to increasing labor shortages (Chhabra and Sharma 2014; Lievans and Highhouse 2003). Employer branding companies should be known as it is the tool that helps companies to demonstrate how they differ from rivals (Ito et al., 2013).

Employer branding further enhances workplace success in recruiting, retention, and participation within the HR environment by helping them distinguish themselves from rivals (Chhabra and Sharma 2014; Russell and Brannan, 2016). Fernon (2008) further argued that employer branding, if handled well, will attract better workers by creating a culture in which staff can experience the brand in different ways, such as growth and promotion, which increases their chances of retention with the company (Cable and Graham, 2000; Jain and Bhatt, 2015).

'Employer Brand Model,' which shows that engagement, retention, performance, satisfaction, and attractiveness can all be related to the employer brand, shows the positive outcome of employer branding on a company (Gaddam, 2008). The paradigm is endorsed by Allen, Bryant, and

Vardaman (2010), acknowledging that employer branding improves staff retention. In addition, employer branding increases employee morals, and it was proposed that workers who love working with a company stick with the organisation longer (Matthews and Holbeche, 2012). Therefore, it is hypothesised,

H3: Employer branding has a significant positive effect on employee retention.

3.5 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMPLOYER BRANDING AND JOB SATISFACTION

Over the last few decades, satisfaction has gotten much attention from scholars and practitioners (Curtis and Glacken, 2014; Davies, 2008; Kosteas, 2011). Part of the rising interest in employee job satisfaction is linked to employee job-related behaviour (Chi and Gursoy, 2009; Kosteas, 2011). Scholars have discovered that satisfied workers are less likely to leave a firm, are less absent, and are more productive at work (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004; Chi and Gursoy, 2009; Curtis and Glacken, 2014; Kosteas, 2011).

Companies can uncover workers' work-related preferences and participate in staff retention by studying job satisfaction (Kosteas, 2011). Employees that are satisfied in their present position are more likely to stick around. Job satisfaction, according to Locke (1976), is "a pleasurable or a positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job" (as cited in Saari and Judge, 2004). Locke (1976) stressed the relevance of affection and cognition, which relates to one's sentiments or thoughts while defining contentment. As a result, when employees evaluate their jobs, they consider their thoughts and feelings (Saari and Judge, 2004). Employees' perceptions of their skills can influence their degree of satisfaction (Sell and Cleal, 2011). The literature has primarily accepted Herzberg's (Herzberg et al., 1959) Two-Factor Theory of Motivation to gauge employee satisfaction (e.g., Richmond and McCroskey, 1979; Rust et al., 1996; Matzler and Renzl,

2007; Raziq and Maulabakhsh, 2015). This motivational theory distinguishes factors in the workplace that might cause employee happiness or discontent (Dartey-Baah and Amoako, 2011).

Research has found that one of the most notable facets of employee satisfaction is the nature of the work itself (Antoncic and Antoncic, 2011; Saari and Judge, 2004). This facet includes the variety, challenges, and scope of the work (Saari and Judge, 2004; Schlager et al., 2011), which the Two-Factor Theory of Motivation refers to as a motivator of employee satisfaction (Herzberg et al., 1959). Further, relationships among employees and those between employees and supervisors have been identified as two facets of employee satisfaction (Antoncic and Antoncic, 2011; Gaylard et al., 2005; Kashyap and Verma, 2018; Spector, 1985).

While more recent studies have argued that employee relationships are a facet of satisfaction (e.g., Antoncic and Antoncic, 2011; Gaylard et al., 2005; Kashyap and Verma, 2018), Herzberg et al. (1959) considered this facet to be a hygiene factor which can only lead to either dissatisfaction or no dissatisfaction. Besides employee relationships, several scholars claim hygiene factors such as salary, promotion, benefits, and rewards to be crucial for employee satisfaction (Antoncic and Antoncic, 2011; Özçelik, 2015). Further, operating procedures and communication were facets of employee satisfaction (Spector, 1985; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a). These facets refer to the company's cleanness of communication and policies (Spector, 1985), which can also be considered hygiene factors (Herzberg et al., 1959).

Research has identified employee satisfaction as the desired positive outcome of employer branding (Schlager et al., 2011; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016b). Hence, it is stated that the signals of

the employer brand have a direct effect on employee satisfaction (Backhaus, 2016; Schlager et al., 2011; Slavkovic et al., 2018). By considering the following five values of employer branding, the relationship between employer branding and employee satisfaction is developed.

Regarding the social value of employer branding, literature has found that this dimension influences employee satisfaction (Bjerke et al., 2007; Saari and Judge, 2004; Schlager et al., 2011). Employees' relationships with co-workers and supervisors are essential aspects of assessing employee satisfaction (Bjerke et al., 2007; Gaylard et al., 2015; Saari and Judge, 2004; Schlager et al., 2011). When employees perceive the feelings of support, trust, and openness among co-workers and supervisors, higher levels of employee satisfaction will be achieved (Davies, 2008; Humphrey et al., 2007). Further, a good organisational climate and culture can enhance employee satisfaction (Antoncic and Antoncic, 2011). It has also been found that employees dissatisfied with a company's social value are more likely to leave the organisation (Kashyap and Verma, 2018).

Another value that emerged as a satisfier among employees is the economic value provided by an organisation (Antoncic and Antoncic, 2011; Kashyap and Verma, 2018; Schlager et al., 2011; Steers et al., 2004). A higher salary, in general, was identified as being directly related to increased employee satisfaction (Schlager et al., 2011). Besides the base salary, receiving financial rewards and recognition was a significant predictor of employee satisfaction (Kashyap and Verma, 2018; Steers et al., 2004).

Furthermore, the benefit structure within a company was revealed to be an indicator of satisfaction (Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a). If the workforce perceives its employer to offer fair and attractive

benefits such as paid time off, medical coverage, or an appropriate number of holidays, employees are more satisfied (Schlager et al., 2011; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a). While monetary aspects play a crucial role in employee satisfaction, non-monetary factors, such as job security, are also positively related to employee satisfaction (Antoncic and Antoncic, 2011; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a). Hence, employees feel satisfied when they perceive themselves to be secure in pursuing their work in the future.

Aside from the previously mentioned values, research has found development value to be one of the most prominent factors for employee satisfaction (Schlager et al., 2011; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016b). The organisation's development and growth opportunities are directly linked to employee satisfaction (Antoncic and Antoncic, 2011; Gaylard et al., 2005; Matongolo et al., 2018; Schlager et al., 2011). These opportunities are significant to employees as they create a sense of progression, which results in higher levels of satisfaction (Schlager et al., 2011; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016b). Companies that ensure that employees experience learning through several development programs and assess and support each employee's development or career needs will enhance employee satisfaction (Matongolo et al., 2018; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016b). Further, training and development through workshops and conferences impacted employee satisfaction (Tanwar and Prasad, 2016b).

H4: Employer branding has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction.

3.6. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PERSON ORGANISATION FIT AND EMPLOYER OF CHOICE

The person-organisation fit, which is a match between employee values and the organisation and is also one of the results of the employer brand, is an antecedent of the EOC (Tanwar and Kumar,

2019). The person-organisation fit has its roots in psychology, whereas brand emotions are mainly derived from consumer branding literature. As a result, it is worth seeing if the person-organisation fit functions as a bridge between the employer brand and the EOC. Building on the previous study's findings, this one claims that person-organisation fit might operate as a mediating variable between employer brand characteristics and EOC status or that it can be an antecedent of EOC (Tanwar and Kumar, 2019).

Consequently, the current study is a step forward since it claims that employer brand attributes, essential for an organisation to become an EOC, must construct a person-organisation fit, leading to EOC status formation. As a result, the current study contends that the person-organisation fit must operate as a complete mediator of an employer brand's dimensions.

H5: person organisation fit has a significant positive effect on the employer of choice.

3.7. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANISATION COMMITMENT AND EMPLOYER BRAND ADVOCACY

Brand advocacy is created as the customer speaks favourable about the brand and helps accelerate the recognition and popularity of new products. People who post or talk favourably about the brand are brand ambassadors or brand advocates (Commander, 2007; Keller, 1993). The brand advocacy theory can be generalized to HRM. It was suggested that ample information about the company should be accessible to an employee as a brand advocate. Literature indicates that the organisation's commitment helps grow the organisation's activism for others (Babin and Boles, 1998; Brown and Peterson, 1993; Mowday et al., 1979). However, strongly committed workers can serve as brand ambassadors to have a more significant brand advocacy impact and present an accurate image of

the company's culture and values to potential employees (Katoen and Macioschak 2007; Kimpakorn and Tocquer 2009).

According to the literature, organisational commitment contributes to employer brand advocacy, as firmly committed employees continue to become brand supporters of the company with the greater community both inside and outside the organisation (Babin and Boles, 1998; Brown and Peterson, 1993; Katoen and Macioschak, 2007; Mowday, Steers, and Porter, 1979; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016). Furthermore, employees who become brand advocates add to the stable acquisition of talent and the strength of workplace satisfaction and commitment (Schweitzer and Lyons, 2008). Hence, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H6: Organisation commitment has a significant positive effect on employer brand advocacy.

3.8 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANISATION COMMITMENT AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

Over the years, many scholars have paid considerable attention to the idea of organisational commitment. Porter et al. (1974) described organisation commitment as the degree of feeling and emotion people have for their organisation. At the same time, Reichers (1985) concluded that the company's dedication was related to employee interest. However, Kohli and Jaworski (1990) find that the workers dedicated are the employees who collaborate to accomplish shared objectives.

Moreover, Becker (1960) concluded from 1960 to 1982 that organisational commitment is referred to as the "side-bet," while Porter et al. (1982) found that organisational commitment is a reference to the "exchange" principle. Becker's (1960) theory proposes that workers remain committed to their organisations because they perceive the expense of leaving if they want to quit and establishes

a link between organisational commitment and costs and the decision to leave, ensuring that employees stay in the company for more extended periods.

Although Porter et al. (1982) concluded that employees stay longer in the organisation because they believe in its purpose, principles, expectations, and priorities, they have a deep motivation to do their best to accomplish its goals. Bansal, Mendelson, and Sharma (2001) retained the same opinion from Porter et al. (1982), measuring the organisation's commitment in line with their employees' expectations, suggesting that employees might seek to accomplish their organisational goals, tasks and priorities as they are committed to their company.

Though Darwish (2000) had a different view, he even said the degree to which employees focused on the changes happening in the organisation is measured. Herold et al. (2008) had the same view as Darwish (2000), also argued that the mindset of employees after changes in an organisation is organisational commitment, to be more precise, the degree to the acceptability of transition and the tolerance of employees to change in the organisations from time to time. In this respect, employee commitment is the most significant aspect that organisations need to make (Meyer, 2007).

The performance of employees is identified as the way employees accomplish the mission based on organisational values and are assessed by the degree of commitment to the company's progress. Yeh and Hong (2012) suggested that employee performance is compatible with the efficiency and the volume of the work, meaning that employee success is equivalent to its competitiveness. Carlson et al. (2006) identified pay, recruiting, training and development, and performance

evaluation as some of the most critical factors in increasing employee performance, arguing that one of the primary responsibilities of human resource management is to ensure that workers in the company have access to the elements mentioned above.

According to Liwei and Erdong (2011), the individual's performances may be split into two sections, the first being the individual's result and the second being the individual's attitude in executing their activities towards goal achievement. Individual performance includes any employee whose job aims to fulfill the company's objectives, and even those tasks, whether direct or indirect, because the individual's acts directly or indirectly influence accomplishing the organisation's goals (Campbell, 1990). According to Motowidlo (2003), the employee's performance is the conduct required of the employees during work. The performance of employees is how employees interpret the job, how they can do it, and how hard they try to complete it (Williams and Anderson, 1991).

Performance words originate from work performance or actual performance (work performance or actual performance of someone). Output awareness (work performance) is the product of an individual conducting their duties with responsibility for quality and quantity (Mangkunegara, 2011). Hasibuan (2013) says that employee performance is a function that everyone can accomplish in executing their duties based on expertise, knowledge, intensity, and time. The general term commitment element is an organisational commitment appropriate for research leading to increased employee performance. Referring to Aris and Ghozali (2006), the commitment of all employers and employees to the company was needed because it would establish a professional working environment.

Organisational commitment is a "behavioural viewpoint where commitment is characterized as a clear line of action, so the more significant commitment of workers to the company will increase the employee performance. Wright (1992) advocated that a higher degree of performance would be generated, contributing to a high level of judgment. Previous research showed a positive relationship between organisation commitment and employee performance (Clarke, 2006; Khan et al., 2010; Memari et al., 2013; Meyer et al., 2002), and Meyer et al. (2002) tested the relationship between organisation commitments and individual performance; they found that they had a positive relationship between organisational performance and commitment. Thus, it is argued that organisational commitment is an antecedent of employees' performance.

H7: Organisation commitment has a significant positive effect on employee performance.

3.9 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN JOB SATISFACTION AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

Many researchers have looked at the link between job satisfaction and employee performance, resulting in different definitions for both concepts. For example, Price (2001) defined an employee's performance as an influencing orientation toward his or her work. Furthermore, Sempane et al. (2002) defined employee performance as a person's total comprehension and appraisal of their work condition and a positive emotional status from their job evaluation and work style (Islam and Siengthai, 2009). Employee performance results from employee satisfaction, revealing how employees feel about their entire employment in an organisational environment.

Different researchers have highlighted personal and environmental characteristics as crucial variables affecting employee performance and satisfaction (Ganguly, 2010). Ganguly (2010), for

example, argued that the person-environmental model has the most acceptable explanatory meaning for interpreting employee performance through satisfaction. Furthermore, studies have shown that job satisfaction and employee performance are dependent on interactive relationships between a variety of factors, such as recognition, colleagues, workplace communications, the nature of the job, family benefits, the quality of technology used in the organisation, organisational strategies, structures, and processes, compensation, promotion, personal development, and security. In general, job satisfaction is considered a critical predictor of employee performance (Dawal et al., 2009).

Employee job satisfaction and performance have also been studied. According to most experts, satisfaction and comprehensive sensitivity to their socio-emotional and physiological requirements are essential for achieving employee productivity and efficiency (Judge et al., 2001; Schneider et al., 2003). According to Judge et al. (2001), employee job satisfaction has a significant positive relationship with critical elements such as employee morale, employee engagement, and job performance. Moreover, Harter et al. (2002) discovered a positive link between job satisfaction, staff performance, and customer satisfaction in organisations.

Examining the link between employee satisfaction and organisational performance in banks and other financial intermediaries, Zohair (2007) found that these two critical variables positively correlate. Chandrasekar (2011) further found that individual employee dissatisfaction resulting from a poor working environment can also significantly decrease individual employee performance. These results were also supported in different studies in Asian economies. We can conclude from these studies that organisations that aim to improve employee performance must

pay attention to employee satisfaction, which helps improve employee performance. Inverse impacts on mental health and job performance in disgruntled jobs are more likely to be detrimental (Judge et al., 2001; Siddique, 2012).

Keaveney and Nelson (1993) have discovered a causal relationship between job satisfaction and job performance. They further identified a positive relationship between these two constructs. Similarly, the impact of job satisfaction on job performance has been studied with a sample of 94 professionals, comprised of bank tellers and hospital professionals. According to the findings, job satisfaction on job performance is more significant than the impact of organisational commitment on job performance (Shore and Martin, 1989). Pugno and Depedri (2009) also suggested that employers improve job satisfaction to improve employees' performance.

H9: Job satisfaction has a significant positive effect on employee performance.

3.10 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMPLOYEE RETENTION AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

In many earlier studies, the association between employee retention and employee performance is established (Kar and Misra 2013; Markos and Sridevi 2010; Susilo, 2013). The higher retention of employees increases job performance. Mangkunegara (2017) believed that performance comes from skill and individual behaviour (Sumarni, 2011). The organisation will establish this specific scenario through an effective and sustainable strategic employee retention program. One key question that should be raised is how the retention of workers impacts employees and organisational performance. Aidamoe et al. (2012) examined the retention of employees influences the performance of employees across various industries, which is consistent with what other

scholars (e.g., Gberevbie, 2010; Kar and Misra 2013; Markos and Sridevi 2010; Paul and Anantharaman, 2003).

Employee retention is vital for reducing the cost of turnover or recruiting and training employees in a company. Many factors show the importance of the retention of employees. Here are the turnover costs, including hundreds of thousands of dollars to the expenses of the company. The cost of sales includes hiring, training, and loss of productivity. As a rough calculation, industry experts often quote 25 percent of the average salary for employees. Customer services are interrupted when new employees enter into business, and customer satisfaction is at stake with a company partly due to their links to their employees when an employee leaves the company. The relationships between employees and customers are developed so that business continuity and services are encouraged. When an employee suddenly leaves the organisation, the relationships built by the employee for the company can also lead to loss of business.

When an individual departs an organisation, one of the most significant losses is low productivity. According to Stovel and Bontis (2002), excessive turnover can be detrimental to a company's performance. According to Alexander et al. (1994), high voluntary turnover affects productivity by disturbing the organisation's input/performance output process, which leads to decreased efficiency. In addition to the literature, Brown and Medoff (1978) discovered a significant positive association between employee performance and employee. As a result, by maintaining a helpful staff, productivity may be boosted.

H9: Employee retention has a significant positive effect on employee performance.

3.11 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMPLOYER BRAND ADVOCACY AND EMPLOYER OF CHOICE

Keller (1993) described brand advocacy as a constructive brand contact to accelerate market adoption and approval of the brand. Persons with strong words or favourable views on a brand are brand ambassadors or brand promoters (Commander, 2007). Men (2014) described employee brand advocacy as "volunteer assistance to external employee partners for brand organisations" (Men, 2014, p. 23). Employees as brand ambassadors or informal corporate spokespersons are more prominent in public relations companies (Dozier et al., 1995). Comparing corporate public relations messages with brand messages provided by employees who serve as brand supporters or informal speakers is more effective, trustworthy, and impartial. Employees use their ties and networks to positively spread the brand's image through the public (Men and Stacks, 2013).

From the perspective of human resources management, employee brand advocacy also aims to recruit and retain talent. Various studies have been performed (Mosley, 2015; Schweitzer and Lyons, 2008; Shinnar et al., 2004; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016). The workers working as brand supporters also add to the attraction of talent and also positively affect recruiting cost-effectiveness and favourable operational results (Morehart, 2001), increase employee morale (Kirnan et al., 1989) and pre-employment awareness and therefore have positive consequences for organisational socialization (Williams et al., 1993).

Furthermore, the internet era offers an increasing number of contact platforms for workers to talk with external viewers about their brand or employer (Men, 2014; Kim and Rhee, 2011). The extraordinary progress on the engagement ability of workers posed the question of companies how

effective control of the advantages and risks involved with employees thinking about their company on social media platforms has made employee brand advocacy a mantra for internal marketing literature (Dreher, 2014; Men, 2014).

Walz and Celuch (2010) claim that brand advocacy involves spreading good words about the brand rather than positive word of mouth, which gives rise to solid relationships with the brand or business with stakeholders. The definition first discussed by Kennedy (1977) describes the vital influence of the employee's positive expression and use favourable words to external stakeholders. When employees start sharing their positive experiences with employers to the outside world, potential employees take it seriously. They are attracted towards the organisation while looking at the way existing employees are happy with the employer and praising their employer.

Similarly, in internal marketing, the brand support principle can be extended to HRM. Workers should be brand ambassadors for their company (Tanwar and Prasad, 2016). Moreover, workers for their brand or organisation are important brand ambassadors (Commander, 2007). Brand advocacy literature has been widely debated to brand advocacy for generating a positive image of the organisation as a first-choice employer for potential employees (Howard and Kerin, 2013; Kemp, Childer, and Williams, 2012; Multicultural, 2005; Parrott et al., 2015; Russel and Morgan, 2009; Vishag and Laverie, 2013; Walz and Celuch, 2010).

H10: Employer brand advocacy has a significant positive effect on the employer of choice.

3.12 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AND ORGANISATION PERFORMANCE

Each employee has their own identity as a personality, and some research demonstrates that uniqueness has a relationship and influence on individual performance and the organisation where the employee works. Mullen et al. (2017) discovered that a person's age impacted how safe they were at work and how well they performed (Groen et al., 2016). When older workers have more experience working with their coworkers, they will do well (Gellert and Schalk, 2012). Workplace motivation may impact a person's performance and work discipline (Nabi et al., 2017; Nadeem et al., 2014; Pawirosumarto et al., 2017; Prophet et al., 2017), as well as organisational performance (Dobre, 2013; Pawirosumarto et al., 2017). According to the theory of motivation and expansion, when an individual has a specific goal in mind, he may perform effectively and achieve his objectives.

According to previous studies, employee's performance has a significant positive impact on organisation performance (Al-Mzary, 2015; Aragon et al., 2014; Atambo et al., 2013; Ayango and Muathe, 2017; Bhat, 2013; Eko, 2015; Falola et al., 2014; Groen et al., 2016; Hameed et al., 2014; Hamed et al., 2012; Kumara and Utama, 2016; Salem and Abdien, 2017; Sharma, 2016; Triasmoko et al., 2014; Panjaitan, 2015). Employee performance is impacted by disparities in the essence of the internal factor of workers, and because employees are part of the firm, the influence on the firm's performance is also impacted (Hatane, 2015; Vosloban, 2012).

H11: Employee performance has a significant positive effect on organisation performance.

3.13 CONCEPTUAL MODEL

The hypothesized associations are shown in Figure 3.1. The model shows that employer branding (culture, development opportunities, work-life balance, and incentives) leads to positive employee and organisational level outcomes. The employer brand generates committed employees who advocate for the employer and make it an ideal employer. Moreover, employer branding makes employees satisfied, who, in turn, are retained and become good performers. All these yield positive organisational performance.

Figure 3.1: Theoretical Model

Source: Current Study.

Table 3.1: List of Hypotheses

Hypotheses	
H1	Employer branding has a positive influence on person organisation fit.
H2	Employer branding has a positive influence on organisation commitment.
H3	Employer branding has a positive influence on employee retention.
H4	Employer branding has a positive influence on job satisfaction.
H5	Person organisation fit has a positive influence on the employer of choice.
H6	Organisation commitment has a positive influence on Employer brand advocacy.
H7	Organisation commitment has a positive influence on employee performance.
H8	Job satisfaction has a positive influence on employee performance.
H9	Employee retention has a positive influence on employee performance.
H10	Employer brand advocacy has a positive influence on the employer of choice.
H11	Employee performance has a positive influence on organisation performance.

Source: Researcher

3.14 SUMMARY

In order to create the conceptual framework described in section 3.14, this chapter studied the literature on employer branding and combined ideas from various domains. The relationship between employer branding and consequences is examined based on the literature. The researcher identified many links between important contrast of this study. Based on the literature, thirteen hypotheses were developed. At the end of the chapter, a research framework is presented, which shows constructs and their connections. The study design used to expand the scales and test the suggested model is designated in the subsequent chapter.

CHAPTER IV

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The selection of suitable methods for research plays a significant character in accomplishing a business research study in a good way. It leads the research study in the right direction; identifies and implements suitable research theories; collects all the necessary data effectively, and ensures adequate data analysis. Furthermore, this chapter is critical in ensuring that the research objectives defined in the first chapter are met. This chapter discusses the justification of appropriate research aspects such as philosophy, approaches, strategy, design, methods of data collection, and data analysis techniques. Furthermore, the researcher also discusses the reason behind the choice of a method over others.

This chapter discusses the techniques for putting the mixed methods design into effect, emphasizing research methodologies and philosophy, the settings and access to the study locations, and judgments on the study population and sampling tactics. In both phases of the investigation, data gathering methods, pilot study, and the data analysis procedure follow. Finally, questions of rigor and reliability about the current study and ethical implications were addressed.

Section 4.2 consists of the Research philosophy, and the Research approach is in section 4.3. moreover, section 4.4 is related to research design with the first phase of qualitative data is in section 4.5. in addition, Details about interviews are in section 4.6 and focus group in section 4.7. Section 4.8 entails the second phase (Research instrument and scale development). Section 4.9

consisted of a pilot study however main survey is in section 4.10. finally, data analysis techniques are presented in section 4.11.

4.2 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

The meaning of research philosophy in a study presents the researcher's beliefs regarding collecting, analyzing, and presenting data in a specific way. Saunders et al. (2009) defined that research philosophies can be interpretivism, positivism, and realism (Collins, 2010, Weaver and Olson, 2006). The selection of a research philosophy for the research suggests that the researcher accepted some assumptions to consider the world. The consideration of these assumptions is also required for the researcher in selecting an appropriate research strategy.

4.2.1 Interpretive Research Philosophy

Tenets of the interpretive research philosophy are based upon understanding the phenomenon from a subjective perspective. It also involves observations that are subjective and qualitative (Carson, 2001). From the perspective of this theory, the researcher needs to understand the social world of the research participants. It is why interpretivism researchers are generally interdependent with their research that is subjective in an authentic way (Wilson, 2014).

According to O'Mahoney and Vincent (2014), interpretivism asserts that it is very difficult to have “true” knowledge of an external “reality” (p.5) because humans decide “reality” through the creation of subjective meaning. As a result, the primary goal of this research philosophy is to comprehend the various interpretations people assign to their experiences and explain why they differ by concentrating on the identification of discourses and narratives.

Moreover, in some situations, researchers may also observe the participants while working with them. It shows that the researcher of this philosophy can have both a collaborative and participatory view. Furthermore, this research philosophy is based on an inductive approach, going from observation to theory (Allison, 2002). The researchers following this theory also consider the world as complex and open to interpretation. Moreover, the reading of determinations can result in the issues associated with dependability.

4.2.2 Positivist Research Philosophy

In contrast to the interpretive research philosophy, tenets of positivist philosophy lie in viewing the research from a truly objective perspective. Thus, it is carried out by maintaining specific and targeted interaction with the research participants. The author of this philosophy also believes that the research must be carried out scientifically while following a strict set of pre-defined guidelines (Wilson, 2014).

According to Easterby-Smith et al. (2002), positivism means that “the social world exists outside, and that its qualities should be assessed objectively rather than assumed subjectively” (p.28). Positivism is thus founded on the ontological notion that reality is external, exists independently of researchers, and is objective. As a result, the emphasis is on observable, factual, and measurable facts in order to create universal conclusions (O'Mahoney and Vincent, 2014). Before data collection, variables in quantitative research are generally isolated and explicitly defined, and then linked together to offer a set of hypotheses. Quantitative research, according to Brannen (1992), is concerned with enumerative induction. As a result, it ‘abstracts by generalising’ (p.7).

As a consequence, quantitative research examines a large number of examples for comparable qualities before abstracting them (conceptually) owing to their generality. According to the quantitative method, numerical data is used to evaluate specific connections between variables and hypotheses about reality. Its emphasis is on cause and effect, as well as determining the size and frequency of connections (Migiros and Magangi, 2011). Experimental, quasi-experimental, correlational, and survey research designs are the most common quantitative research designs (Migiros and Magangi, 2011).

This philosophy is based on a deductive approach going from theory to observation. Additionally, proponents of positivist philosophy strive for the generalizability of their findings to the entire population. This tendency towards generalizing the findings is derived from a quantifiable analysis instead of qualitative (Allison, 2002). Moreover, due to its highly structured approach, positivist research is likely to produce a high reliability level.

4.2.3 Realism Research Philosophy

Another form of research philosophy is realism, which focuses on scientifically and practically investigating social factors (Saunders et al., 2007), which supports philosophers' claims that things are inherently independent of people and are not governed. The most fundamental characteristic of realism is that it is entirely dependent on the senses, implying that what we perceive in actual life is the truth. Realism is a subset of epistemology comparable to each other in terms of the idea that scientific methods are linked to the advancement of knowledge (Bryman, 2006). The researcher did not adopt this philosophy because it has no link with the study aims.

4.2.4 Justification of Research Philosophy

This research is based on both interpretivism and positivism philosophies. The justification for the choice of philosophical approach is based on the “what and how” aspect. Because the researcher focuses on what employer branding is and what are elements of employer brandings. In addition, the researcher examining how employer branding influences employer of choice and organisation performance. Moreover, the researcher in creating a suitable research framework (Ahmed et al., 2016) by applying both interpretive and positivist research philosophies for this study.

In Addition, this philosophy also enables the researcher to interpret different views and opinions about the concept and understanding of EB in perceptions of current employees working in service firms (Collins, 2010; Foroudi et al., 2021; Hauken et al., 2019). This research philosophy helped the researcher to answer the first research question (what are the key elements of robust employer branding in service firms according to the perception of current employees?). The interpretive paradigm was deemed the most suitable for the research due to its potential to generate new understandings of an emerging concept in the marketing and branding arenas (Poth & Munce, 2020; Timans et al., 2019; Wilkinson & Staley, 2019), such as the concept to be investigated in this research (i.e., elements of employer branding). Because the practical knowledge that is embedded in the world of human interaction and meanings was sought.

However, a primary goal of positivist inquiry is to generate explanatory associations or causal relationships (Balakrishnan and Foroudi, 2019; Foroudi et al., 2019b). The positivist paradigm is based on the assumption that a single tangible reality exists, one that can be understood, identified, and measured. This allows explanation and prediction in a causal framework to operate naturally

(Foroudi et al., 2019a; Foroudi et al., 2021; Ageeva et al., 2019). At the same time, as a part of positivist philosophy, the researcher collects a wide range of quantitative data so that reliability towards the qualitative data can be enhanced. In addition, the causal relationship between employer branding and employer of choice and organisation performance can be examined. The positivism philosophy guided the researcher to organize this study in the right direction so that the second research question (how employer branding influences the employer of choice and organisation performance?) can be answered effectively.

At the same time, as a part of positivist philosophy, the researcher collects a wide range of quantitative data so that reliability towards the qualitative data can be enhanced. In addition, the causal relationship between employer branding and employer of choice and organisation performance can be examined. The positivism philosophy guided the researcher to organize this study in the right direction so that the second research question (How employer branding influences the employer of choice and organisation performance?) can be answered effectively.

4.3 RESEARCH APPROACH

To complete research, the researchers must have an awareness of the research approaches. There are two main types of research approaches, including inductive and deductive, that could be utilized to select and justify suitable research techniques and data collection methods for research. A researcher must consider various factors before selecting a suitable research approach. For example, the deductive approach may be helpful in the case where the researcher has the interest to evaluate current theory' (Gratton and Jones, 2010). On the other hand, when the area is relatively new or under-researched, and the researcher wants to explain a phenomenon, an inductive approach is appropriate. In

addition, time and resources are also other essential factors because inductive research requires more resources and more time than the deductive approach (Anderson, 2004). Moreover, the deductive approach is less risky than the inductive approach due to its focus on existing theories. The below section discusses the different relationships with the theories of the two approaches:

4.3.1 Inductive Research Approach

The inductive approach is related to theory-building processes, and thus, it involves search and observation into the relationship between the actions and meanings of participants. Additionally, data is gathered without a prior assumption about measurement and categorisation (Anderson, 2004). Moreover, as the researcher emphasizes understanding the internal logic and human actions' purposive nature, the situation context is incorporating into the analysis process. Lastly, the research outcomes are based on suggesting a credible explanation of behaviours that have been observed (Engel and Schutt, 2009).

4.3.2 Deductive Research Approach

In contrast to the inductive approach, deductive research is associated with theory testing and involves hypothesis formulation. In this, hypotheses are operationalised so that the involved variables can be recognized and measured objectively (Anderson, 2004). After this, data is gathered, and the collected data is used to test the hypothesis to define their reality (Engel and Schutt, 2009). Lastly, the research outcomes emphasize modifying or confirming the theory from which the hypotheses were derived.

4.3.3 Justification of Research Approach

The best fit to understand the research problem researcher combined both inductive and deductive approaches. Mingers (2001) states, “the different research methods (especially from different paradigms) focus on different aspects of reality and therefore a richer understanding of research together in a single research project can be generated” (p. 241). The aim of the study was two-pronged, to explore key employment benefits to develop a strong employer brand and test the influence of EB on the employer of choice and organization performance. Hence, a combination of both inductive and deductive approaches is utilised by the researcher.

The fundamental justification for utilising both approaches is that the researcher is concerned with the views and explanations of the individuals about the phenomenon. Moreover, the researcher wants to measure the phenomenon or research problem numerically (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018; Eger et al., 2019; Gratton and Jones, 2010). In addition, inductive research is also suitable for this study as the researcher thinks that the truth is different for everyone. Thus, the inductive approach guided the researcher in investigating the meanings and perceptions of current employees working in service firms about employer branding.

A deductive approach is concerned with developing a hypothesis (or hypotheses) based on existing theory, and then designing a research strategy to test the hypothesis (David et al., 2018; Foroudi et al., 2021). A deductive design might test to see if this relationship or link did obtain in more general circumstances (Timans et al., 2019). The deductive approach follows the path of logic most closely. The reasoning starts with a theory and leads to a new hypothesis. This hypothesis is put to the test by confronting it with observations that either lead to a confirmation or a rejection

of the hypothesis (Foroudi et al.,2020b; Linnander et al., 2019; Wilkinson & Staley, 2019). The deductive approach helped to answer the second research question of the study which was concern with the examination of a causal relationship between employer branding and employer of choice and organization performance.

At the same time, to confirm the employment of both qualitative and quantitative research methods, both approaches are also beneficial for this study. In this, the utilization of the inductive approach supported the author in collecting qualitative data, while the deductive approach assisted in gathering numerical data (Mingers, 2001; Saunders et al., 2019; Steen, 2007). For the inductive approach, the researcher conducted in-depth interviews to learn about the concepts of employer branding and its dimensions and its influences on job-related outcomes like job satisfaction, organisation commitment, which lead to the employer of choice and organisation performance. At the same time, a close-ended questionnaire was developed and sent to the selected participants to define the relationships identified through the inductive research process (Engel and Schutt, 2009; Priya and Raman, 2021). Overall, the above-discussed factors justify using both approaches for the researcher to complete this research fruitfully.

4.4 RESEARCH DESIGN

4.4.1 Qualitative Research Design

The use of qualitative research design is related to an in-depth understanding of the subjective phenomenon. The main emphasis of the qualitative design is to recognize the deeper meanings of specific human experiences to provide more robust theoretical observations that cannot be counted

and measured in numbers with ease (Dawadi, 2019; Rubin and Babbie, 2007). A qualitative approach is helpful to understand and define the reasons behind the research issue.

Qualitative research designs go from general to specific as, at first, it includes collecting data, interpretation of experiences, data analysis, and presenting conclusions so that the primary research aim and objectives can be attained. For this purpose, data collection techniques include observations, in-depth interviews, content analysis, focus groups (Blery, 2014; Dawadi, 2019). In addition, this design also considers a small sample size so that a wide range of information can be collected from the participants. Additionally, the main terminologies used under a qualitative study are meaningfulness, inductive approach, and informants (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018; Monsen and Horn, 2007).

4.4.2 Quantitative Research Design

Contrary to qualitative research design, quantitative design concentrates on gathering data collected and analysed in numbers. It also emphasizes providing more exact and generalizable findings through statistical techniques (Al-Busaidi, 2008; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018; Riasi, 2015). Additionally, when researchers want to support that a cause creates an effect, quantitative design is beneficial. In contrast with qualitative research design, quantitative research design goes from specific to general. Under quantitative research design, theories could be tested, previous research studies are critiqued, and hypotheses are developed based on the results and theoretical framework (David et al., 2018; Hauken et al., 2019; Linnander et al., 2019). In addition, the developed hypothesis guides the data collection process and analysis technique. Lastly, data is analysed based on the hypothesis, and theories are confirmed or rejected to draw relevant conclusions.

The primary data collection techniques under quantitative research include experiments and surveys. Furthermore, sample size also a significant role in determining the statistical significance of the study. Researchers predetermine the sample size and generally select large enough sample sizes to establish statistical significance and generalizability of the study. Moreover, the Quantitative approach is related to the theory-testing process, and it also starts with a theory. Additionally, it is also found that a quantitative study is based on a deductive approach while a qualitative study is based on an inductive approach. On the other hand, the qualitative approach is related to the exploitation of theories, ending with theory. The mixed approach is holistic and completes the cycle, and helps in closing the existing gap.

4.4.3 Mixed Research Design

It includes the employment of both qualitative and quantitative designs. In the views of Polit and Beck (2004), the implementation of both quantitative and qualitative aspects is beneficial in research that is based on multi-method component designs. The researcher can implement both aspects as different components of the overall research, which remain different during the collection of data and analysis processes. Component designs can be classified into triangulated, complementary, and expansion designs (Polit and Beck, 2010).

Both qualitative and quantitative methods are applied in a triangulated design to enhance the validity by capturing the same phenomenon. In addition to this, in complementary designs, to clarify and enhance the results from one method type, one method type is used. For example, through quantitative results, qualitative results are clarified, discussed, and enhanced. Lastly, different methods are applied for researching different components in the expansion design to

enhance the reliability and validity of results (Shorten & Smith, 2017; Timans et al., 2019; Wilkinson & Staley, 2019).

4.4.4 Justification for Mixed Research Design

In marketing and management research, both quantitative and qualitative techniques are often used to explain different data collection, processing, and analysis mechanism (Saunders and Lewis, 2009; Shorten & Smith, 2017; Poth & Munce, 2020). The current research used a “mixed-method approach” for data collection. Hybrid approaches have shown effectiveness in social and behavioural sciences (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018; Linnander et al., 2019). Moreover, mixed-method research blends qualitative data collection and analysis with the quantitative data collection and analysis within a single study (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). More than one analysis approach (interview, focus group, questionnaire) increases understanding and reveals new perspectives of the study phenomenon (Gupta et al., 2011; Palmer and Gallagher, 2007). Based on research methodology and the credibility and significance of quantitative and qualitative research, social and human science literature is gradually adopting a mixed-methods approach (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

Researcher in the area of marketing and branding (Akbari et al. 2021; Balakrishnan and Foroudi, 2020; Foroudi et al., 2014; Foroudi et al., 2018; Foroudi et al., 2019i; Foroudi et al., 2020i; Foroudi, 2020ii; Gupta et al., 2020; Hwang et al., 2021) believe that employing qualitative research is the more productive way to study social order and that it is achieved through the subjective interpretation of participants involved, such as by interviewing different participants and reconciling differences among their responses using their subjective perspectives. With this type

of research, findings emerge due to the interactions between the researcher and the participants (i.e., employees in service firm); the research also progresses because subjectivity is valued (Krishna and Kim, 2021; Melewar et al., 2017; Nguyen et al., 2020; Zha et al., 2020). To answer the first research question (what are the key elements of robust employer branding in service firms according to the perception of current employees?) researcher collected qualitative data through interviews and focus groups. Therefore, the values held by the researcher, the questions asked of the participants, and the generated and interpreted findings all allow the research to be unique inquiry (Poth & Munce, 2020; Shorten & Smith, 2017; Wilkinson & Staley, 2019).

The second phase of the research applied the positivist paradigm to investigate the causal associations and proposed hypotheses. At the same time, as a part of positivist philosophy, the researcher collects a wide range of quantitative data so that reliability towards the qualitative data can be enhanced (Foroudi et al., 2020a; Shorten & Smith, 2017; Timans et al., 2019; Wilkinson & Staley, 2019). In addition, the causal relationship between employer branding and employer of choice and organisation performance was tested. The content validity of scales was satisfied through the panel of experts. Academics suggested to remove irrelevant items (De-Vellis, 2003; Foroudi et al., 2019a; Fàbregues et al., 2020; Poth & Munce, 2020) to get accurate items to measure employer branding. To answer the second research question (does employer branding influence the employer of choice and organisation performance?) researcher collected quantitative data through a self-administered questionnaire. A qualitative data collection design was deemed appropriate to test the influence of EB on EOC and organisational performance.

The research questions decide the methods to perform the research. Therefore, a quantitative approach for testing hypotheses and collecting data from the questionnaire is used in this analysis . The quantitative approach to integrating deductive logic, based on experimental observations of behaviour patterns of individuals, is suggested by Van Teijlingen and Hundley (2016) to find and check several causative variables that could predict a large variety of human interaction patterns.

The qualitative approach includes interviews or data analytics techniques such as the non-statistical classification of information gathered through interviews of respondents, which have been chosen objectively from the target population. At the same time, Hair et al. (2016) indicated that quantitative analysis helps scholars define the relationship between internal and external constructs systematically. This study measures the constructs in the research framework that is an integral part of quantitative research (Fauser, 2018; Hauken et al., 2019; Westphal and Fredrickson, 2001). Hair et al. (2016) further noted that a high level of reliability hypothesis might be tested, and this approach was also used in similar strategic marketing and management studies with a high level of effectiveness. Based on empirical proof, this study investigates the causal relationships in the underlying constructs and finds the quantitative approach the most effective approach (Sharma, 1996).

Concepts are defined more widely in qualitative research and are subject to alteration over the course of the investigation and data gathering. Rather than verifying or disproving hypotheses and examining a pre-specified collection of variables, qualitative research takes a broader approach and aims to discover “patterns of inter-relationships between a previously defined set of concepts” (Brannen, 1992, p.4). As a result, qualitative research is connected with analytic induction, in

which the primary goal is to test theory rather than infer and generalise findings. Analytic induction 'generalises by abstracting,' which implies that qualitative research abstracts from a single, concrete example and generalises its characteristics. Qualitative research is connected with a variety of research methodologies, such as phenomenology, ethnography, grounded theory, discourse analysis, narrative analysis, case studies, and various data-gathering techniques such as interviews, observation, focus groups, and fieldwork, among others.

Researcher in the area of marketing and branding (Akbari et al. 2021; Balakrishnan and Foroudi, 2020; Foroudi et al., 2014; Foroudi et al., 2018; Foroudi et al., 2019i; Foroudi et al., 2020i; Foroudi, 2020ii; Gupta et al., 2020; Hwang et al., 2021; Krishna and Kim, 2021; Melewar et al., 2017; Nguyen et al., 2020; Zha et al., 2020) believe that employing qualitative research is the more productive way to study social order and that it is achieved through the subjective interpretation of participants involved, such as by interviewing different participants and reconciling differences among their responses using their subjective perspectives. With this type of research, findings emerge due to the interactions between the researcher and the participants (i.e., employees in service firms); the research also progresses because subjectivity is valued. This acknowledges that the research participants are human and incapable of total objectivity because their reality is constructed by subjective experiences within certain situations.

It is necessary to analyse the measurement part of employer branding, that is, the many characteristics of the employer brand, in order to determine whether it is genuinely assisting organisations in achieving their targeted objectives. Various research (Alnaçk and Alnaçk, 2012; Berthon et al., 2005; Hillebrandt and Ivens, 2013; Roy, 2013; Tuzuner and Yuksel, 2009; Zhu et

al., 2014) have found elements of the employer brand. All of them, however, have flaws that demand more research in order to build a trustworthy and accurate employer brand scale. In terms of the limitations of earlier scales, the Berthon et al. (2005) scale is the most often used in the context of employer branding.

From a conceptual and methodological standpoint, Berthon et al. (2005)'s "EmpAt" scale is remarkably strong. To offer a robust theoretical foundation for the scale, the authors employed Ambler and Barrow's (1996) theoretical framework. However, this scale has a limitation in that it was designed using a sample of potential employees (students) and can only be applied to final-year college students with limited work experience (Berthon et al., 2005).

Employee experience in the organisation, according to Moroko and Uncles (2008), reveals if the organisation is adhering to its principles and standards. Kimpakorn and Tocquer (2010) emphasised the value of existing employees, claiming that if employees are convinced that the company is a good place to work, they will become brand champions who will suggest the company to others through positive word-of-mouth. This, in turn, aids the organisation in attracting new talent. This has also been proposed by Bergstrom and Anderson (2001), who believe that current employees might be a beneficial source of new hires. Hence, Current employee may be the target audience to collect data while developing a robust scale for employer branding.

This study designed a questionnaire for the present survey based on Churchill's (1979) advice. This study focuses on previous literature that defines and specifies the field of research and metrics for employer branding and the aspects and impacts of employer branding. In order to establish a set

of trustworthy, valid scales, this study follows the methods of Churchill (1979) in constructing measurements of numerous things for the marketing construct, as well as Gerbing and Anderson (1988) and DeVellis (2003). Churchill's (1979) theory argues that it primarily incorporates a qualitative and quantitative paradigm. The proposed processes in the establishment of marketing constructs with measurement scales are shown in Figure 4.1. The initial phase of study design, according to Churchill (1979), is exploratory fieldwork. This initial phase will be described in the following sections.

Figure 4.1: Steps in measurement scale development

Source: Churchill (1979, p. 66).

4.5 THE FIRST PHASE (QUALITATIVE DATA COLLECTION)

An initial exploratory study was done to undertake research questions. Regarding the researcher's best knowledge, very few studies have provided a valid and reliable measure of employer branding to date. This research is intended to fill the gap in this field and adopt Churchill (1979) procedures to create a suitable scale. For the following purposes, an initial exploratory analysis was undertaken in this area: 1) to gain an in-depth knowledge of the area of interest (Dacin and Brown,

2002). 2) Understand the current practice on the ground to determine the relevance of the proposed research. 3) Develop hypotheses and purify a questionnaire to get informative knowledge and insight and understand the suggested research questions (Churchill, 1979).

The exploratory research, known as the experience survey, is based on the concept that a group of individuals that can give insight into the phenomena. Exploratory studies appear to start with a broad sample and evolve narrowly (Saunders et al., 2007). Churchill (1979) suggests that such techniques produce ample items and represent constructs (exploration, literature search, interviews, and focus group). This research follows the approaches mentioned above (focus group and interview) for assessing the employer branding construct.

In-depth interviews and group discussions are of considerable importance in integrating significant resources and information that gives a new insight into current data (Palmer, 2011; Palmer and Gallagher, 2007). The evidence obtained from focus groups and in-depth interviews offered knowledge and perspectives for this study and led to further information, which was not recognized in the existing literature review. However, large samples are rarely involved in exploratory research (Malhotra and Birks, 2000). Qualitative data were used, primarily in the form of a questionnaire, to establish a quantitative study (Churchill 1979). The Arrangement, administration, and data interpretation of the qualitative stage are explained in the following section.

4.5.1. Planning, management, and interpretation of the qualitative data

As literature explored, several approaches are available to analyse qualitative data (Bryman and Burgess, 1994; Guba, 1990; Silverman, 1993). The researchers started with a grounded theory

approach to test the qualitative data to pursue quality research. A coding method was used to interpret the qualitative data and was driven by the conceptual framework built based on the literature. In order to establish a collective understanding of employer branding, its dimensions, and consequences, the researchers created the codes—the sets the coding and processing framework for the results. In addition, the researcher found that the original codes discussed research problems, theories, and primary variables that the researcher had carried (Miles and Huberman, 1994; Palmer and Gallagher, 2007). The research questions and hypotheses have been empirically evaluated (Bazeley, 2007; Sheth and Parvatiyar, 2002).

Initially, the narrative coding was focused on open codes and the constructs found during the literature review. “The initial list of codes should be based on a conceptual framework, list of research questions, hypotheses, problem areas, and key variables that the researcher brings to the study”(Miles and Huberman, 1994, p. 59). Before coding the transcript, the memo was written by the researcher for each transcript. The data coding enables the search, comparison, and detection of any patterns needing further investigation. The interview transcript coding procedure situates the process in approaches to qualitative analysis (Malhotra and Birks, 2000). The collected data was extracted under descriptive codes and thematic ideas from data collected and connected with the same content (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Weston et al., 2001).

According to Lincoln and Guba (1985), it is essential to "devise rules that describe category properties, and that can, ultimately, be used to justify the inclusion of each data bit that remains assigned to the category as well as to provide a basis for later tests of replicability" (p.348). This method guarantees the systematic introduction of the theoretical ideas from the first coding round

(Esterberg, 2002). There are three stages of evaluation of coding: 1) open coding, 2). axial coding, and 3). selective coding (Esterberg, 2002; Huberman and Miles, 1994). The three coding stages enhance the trust in developing data (Esterberg, 2002; Huberman and Miles, 1994).

The first step of the qualitative data analysis was open code generation. The open codes were interpreted and categorised into higher concepts before the key categories appeared. The open code started with a line-by-line analysis of the text (interview transcripts). It highlighted passages that addressed and coded the employer branding, person-organisation fit, employee satisfaction, commitment, retention, employer brand advocacy, employee performance, employer of choice, organisational performance, and the relationship between these constructs in either the starting list or new open codes.

The transcripts have been read very closely twice to identify the appropriate patterns in the texts highlighted in past literature. Each sentence has been compared to the previous sentences and open codes for variations, differences, and similarities. If the codes were identical or somewhat similar, they were identically coded. If the codes were different, the new sentence was coded with a different name. The main goal of open coding is to identify themes in the text which are either close or different from the related literature. After finishing open coding with each interview transcript, the researcher wrote further remarks and notes to examine them further rigorously. It contributed to the creation of the axial code.

The second phase of data analysis was AXIAL CODING, which attempts to define the connection and contrast between core categories and subcategories to recognise patterns within text.

According to Balmer (1996), after open coding, systemic axial coding has begun. The axial coding technique is a method of continuous contrast. Axial code focused on variations and parallels in open codes identified earlier. The open codes were compared with each other, and the produced axial codes. This method allows the researcher to construct a new axial code, alter or combine existing axial codes.

The final coding process is selective coding, which aims at incorporating the emerging theory. Selective coding is the most complex stage in the grounded theory analysis. In order to generate a hypothesis that can ultimately match with the evidence, it is essential to explain the phenomenon in a parsimonious manner (Strauss and Corbin, 1998). According to Spiggle (1994), selective coding involves moving to a higher level of abstraction with the developed paradigmatic constructs, specifying relationships, and delineating a core category or construct around which the other categories and constructs revolve, and that relates them to one another "(p. 494). Strauss and Corbin (1998) reported that selective coding started in the entire axial coding process by writing the relationship between these axial codes. Thus, this stage is considered the most challenging and frustrating stage in grounded theories since it is crucial to clarify and be parsimonious about the phenomenon.

The researchers employed three additional methods and the traditional analytical coding: 1) a general guideline reviewing the research questions; 2) re-examining the open and raw codes when evaluating axial codes, and 3) code compatibility and relationship discussion with experts and supervisor. By interpreting the data analysis, the researcher has been able to figure out the dimensions and key influences of employer branding. In order to check the reliability of coding by

reviewing text, the researcher developed the code more than once (Weber, 1985) to obtain consensus on the recognition of themes. In order to analyse each word and sentence, the researchers used the coding scheme to consider the possible meanings believed or expected by the speaker (Weston et al., 2001).

Due to various philosophical and methodological approaches to studying human behaviour, the data quality of social sciences is essential (Ritchie et al., 2003). Validity and reliability are the considerations leading to the design, interpretation of outcomes, and quality assessment of the research. However, in qualitative analysis, there is no standard concept of reliability and validity. An indication of 'trustworthiness' is decisive to certify the reliability of the study. The notion of truth determination by reliability and validity assessments is endorsed by the perception of credibility (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). "trustworthiness of a research report lies at the heart of issues conventionally discussed as validity and reliability" (Seale, 1999, p. 266).

Lincoln and Guba (1985) have noted, "there is no validity without reliability. An expression of the former validity is sufficient to establish the latter reliability" (p. 315). Reliability means persistence, and validity means that the strength of the evidence is well established. Reliability deals with how accurately data were generated by research methods and techniques (Patton, 2001). The triangulating approach is used to investigate how the reliability and validity of data are impacted by researchers' expectations. Moreover, reliability and validity mean the elimination of biases and improve the truthfulness of the study.

Creswell and Miller (2000) defined triangulation as "a validity procedure where researchers search for convergence among multiple and different sources of information to form themes or categories in a study" (p. 126). Triangulation increases the validity and reliability of research and the estimation of its results. Therefore, reliability, validity, and triangulation are pertinent study principles, mostly from a qualitative perspective, to reflect the different forms that reality is formed. To check the reliability of the coding researcher used the content analysis, the researcher determined stability when the content was coded more than once (Weber, 1985). Moreover, one autonomous coder with substantial qualitative data analysis expertise and unfamiliar with the analysis was hired to test the reliability of the emerging employer branding dimensions.

4.6 INTERVIEW

This study begins with interviews to define and operationalise the key elements required to quantify the concept of the employer branding construct. This study led to in-depth interviews and with managers who are currently working in service industries, allowing the researcher to deepen the knowledge of the subject and to gather attitude and behaviours data related to area of interest (Ritchie et al., 2003; Shiu et al., 2009; Yin, 1984). In this research, the interview guide was created, which described the employer branding as the subject of concern, balanced the interview with the main issues, and allowed the conversation to continue.

The researcher contacted the fifteen well-known Pakistani service firms to find the research subject's best contact person(s). Their consent was obtained to become part of the study. Of the fifteen firms approached, they all responded via mail or e-mail, but five did not participate in the study because of their tight schedules. Therefore, ten in-depth personal interviews were conducted with the managers of different service firms in Pakistan.

Almost all (9 out of 10) interviews were held face to face with actual respondents from the firms. Face-to-face interviews help obtain a clear overview of employer branding and better understand the research objectives (Churchill, 1999). The interviews were conducted at the participant's choice site (Andriopoulos and Lewis, 2009) except for one manager who preferred a telephonic interview. The interviewees determined the locations and the time of the interviews. The average interview time was 90 minutes, and all the interviews were recorded and transcribed in writing so that reliability may be ensured (Ritchie et al., 2003). The in-depth interview technique was an undisguised direct, semi-structured, and personal interview to discover fundamental beliefs, attitudes, and feelings about the topic. An interview protocol containing a question sheet was structured to check that all areas of concern were discussed during the interviews. The details of the participants in the interviews are seen in table 4.1.

Table 4.1: The details of in-depth interviews with managers

Interview Date	Organisation	Interview position	Interview approx. duration
Managers in service sector firms			
10.02.2020	State life insurance Ltd	Marketing Manager	90 min.
12.02. 2020	Lahore Garrison University	Dean, Social Sciences	90 min.
13.02.2020	TCS Pakistan	Regional Manager	60 min.
14.02.2020	Sargodha Medical College	Senior Registrar	60 min.
17.02.2020	Pearl Continental Hotel	Human Resource Manager	60 min.
18.02.2020	Muslim Commercial Bank Ltd	Assistant Vice President	60 min.
19.02.2020	U-fone	Regional Manager	90 min.
19.02.2020	University of Sargodha	Additional Registrar	90 min.
20.02.2020	University of Sargodha	Director Noon Business School	90 min.

21.02.2020	Habib Bank Ltd	Manager Agri-Finance	60 min.
Topics discussed			
The understanding of employer branding. The key dimensions of employer branding. The general perception about employer branding and its outcomes. Discussion of organisation culture, CSR, WLB, and salary and incentives used in employer branding The main perceived impacts of employer branding on the employer of choice. The main perceived impacts of employer branding on person-organisation fit, job satisfaction, commitment, and employee retention. The main perceived impacts of employer branding on organisation performance.			

Source: The researcher

4.7 FOCUS GROUP

According to authors (Byers and Wilcox, 1991; Fern, 1982; Zeller, 1986), researchers in marketing use the focus group technique as a great source of obtaining qualitative data. Focus group technique was used in the current study for the following reasons: 1) “people can report on and about themselves, and that they are articulate enough to verbalise their thoughts, feelings, and behaviours,” 2) “the facilitator who ‘focuses’ the interview can help people retrieve forgotten information” 3) “the dynamics in the group can be used to generate genuine information, rather than the “group think phenomenon,” 4) “interviewing a group is better than interviewing an individual” (Byers and Wilcox, 1991, p. 65), and 5) “identifying and pretesting questionnaire items” (Fern, 1982, p. 1).

Four focus groups with six participants in each focus group (nineteen men and five women) were conducted in this study. An appropriate degree of group engagement was encouraged (Krueger 1994) to stimulate dialogue and explore the idea of employer branding more explicitly. The respondents were between 24 and 52 years old, averaging 37 years. The participants were culturally diverse communities that made the study more valuable (Smithson, 2000). In addition, it allowed the researcher to collect a significant number of answers on the subject (Kover, 1982).

The participants were asked about their perception of employer branding. The questions were primarily unstructured and open-ended so that respondents could answer from a range of dimensions. The data were collected from focus groups by the non-managerial employees and first-line managers working in service firms in Pakistan (University of Sargodha, Habib Bank Ltd, U-fone Ltd., State-life insurance Ltd.), who are experienced in marketing. The participants (employees and first-line managers) were invited to research to explore their opinions, views, beliefs, and behaviours towards employer branding. The main topic of discussion was to highlight key dimensions and outcomes of employer branding. The discussion also includes the influence of employer branding on person-organisation fit, employee job satisfaction, organisation commitment, employee retention, employer brand advocacy, employee performance, employer of choice, and organisation performance. The details of the participants in the focus group are seen in table 4.2.

Participants settled on sites and the scheduling of focus group interviews, mainly in the offices of their respective organisations. The researcher made all attempts to make the environment more conducive and comfortable for respondents to share their views (Malhotra and Birks, 2000). In addition, focus groups offer a platform where participants could interact and share perceptions and opinions (Ritchie et al., 2003). The focus group benefitted from some variation in the group structure and helped the researchers to learn more about what people thought about service sector firms in Pakistan (Churchill, 1979; Krueger, 1994).

Table 4.2: The details of participants in focus groups

Interview date	Number of participants	Interview occupation	Age range	Interview approx. length
13.02.2020	6	Chairman/ HODs of various departments, University of Sargodha	37-52	90 min.
14.02.2020	6	Employees at University Road Branch, Habib Bank Ltd	29-41	90 min
18.02.2020	6	Sales Team, Sargodha Region, U-Fone	24-36	90 min
19.02.2020	6	Assistant Sales Managers, State-life insurance Ltd	31-43	90 min
Topics discussed				
The understanding of employer branding. The key dimensions of employer branding. The general perception about employer branding and its outcomes. Discussion of organisation culture, CSR, WLB, and salary and incentives used in employer branding The main perceived impacts of employer branding on the employer of choice. The main perceived impacts of employer branding on person-organisation fit, job satisfaction, commitment, and employee retention. The main perceived impacts of employer branding on organisation performance.				

Source: The researcher

The interviews with the focus group were recorded and transcribed verbatim. Moreover, the recording of the focus group interview was used to verify the transcripts. For secrecy purposes, participants' names have been substituted by alphabets and their general role in organisation. The following section illustrates how the details were integrated into the creation of the questionnaire.

4.8 THE SECOND PHASE (RESEARCH INSTRUMENT AND SCALE DEVELOPMENT)

This section aims to establish valid and reliable measures for the theoretical established constructs by synthesizing insight from the qualitative study. During the first process, various items were made. For parsimony, few items were similar or equivalent and were thus omitted. A panel of experts consisting of academicians and researchers reviewed the items developed through qualitative analysis and review of relevant literature. The panel of experts recommended modifying/ edits some items. The recommendations were added to ensure the representativeness of all items.

4.8.1 Specifying the domain constructs

The description of the subject area was accomplished by relevant literature and qualitative study, the first step in the construction of questionnaires. As very few studies have provided a reliable and valid measurement of employer branding to the best knowledge of the researcher. Thus, this study filled the gap in this field. It has adopted Churchill's model (1979) for designing better steps for producing a collection of items from literature and qualitative study that capture the construct domain. The operational definition and dimensions of the primary constructs were defined to identify better measurement. Table 4.3 shows important constructs and definitions.

Table 4.3: The main constructs and their definitions

Construct	Definitions	Major References
Employer Branding	Employer branding is a Process of building a recognizable and distinctive employer identity by offering employment benefits (Functional, economic, and psychological) that differentiate it from its competitors.	Biswas and Suar, 2016; Rosengren and Bondesson, 2014; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019.
Organisation Culture	A system comprises values shared by each member of an organisation.	Tanwar and Prasad, 2016
Development and Growth opportunities	Possibility of building career and promotion opportunities within the organisation	Rampl, 2016
Salary and Incentives	Overall compensation package including compensation, perks, and other benefits offered by an employer to motivate employee	Tanwar and Kumar, 2019
Work-life balance	Equilibrium between the person's personal and official life	Tanwar and Prasad, 2016

Employer of choice	An EOC can be an organisation for which a potential employee desires to join and remain with to have some unique benefits	Rosengren and Bondesson, 2014; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019.
Employee Performance	Employee performance is the use of time effectively by an employee to achieve desired outcomes	Haynes, 2007; Mohammad, 2019
Organisation Performance	Organisation performance is defined as goal achievement, the behaviour of organisation participants, and the relationship of organisation with its environment	Kim et al., 2017; Gomes et al. 2017
Organisation Commitment	Organisation commitment is a force psychological bond with an organisation and expression of employees to remain a member of an organisation	Bulut and culha, 2010; Christopher et al., 2019; Kim and Gray, 2017
Job Satisfaction	job satisfaction is the employees' attitude and feeling towards their job and other mechanisms of a job at the workplace	Bangwal and Tiwari, 2019; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016
Employer Brand Advocacy	Voluntary favorable communication, promotion, and spreading a positive word of mouth of organization brand by employee to external stakeholders	Choisa et al. 2018; Men 2014; Tanwar and Prasad 2016
Employee Retention	Employee retention is the effort and determination to keep a desirable employee who contributes towards the success of the organisation	Christopher et al. 2019; Govaerts et al., 2011; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016
Person Organisation fit	A match of employee's values, needs, and ideas with that of organisation enhances more attraction of organization.	Tanwar and Kumar, 2019

Source: Researcher

This research focuses on examining the influences of employer branding on the employer of choice and organisation performance. Therefore, the literature review includes employer branding, employee retention, employee performance, and organisation performance. The existing scales relating to domains and items are extracted from various marketing, branding, and management journals such as the Human Resource Management Review, European Journal of Marketing, International Journal of Advertising, Journal of Marketing Management, Journal of Brand Management, and Based on the theoretical information obtained, the conceptual framework was developed from the literature review.

4.8.2. Generation of measurement items

The second step in the framework of Churchill (1979) is item generation. DeVillis (2003) made the following suggestion to establish the scale: 1) avoiding extraordinary length, 2) double-barrel items, 3) legibility for each item, 4) vague pronoun references, and 5) items with positive and negative wording (p. 68). The researcher used a mixture of literature and qualitative analysis to produce the measurement items (i.e., semi-structured interviews and focus groups) (Churchill, 1979; Gupta et al., 2010, 2011; Palmer, 2011).

The primary purpose of using qualitative study in this research was to uncover new ideas not identified in the literature review. The literature is accompanied by interviews with managers and four focus groups with non-managerial employees in service firms. According to Churchill (1979), each construct should have a multi-item scale. Sholar (Churchilli 1979; Jacoby, 1978; Kotabe 1990; Lichtenstein et al., 1990; Peter 1979, 1981; Zaichkowsky, 1985) stresses that the reliability and validity of measurements used in marketing studies must be studied with explicit focus. The researcher develops some scales dependent on prior studies and inputs from a qualitative study, which are highly reliable and valid. The researcher identified the related items to a minimum to eliminate redundancies and an unusually long questionnaire.

The initial item generation produced 63 items. The measurement items generated: 27 items for the employer branding (used as second-order construct) with six items for organisation culture, seven items for development and growth opportunities, six items for salary and incentives, five items for work-life balance, and three items for equality and justice. Moreover, the researcher developed

four items for person-organisation fit, six items for organisation commitment, six items for job satisfaction, four items for employer brand advocacy, five items for employee retention, five items for employee performance, four items for the employer of choice, and five items for organisation performance. Table 4.4 shows the constructs and the number of initial items.

Table 4.4: The constructs and the number of initial items used for EFA

Constructs		No. of initial items
Employer branding		27 (6+7+5+6+3)
Dimensions of employer branding	Organisation culture	6
	Development and Growth opportunities	7
	Work-life balance	5
	Salary and incentives	6
	Equality and justice	3
Person organisation fit	4	
Organisation commitment	6	
Job satisfaction	6	
Employee retention	5	
Employer brand advocacy	4	
Employee performance	5	
Employer of choice	4	
Organisation performance	5	

Source: Researcher

The following primary constructs and their measurements from the literature and the qualitative study are illustrated below.

Table 4.5: The domain and items of construct in extant literature

Construct	Measurement items	Major references
Organisation culture		
	My organisation offers good internal training opportunities	Tanwar and Kumar (2019); Tanwar and Prasad (2016)
	In my organisation, friendly relationships exist among individual co-workers	Dabirian and Diba (2017); Gilani and Cunningham (2017); Sedighi and Loosemore (2012); Tanwar and Kumar (2019); Tanwar and Prasad (2016a); Supported with Qualitative study

My organisation follows the rules and regulations	Dabirian and Diba (2017); Gilani and Cunningham (2017); Tanwar and Prasad (2016); Supported with Qualitative study
My organisation provides recognition/appreciation from management	Dabirian and Diba (2017); Gilani and Cunningham (2017); Tanwar and Kumar (2019); Tanwar and Prasad (2016i)
My organisation offers job security	Dabirian and Diba (2017); Sedighi and Loosemore (2012); Tanwar and Kumar (2019); Tanwar and Prasad (2016i); Supported with Qualitative study
In my organisation, Bosses are supportive	The qualitative study
Development and Growth opportunities	
My organisation has good opportunities for career advancement	Lievens et al., (2005); Lee and Bruvold (2003); Rampl (2014); Weng and Hu, 2009
My organisation has good promotion opportunities within the organisation	Lievens et al., (2005); Rampl (2014); Weng and Hu (2009); Supported with Qualitative study
My organisation offers the possibility of building a career	Lee and Bruvold (2003); Rampl (2014); Weng and Hu, 2009;
In my organisation, every employee has equal opportunities for career advancement and career-building	The qualitative study
My organisation has a plan for individual (Skills) development.	The qualitative study
In my organisation, there is a policy of employee rotation to various jobs/roles to grow and develop my skills	The qualitative study
My organisation has a defined promotion policy.	The qualitative study
Salaries and incentives	
My organisation offers above-average compensation and benefits	Tanwar and Kumar (2019); Tanwar and Prasad (2017); Turban (2001).
My organisation offers additional benefits to motivate employees	Tanwar and Kumar (2019); Tanwar and Prasad (2017); Turban (2001).
My organisation offers an attractive overall compensation package	Berthon et al., (2005); Tanwar and Kumar (2019); Tanwar and Prasad (2017); Turban (2001).
My organisation provides overtime pay	Tanwar and Prasad (2017)
My organisation provides medical and insurance coverage for employees and dependents	Tanwar and Prasad (2017)
My organisation offers attractive retirement benefits	The qualitative study
Work-Life Balance	
My organisation provides flexible working hours	Kumari and Saini (2018); Tanwar and Prasad (2016a); Tüzüner and Yuksel (2009); Supported with Qualitative study
My organisation provides the opportunity to work from home	Carlier et al., (2012); Kumari and Saini (2018); Tanwar and Prasad (2016i); Supported with Qualitative study
My organisation provides access to paid parental leave	Kumari and Saini (2018); Tanwar and Prasad (2016i); Tüzüner and Yuksel (2009); Supported with Qualitative study

In my organisatin, employees are permitted to leave the workplace in case of a family emergency	Carlier et al., (2012); Kumari and Saini (2018); Tanwar and Prasad (2016); Supported with Qualitative study
My organisation provides on-site sports activities	Kumari and Saini (2018); Tanwar and Prasad (2016)
Equality and Justice	
My work schedule is fair (I am not overburdened at work)	The qualitative study, Colquitt et al., (2001); Greenberg, (1990)
My organisation distributes rewards quite fairly	The qualitative study, Colquitt et al., (2001); Greenberg, (1990)
When decisions are made about my job, my supervisor treats me with kindness and consideration.	The qualitative study, Colquitt et al., (2001); Greenberg, (1990)
Organisation Commitment	
It is my good decision to choose this organisation where I am working today.	The qualitative study
I suggest my friends join my organisation	The qualitative study
I am motivated to remain part of my organisation	The qualitative study
I talk to my friends that the organisation where I am currently working is an excellent organisation to work for	Arasanmi and Krishna (2019); Karia (2019); Meyer and Allen (1991); Supported with Qualitative study
I care about the future of my organisation	Arasanmi and Krishna (2019); Karia (2019); Meyer and Allen (1991);
I am willing to put more efforts to work for this organisation	Arasanmi and Krishna (2019); Karia (2019); Meyer and Allen (1991); Supported with Qualitative study
Job Satisfaction	
I am satisfied with the amount of pay I receive from my organisation.	Homburg and Stock (2005); Homburg and Stock (2005); Karia (2019); Tanwar and Prasad (2016a); Supported with Qualitative study
I am satisfied with my colleagues in my organisation	Homburg and Stock (2005); Karia (2019); Tanwar and Prasad (2016a); Supported with Qualitative study
I am satisfied with the working conditions of my organisation	Homburg and Stock (2005); Karia (2019); Tanwar and Prasad (2016i); Supported with Qualitative study
I am satisfied with my job in my organisation	Homburg and Stock (2005); Karia (2019); Tanwar and Prasad (2016i); Supported with Qualitative study
I am satisfied with the feeling of accomplishment I get from the job in my organisation	Fernandes and Moreira (2019); Homburg and Stock (2005); Karia (2019); Tanwar and Prasad (2016a) ;
Overall, I am satisfied with my organisation	Homburg and Stock (2005); Menidjel (2017); Tanwar and Prasad (2016a)
Employer Brand Advocacy	
I have the best possible information about my organisation	Kim et al., (2001); Tanwar and Prasad (2016i);
I talk directly to other people about my experience with my organisation.	Kemp (2012); Kim et al., (2001); Tanwar and Prasad (2016i)
I suggest to others that they should join my organisation.	Chiosa and Anastasiei (2018); Kemp (2012); Supported with Qualitative study

I speak favourably about my organisation	Chiosa and Anastasiei (2018); Tanwar and Prasad (2016i); Supported with Qualitative study
Employee Retention	
I see a future for myself within my organisation.	Govaerts (2011); Kyndt et al., (2009); Tanwar and Prasad (2016a); Supported with Qualitative study
I will like to work for my organisation for the next five years.	Govaerts (2011); Kyndt et al., (2009); Tanwar and Prasad (2016i); Supported with Qualitative study
On the job, I have sufficient opportunity to use my talents and use my initiative.	Govaerts (2011)
My colleagues want to stay with my organisation for a longer time	The qualitative study
If I wanted to do another job or function, I would look first at the possibilities within my current organisation	Govaerts (2011); Kyndt et al., (2009)
Person Organisation Fit	
My skills and abilities match the skills and abilities my organisation looks for as an employee	Tanwar and Kumar 2019; Memon et al., 2018.
I feel my organisation suits my style of working	Tanwar and Kumar 2019; Memon et al., 2018.
I feel my values are a good fit for my organisation.	Tanwar and Kumar 2019; Memon et al., 2018.
My values match those of current employees in an organisation.	Tanwar and Kumar 2019; Memon et al., 2018.
Employer of Choice	
My organisation is one of my first choices as an employer	Highhouse et al., (2003); Sivertzen (2013); Tanwar and Kumar (2019)
My organisation is the most attractive employer for me	Highhouse et al., (2003); Sivertzen (2013); Tanwar and Kumar (2019)
I wanted a job with my current organisation	Highhouse et al., (2003); Sivertzen (2013); Tanwar and Kumar (2019)
It was my dream to join my current organisation	The qualitative study
Employee Performance	
It is not difficult for me to fulfill my work obligations	Mohammad (2019); Paterson (1992); Supported with Qualitative study
I usually meet work deadline at work	Mohammad (2019); Paterson (1992)
I usually leave the office after completing my work	Mohammad (2019); Paterson (1992)
I add value to my work in my organisation	Aboelmaged (2018); Paterson (1992)
I am an effective worker	Aboelmaged (2018); Paterson (1992); Supported with Qualitative study
Organisation Performance (in my organisation, Compare to last five years)	
Customers' satisfaction increased	Kim and Gray (2017); Supported with Qualitative study
There is sufficient growth in the number of customers	Kim and Gray (2017); Supported with Qualitative study
Employee satisfaction increased	Gomes and Carvalho (2017); Kim and Gray (2017)
Quality in products and services increased	Gomes and Carvalho (2017); Kim and Gray (2017); Supported with Qualitative study
Organisational reputation in the market increased	Kim and Gray (2017)

4.8.3. Purifying measurement scales

The third step for improved Churchill's (1979) paradigm is the purification of the measurement scales. The validity is "the degree to which the researcher was trying to measure, was measured" (McDaniel and Gates, 2006, p. 224). In the preliminary stages and before performing the main survey, two forms of validity were performed: content validity and face validity. Both types of validities demonstrate the adequacy of the questionnaire and are subjective. According to Kerlinger (1973), content validity is essentially based on judgment and applies the extent to which a particular set of items reflects the content domain (DeVellis, 2003).

The content validity of the items was done with the help of a panel of experts. The first version of measurement items was discussed with seven faculty members and professionals working in the Marketing or HRM departments in Pakistan. Those were familiar with the topic and assessed for content validity by using judging procedures (Bearden et al., 1993; Zaichkowsky, 1985). They were asked to check the clarity of each item's wording and comment on the appropriateness of the item; the Researcher then added their recommendations (Lichtenstein et al., 1990). They thoroughly check each item for its suitability and representativeness for the area of being investigated. Academics that were part of the said panel have been served in previous studies as judges on a scale domain.

All items used 7-point Likert scales (anchored by 0, strongly disagree, and 7 strongly agree), and the respondents were employees, based on how well they perceived the situation. The Likert scale

allows respondents to specify a level of familiarity or difference to measure attitudes towards employer branding. Likert is the most widely used scale in marketing research and offers adequate properties for disseminating underlying answers (Bagozzi, 1994). The researchers (Churchill and Peter, 1984; O' Neill and Palmer, 2004) proposed that the number of scale points should be expanded to a Likert 5-point scale with a Likert 7-point scale to maximize construct variance and minimise measurement error variance to replace the ubiquitous. Based on the findings of the quantitative analysis, the constructs were updated and submitted to the questionnaire for scale purification and pilot study.

Table 4.6: Measurement items of the theoretical constructs and the codes before EFA

Construct	Measurement items	Major references
Organisation culture		
	My organisation offers good internal training opportunities	OC_1
	In my organisation, friendly relationships exist among individual co-workers	OC_2
	My organisation follows the rules and regulations	OC_3
	My organisation provides recognition/appreciation from management	OC_4
	My organisation offers job security	OC_5
	In my organisation, Bosses are supportive	OC_6
Development and Growth opportunities		
	My organisation has good opportunities for career advancement	DGO_1
	My organisation has good promotion opportunities within the organisation	DGO_2
	My organisation offers the possibility of building a career	DGO_3
	In my organisation, every employee has equal opportunities for career advancement and career-building	DGO_4
	My organisation has a plan for individual (Skills) development.	DGO_5
	In my organisation, there is a policy of employee rotation to various jobs/roles to grow and develop my skills	DGO_6
	My organisation has a defined promotion policy.	DGO_7
Salaries and incentives		
	My organisation offers above-average compensation and benefits	SI_1
	My organisation offers additional benefits to motivate employees	SI_2
	My organisation offers an attractive overall compensation package	SI_3
	My organisation provides overtime pay	SI_4

My organisation provides medical and insurance coverage for employees and dependents	SI_5
My organisation offers attractive retirement benefits	SI_6
Work-Life Balance	
My organisation provides flexible working hours	WLB_1
My organisation provides the opportunity to work from home	WLB_2
My organisation provides access to paid parental leave	WLB_3
In my organisation, employees are permitted to leave the workplace in case of a family emergency	WLB_4
My organisation provides on-site sports activities	WLB_5
Equality and Justice	
My work schedule is fair (I am not overburdened at work)	EJ_1
My organisation distributes rewards quite fairly	EJ_2
When decisions are made about my job, my supervisor treats me with kindness and consideration.	EJ_3
Organisation Commitment	
It is my good decision to choose this organisation where I am working today.	OCM_1
I suggest my friends join my organisation	OCM_2
I am motivated to remain part of my organisation	OCM_3
I talk to my friends that the organisation where I am currently working is an excellent organisation to work for	OCM_4
I care about the future of my organisation	OCM_5
I am willing to put more efforts to work for this organisation	OCM_6
Job Satisfaction	
I am satisfied with the amount of pay I receive from my organisation.	JS_1
I am satisfied with my colleagues in my organisation	JS_2
I am satisfied with the working conditions of my organisation	JS_3
I am satisfied with my job in my organisation	JS_4
I am satisfied with the feeling of accomplishment I get from the job in my organisation	JS_5
Overall, I am satisfied with my organisation	JS_6
Employer Brand Advocacy	
I have the best possible information about my organisation	EBA_1
I talk directly to other people about my experience with my organisation.	EBA_2
I suggest to others that they should join my organisation.	EBA_3
I speak favourably about my organisation	EBA_4
Employee Retention	
I see a future for myself within my organisation.	ER_1
I will like to work for my organisation for the next five years.	ER_2

On the job, I have sufficient opportunity to use my talents and use my initiative.	ER_3
My colleagues want to stay with my organisation for a longer time	ER_4
If I wanted to do another job or function, I would look first at the possibilities within my current organisation	ER_5
Person Organisation Fit	
My skills and abilities match the skills and abilities my organisation looks for as an employee	POF_1
I feel my organisation suits my style of working	POF_2
I feel my values are a good fit for my organisation.	POF_3
My values match those of current employees in an organisation.	POF_4
Employer of Choice	
My organisation is one of my first choices as an employer	EOC_1
My organisation is the most attractive employer for me	EOC_2
I wanted a job with my current organisation	EOC_3
It was my dream to join my current organisation	EOC_4
Employee Performance	
It is not difficult for me to fulfill my work obligations	EP_1
I usually meet work deadline at work	EP_2
I usually leave the office after completing my work	EP_3
I add value to my work in my organisation	EP_4
I am an effective worker	EP_5
Organisation Performance (Compare to last five years)	
Customers' satisfaction increased	OP_1
There is sufficient growth in the number of customers	OP_2
Employee satisfaction increased	OP_3
Quality in products and services increased	OP_4
Organisational reputation in the market increased	OP_5

Source: Researcher

4.9 PILOT STUDY

Essentially, pilot studies are preliminary small-scaled studies that are carried out to verify specific components of the main study. Typically, this relates to randomized controlled trials to test the feasibility of the chosen samples. Pilot studies are beneficial for large-scale studies which aim to optimize the study design and predict appropriate sample sizes for the full-scale study (Saunders et al., 2000). A pilot study was undertaken to figure out the uniformity of the items in the

questionnaire. Moreover, a pilot study helps to judge the understanding of respondents related to the research questionnaire. In this pilot study, a referral sampling method was used in order to draw the sample. By following the suggestions of Hair et al. (2004), for the testing appropriateness of questionnaire data was collected from 80 respondents. Before collecting data, respondents were told about the purpose of the study. All respondents of this pilot study were current employees of service firms in Pakistan.

4.9.1 Participants

Table 4.7 presents the demographic information of respondents for the pilot study. The response rate in each industry was as follows; University 27%, Banks 15%, sports 13%, Insurance firms 08%, Travel agency 08%, Hotel 11%, Hospital 09%, Transportation firms 12 and Courier/ Postal Services 10%. About 66% of respondents were male, and 34% were female. 9% of respondents were below 25 years of age, 53% of respondents were between 25 to 34 years, 29% of respondents were between 35 to 44 years, and 9% were above 44 years of age.

As far as the qualification of respondents is concerned, 93% respondents had post-graduation, 5% respondents had graduation, and only 02% respondents had Under-graduation. The majority of respondents had a vast experience of their relative fields, with 30% respondents have less than 6-year experience, 32% of respondents have 6 to 10 years' experience, 30% respondents have 11 to 15 years' experience, and 08% of respondents have more than 15 years' experience.

Table 4.7: Demographic Characteristics of Responding Firms

Demographic Profile	Respondents (80)	Valid %
Industry		
University	22	27
Bank	12	15
Insurance Firm	6	8
Forces	6	8
Hotel	9	11
Hospital	7	9
Transportation Firm	10	12
Telecom	8	10
Gender		
Male	53	66
Female	27	34
Age		
Less than 25 Years	7	9
25-34 Years	43	53
35-44 Years	23	29
45 or more Years	7	9
Education Level		
Undergraduate/Intermediate	1	2
Graduate/ Bachelor	4	5
Post Graduate/ Master and above	75	93
Experience		
Up to 5 Years	24	30
6-10 Years	26	32
11-15 Years	24	30
16 or more Years	6	8

Source: Survey data

4.9.2 Results Discussion of Pilot Study

The observation and feedback from respondents in the pilot study illustrate much of the questionnaire's shortcomings. For example, the respondents recommend that additional space be available between the various categories of questions in a related section to make reading the questionnaire easier. The pilot study respondents also suggested that the directions for the construct should be more precise and detailed, whereas the size of the questionnaire items occupying more pages should be given on each page. Therefore, recommendations were considered while going for large-scale data collection.

The Cronbach alpha was used to determine the reliability of the constructs (Churchill, 1979), whose acceptable value (reliability) should be greater than 0.70 (Hair Jr et al., 2016). Table 4.8 displays the composite reliability values between 0.901 and 0.960 and between 0.863 and 0.948 of Cronbach alpha. The composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values were above 0.7 and acceptable, so all values for the constructs fall into an acceptable range (Hair Jr et al., 2016). However, because of the limited sample size in the pilot study, the validity of the results cannot be confirmed. Consequently, the validity review was carried out after the final data set was processed.

Table 4.8: Reliability for Pilot Study

Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Organisation Culture	0.907	0.931
Development and growth opportunities	0.922	0.944
Work-Life Balance	0.904	0.933
Salaries and Incentives	0.911	0.937
Equality and justice	0.883	0.928
Organisation commitment	0.894	0.927
Job Satisfaction	0.906	0.927
Employee Retention	0.910	0.933
Employer Brand Advocacy	0.948	0.960
Employee performance	0.863	0.901
Employer of choice	0.922	0.945
Organisation Performance	0.915	0.937

Source: Survey data

4.10. MAIN SURVEY

4.10.1 Study Population

According to the Pakistan economic survey report (2020) total population of Pakistan is 212 million, and the total employed labour force is 65.5 million. Moreover, the total employees currently working in the service sector are 38.32% of the total employed workforce in the country

(Economic survey report, 2020). The population of the is employees currently working in service firms of Pakistan. Hence the size of the population is 25 million (25099600). Table 4.9 presents the classification of service firms in Pakistan.

Table 4.9: Classification of Services Sector in Pakistan

I. Distributive Services	
Communications and Transportation	Road, Rail, Water, and Air Transport Mechanised and Non- Mechanised Communications
Retail Trade, Wholesale Trade, and Restaurants, and Hotels	Hotels and Restaurants Retail and Wholesale Trade including Purchase and Sale Agents and Brokers
II. Producer Services	
Financial Institution	Commercial Bank and State Bank of Pakistan Insurance Corporations and Financial Intermediaries
III. Personal Services	
Recreation and Entertainment Services	Cinema, theatre Parks TV and Film Industry/ Production Houses
IV. Social Services	
Public Administration and Defence	Forces Intelligence agencies
Social Community and Private Services	Education Medical and Health Services Emergency Rescue Services Other Household and Community Services

Source: Economic Survey reports (2020) and Annual Report of State Bank of Pakistan (2020)

4.10.1.2 Target Population

Among all sub-sectors in service are identified and selected/targeted specific sectors that comparatively contribute more to Pakistan's economy and are well organized, documented, and easily accessible (Pakistan Bauru of Statistics, 2020). All firms located/ Operational in PUNJAB

province, which is the largest province of Pakistan with 7,25,85,000 individuals (Economics Survey report of Pakistan, 2020), were targeted instead of covering the whole country due to time and financial resources constrain. Hence, the total population of employees targeted was 9,950,000. Table 4.10 shows firms that were to target significant service industries in Pakistan.

Table 4.10: Selected Services Sector firm in Pakistan for study

Sr. No.	Service Sector	Firms
1.	Road Transport	Transportation firms
2.	Communications	Telecom firms
3.	Hotels	3-5 Star Hotels
4.	Commercial Bank	Schedule Banks
5.	Insurance Corporations	Insurance Firms
6.	Forces	Punjab Police Department Pakistan Army Pakistan Air force
7.	Education	Universities
8.	Medical and Health Services	Hospitals

Source: Researcher.

4.10.2 Sampling Strategy

It is challenging to organize the survey process with the consideration of the whole population. Therefore, it is essential to select a suitable sample from the target population that represents the whole population to ensure the successful organisation of the survey process (Zikmund, 2003). This process also permits the researcher to generalize the findings from a sample to the population. The use of sampling strategy during research assists the researcher in getting exact, valid, and more reliable information directly from the selected participants.

Probability and non-probability are two effective sampling strategies that support the researcher in selecting a suitable sample size. A probability sampling strategy allows the researcher to select a random sample from the targeted population (Rubin and Babbie, 2010). On the contrary, the non-probability sampling method is based on subjective judgments, and in this, samples are

selected in some way not proposed by sampling theory. Some main non-probability sampling methods include snowball, judgmental, and quota sampling, convenience sampling (Babbie, 2013). At the same time, under the probability method, there are several methods such as random sampling, Systematic sampling, stratified sampling , and others that can be used by the researcher with the suitability with the research problem.

In behavioural science, sampling processes are split into probability and Non-probability (Teddlie and Yu, 2007). Probability sampling techniques are typically utilized in quantitative investigations since they include randomly picking many units from a population to determine the probability of inclusion for each member of a population. The goal is to obtain representativeness, or how well a sample reflects a whole population. Non-Probability sampling is a methodology primarily used in qualitative research that involves picking units for particular goals related to addressing the study's questions. Appropriate places, people, or events are picked in this sampling approach for the knowledge they can provide that cannot be obtained from other sources (Maxwell, 1997; Teddlie and Yu, 2007). External validity may be improved using probability sampling, and generalisability may be improved using non-probability sampling procedures.

Probability sampling is the more recognized of the two since it allows for more confidence in the representativeness of the sample, and so boosts the validity of the results (Haber, 2002; Parahoo, 2006; Robson, 2011). Non-probability, on the other hand, is when the components are chosen from a sample that is thought to be the most capable of providing the data required. Another point of view is that using non-probability samples with small sample sizes is usual practice (Robson, 2011), and researchers frequently employ a sample of convenience, which is a sort of non-

probability sampling for in-depth interviews and focus groups (Moule and Goodman, 2014). Phase one of the current investigation employed a non-probability, convenience sample.

In the service sector, non-probability samples were most commonly utilized, with convenience sampling being the most common (Haber 2002; Parahoo, 2006). The difficulty in generalising results is a well-known drawback of convenience sampling. Another downside is the danger of bias, which arises from convenience samples being self-selecting or consisting of people who agree to participate (Haber, 2002). Hence the representativeness of those who did participate in respect to the population may be called into question (Haber, 2002).

However, in the current study, as indicated by Haber (2002) and Parahoo (2006), the careful selection was made to reflect the target population, and detailed inclusion and exclusion criteria were established, resulting in confidence in the representativeness and validity of the findings, to the extent feasible. The target population is selected service sector employees who are currently working in the organisation. A further aim was to promote the validity and representativeness of the sample by using criteria that reflected the target population. Inclusion Criteria: 1) Employee working for full-time capacity and Permanent/Regular (Not on probation or training) within the service sector firm. Exclusion Criteria: 2) Employee at apprentice or training or newly selected in service sector firm.

Focus group interviews were conducted using purposeful sampling. According to Parahoo (2006) and Moule and Goodman (2014), purposive sampling is appropriate when acquiring information from a group of knowledgeable participants about the topic at hand and are regarded as

representative of the population. Purposive sampling is commonly employed in qualitative research (Moule and Goodman, 2014). Purposive sampling has the same drawbacks as convenience sampling, according to Parahoo (2006) and Moule and Goodman (2014): the capacity to generalize the findings is limited, and because participation is voluntary, there is a higher risk of bias being introduced. To tackle the issues mentioned above, experienced and well-educated employees were selected to share their opinions on employer branding and its outcomes based on their perceptions and experiences (Haber, 2002; Parahoo, 2006).

Snowball sampling was used to collect quantitative data through a questionnaire. Purposive sampling used in the qualitative phase of the study is comparable with snowball sampling since the researcher chooses the participants based on their ability and experience regarding the social phenomena studied (Bryman and Bell, 2015). The use of snowball sampling for this study was followed, encouraging the participants to help identify and recommend other participants with expertise relevant to the research subject (Bryman and Bell, 2015). In other words, snowball sampling is a type of sampling in which the researcher initially contacts a small group of participants who are significant to the research topic. These participants will be asked to refer other informants who share a similar experience or knowledge relevant to the research under question. The issue arising with snowball sampling is that they are less likely to represent the population (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

4.10.2.1 Sample Size

Saunders et al. (2009) believed that sample size helps generalization about the population. Sampling is the process of selecting a specific number of objects from the population. The selection

of these units is based on criteria that produce the outcome by generalizing the total population sample. According to Lindner et al. (2001), from the known population, the minimum sample size can be calculated with a margin of error of 5% (Lindner et al., 2001). Hence. Following Linder et al.'s recommendation minimum sample size for the current study was 384. Similarly, Krejcie and Morgan (1970) claim that a sample size of 384 is adequate to estimate the unbiased parameters accurately.

Furthermore, a cases and parameters ratio implies that a 10:1 minimum sample size ratio is necessary to estimate structural equation modeling using maximum likelihood estimation (Kline, 2011). The maximum likelihood approach of estimate for the SEM is not used in this study. The model is instead estimated using PLS-SEM. As a result, a minimum sample size of 500 was set as the study's goal (Krejcie & Morgan, 1975).

4.11. DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

4.11.1 Introduction to Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used for the application of CFA to test the hypothesis. It is found predominantly that the SEM technique is beneficial in behavioural and social sciences when the study consists of several unobserved constructs (Sharma, 1996). SEM is therefore of great use for researchers to test the validity, reliability, and uni-dimensionality of all constructs. Furthermore, the researcher could measure the model fitness using SEM and simultaneously evaluate the test of individual parameter estimates (Gefen, 2000; Hsu, 2010; Lowry and Gaskin, 2014). Scholars frequently use SEM in academic study, particularly in the social sciences (Gupta et al., 2011; Kline, 2005).

In addition, SEM is considered an excellent tool for multivariate data processing (Hershberger, 2003). In addition, researchers could concurrently analyse all hypothesised correlations between variables, including multiple dependent variables in one analysis (Hsu, 2010; Jia et al., 2014). The researchers have identified two significant alternatives for using SEM as covariance-based - software such as AMOS, LISREL, EQS, and software used for variance-based techniques PLS Graph and Smart PLS software (Ringle et al., 2016)

4.11.1.1 SEM Assumptions

Many assumptions exist in implementing SEM for data analytics, such as normally distributed data and sufficient sample size. It is imperative to presume data normality since data is not normal and thus leads to infringement of other assumptions (Henseler et al., 2015). Furthermore, sufficient sample size is needed to implement SEM, as the covariance and correlation are less stable with limited sample size estimates (Kline, 2005; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2001). Moreover, with a limited sample size, a significant path coefficient is difficult to find, and covariance matrix instability (sample error) is produced, leading to a low degree of fitness and providing inadmissible solutions (Quintana and Maxwell, 1999). PLS-SEM is thus used in this analysis to evaluate the model for theoretical studies on the following grounds:

According to Hair et al. (2014) and Ringle et al. (2010), researchers should prefer PLS-SEM techniques over CB-SEM when 1) the research goal is to explore and extend an existing structural theory. 2) formative constructs are part of the structural model. 3) a structural model is complex. 4) distribution is non-normal. 5) Use latent variable scores in subsequent analyses 6) sample size is less than 200. This study investigates a large number of latent variables and a complex

theoretical model. Moreover, the structural model of the study includes a mix of reflective and formative measures. Hence, PLS-SEM is the most appropriate technique to analyse quantitative data for the current study (Hair et al., 2014; Ringle et al., 2010).

The econometrician Herman Wold made PLS based on the alternate least square's algorithms, which also can extend principal components and perform canonical analysis of constructs based on correlation (Hair et al., 2014). According to Hair et al. (2014), the model with paths represents the measurement and the structural model. The measurement model postulates the relationships between unobserved variables. On the other hand, the structural/ outer model identifies the relationships between latent variables and the observed variables.

4.11.1.2 Reflective and Formative Constructs

According to SEM literature, the modeling of a latent variable can be done using either formative or reflective indicators. Reflective variables can be utilized as constructs that are impacted by another underlying construct, according to Jarvis, MacKenzie, and Podsakoff (2003), which necessitates parallel measurements that also co-vary and assess another underlying construct at the same time. The reflective construct's arrow points from LV to the reflective indicators. In reflective constructs, the indicators should also be internally consistent since all measurements are believed to be equally legitimate indicators of the underlying latent variable (Ringle and Sarstedt, 2016). A combination of indicators comes together in a reflective construct to determine the construct's conceptual and empirical meaning. From indicators to a latent variable, causation goes in one direction (Petter et al., 2007).

For a reflective construct, internal consistency is critical. As a result, using internal reliability measures necessitates ensuring that the measures are reliable. Furthermore, a reflective construct is usually one-dimensional, and removing any of the measures will not influence the content validity (Ringle and Sarstedt, 2016). The formative construct is a construct that includes formative indicators coupled to provide the latent variable with some meaning (Jarvis et al., 2003).

Formative indicators are not always correlated, and they do not have much internal consistency. Thus, any changes in the formative measures will affect the underlying concept (Jarvis et al., 2003). The latent construct represents distinct dimensions of the formative construct resulting from a formative construct (Hair et al., 2000). These observed variables are not supposed to be associated or represent the same underlying dimension (Chin, 1998a). The formative construct has an arrow pointing from formative indicators to LV. The diagram of reflecting and formative structures is shown in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: The Diagrams of Reflective and Formative Constructs

Source: Petter et al. (2007)

When reflective measures are used in constructs, loadings are also looked at since they show the relationship between the indicators and component scores (Henseler et al., 2015). On the other hand, weight should be used to evaluate constructs using formative measurements since they provide information about the value of each indication in forming a component (Chin, 1998a). It is critical to use previous knowledge to identify the causation flow to avoid measurement model misspecification (Gefen et al., 2000).

4.11.1.3 Evaluating Measurement Model Using Partial Least Square

In this research, a two-step approach is used to evaluate a theoretical model. Firstly, by assessing the measurement model and secondly, by assessing the structural model. Model validation aims to determine if both models (measurement and structural) experimentally justify the quality standards (Chin et al., 2013). The guidelines utilised in this study evaluate both the measurement and the structural model of the current thesis. The reliability and validity of a reflective measurement model are tested during validation (Chin et al., 2003).

4.11.1.3.1 Internal Consistency

Measurement is considered reliable when the predictions generated are consistent when reflecting unchanging social circumstances, regardless of the probability of chance and variations in techniques (Saunders and Lewis, 2009). “A reliable measure is stable and devoid of the effects of random errors” (Brewer and Hunter, 1989). Typically, researchers use one of two ways to test an instrument's reliability, and both need internal consistency of measurement. The first method is to use Cronbach's Alpha to determine the degree to which the elements in a cluster positively interrelate with one another (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). An alpha value of less than 0.6 is

considered flawed, those between 0.7 and 0.8 are acceptable, and those more than 0.8 are considered excellent (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

The composite reliability generated from the SEM analysis is assessed in the second technique. This approach equals Cronbach's coefficient alpha since it examines internal consistency. On the other hand, composite reliability is a superior choice, according to Hult et al. (2004), since it incorporates the standardized loadings and measurement error for each item over the coefficient alpha. The coefficient alpha has limits; for example, it implies that all items have the same reliability distribution; in this study, both criteria are utilized to determine the level of reliability.

4.11.1.3.2 Indicator Reliability

The reliability of indicators is assessed to the point where constructs are consistent with what they are supposed to measure (Hair et al., 2011). The reliability construct is distinct from the others and is calculated separately. The loading value of an indicator must be significant up to the 0.05 level, and the loading must be more than 0.7 (Hair et al., 2011). According to Hensler et al. (2015), one must be careful when eliminating an indication in PLS. As a result of removing the indication with low dependability, the CR increases.

4.11.1.3.3 Validity

Researchers are also concerned about the validity of the collected data. The validity of a questionnaire is determined by computing the selected questions using measuring techniques (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The majority of research reports on two forms of validity: construct validity and face or content validity.

4.11.1.3.4 Face or Content Validity

A final version of the questionnaires was created based on comments and suggestions. Content validity assures that the set of units created from the start of the scale development process reflects the primary hypothesis. Content validity is assessed at the outset of scale explanations by establishing a set of units and having laypeople or specialists (or both) evaluate them (Sharma et al., 2003). This research includes a literature review to determine existing scales and interviews with experts in the subject, including academic and industry leaders. In addition, the questionnaire would be reviewed by at least three experts in the industry to see if it is clear, user-friendly, and easy to understand, as well as having appropriate response forms.

4.11.1.3.5 Construct Validity

The extent to which a particular measure matches other comparable measures with the theoretically based hypothesis constructions being tested is investigated through construct validity (Carmines and Zeller, 1979). discriminant validity, Convergent validity, and nomological validity are three tests that are frequently used to establish construct validity. When items used to compute the same construct are correlated at least to a significant degree, convergent validity is present (Kane, 2010).

Furthermore, It may be assessed by examining the significance and strength of correlations between items within the same concept (Netemeyer et al., 2003). The statistical procedure known as confirmatory factor analysis may also be used to establish convergent and discriminant validity. Convergent validity, according to Jiang et al. (2012), analyses factor loading and the average variance extracted (AVE). Factor loadings of higher than 0.35 are acceptable as a first step. The

AVE is determined in the following step. The AVE estimates the latent construct-adjusted total degree of variation in the indicators. An acceptable AVE is defined as a degree of normality of 50% or above (Bagozzi and Yi, 1988).

If the interrelationships between a group of factors used to calculate various things are not significantly high, they have discriminant validity (Kline, 2010). Similarly, discriminant validity states that a variable should not significantly affect other variables expected to vary (Netemeyer et al., 2003). The general test devised by Bagozzi and Yi is used to assess discriminant validity (1988). The AVE for any particular construct should be greater than the squared correlation of that construct with another construct, according to them (Hair, Ringle, and Sarstedt, 2013).

Therefore, in the present study, the validity of the measurement model is acceptable when: 1) The Composit reliability value is more than 0.8. 2) The item loading is greater than 0.7, and the p-value is less than 0.05. 3) The AVE value is higher than 0.50. 4) The square root value of the AVE of a construct is higher than the correlations between the construct and other constructs in the model.

4.11.1.4 Evaluating Structural Models using Partial Least Square

The structural model validation method helps determine the support for hypotheses by the data (Urbach and Ahlemann, 2010). The coefficient of determination (R^2) and path coefficients are used to examine the SM in PLS. The R^2 value of each DV, which explains the latent variable's (LV's) variance to its overall variance, is used to evaluate the PLS-SEM. High variance is represented by R^2 value 0.67, whereas moderate variance is represented by R^2 value 0.33, and weak variance is represented by R^2 value 0.19. The size, algebraic sign, and significance level of

the link between two latent variables, as measured by the path coefficient value (B). To account for a significant influence, the value of path coefficients inside the model should be larger than 0.100 with a p-value greater than 0.05 (Huber et al., 2007).

4.12 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

The researcher completed this study ethically to enhance the validity and dependability of the selected methodologies and final research results. For accomplishing this inquiry ethically, the researcher follows all rules and regulations provided by the university and research ethics committee. In addition to this, the author of the study also collected data by using authentic and relevant data sources, including books, journal articles, magazines, Company websites. Concurrently, the researcher also presented the information gathered from the interview and questionnaire process participants without obtaining desired results.

The consent of participants of the survey and interview process was sought in advance. Moreover, the researcher briefed the participant has clearly about the purpose of the study. At the same time, the researcher also informed the participants of the purpose of the survey and interview, what kind of questions will be asked, whether a personal question will be asked or not, and if yes, what kind of security tools will be asked used through the participant information sheet. All these were beneficial to attain the participants' permission to be a part of the research.

In addition, the researcher also described the confidentiality of the information related to the participants' background and other private information. The researcher also stated that all the information would be kept secured in password-protected computers and laptops to ensure

adequate security. Moreover, results will be published in consolidated form without the identification of the individual respondent.

All ethical considerations were made in this research are presented following under various headings:

- 1. Informed consent and autonomy:** informed consent from respondents and authorization was obtained from the service firms involved in the study.
- 2. Beneficence:** the questions were framed to avoid inflicting harm to the participants, and the interviews were conducted in a safe and secure environment. The participants were informed of their anonymity and that the information provided would not be used in a manner that could result in injury or loss of livelihood.
- 3. Dignity:** the anonymity of the participants was safeguarded. The participants were also reminded that their participation was voluntary, and they could refuse to disclose information at any stage.
- 4. Equitability:** the participants were selected and treated fairly, with no discrimination or prejudice, ensuring a respectful environment and relationship ensued before, during, and after the research.
- 5. Researcher competence:** the affiliate institution approved the research study. The researcher also participated in and passed a research methodology program and was in close contact with a supervisor.

3.10 SUMMARY

From the above discussion, it can be summarized that successfully selecting and using various research methods is crucial in completing the research. It can also be concluded that as this inquiry applies the use of multi-method component design, the use of a mixed approach is suitable to address the research objectives effectively. Additionally, the employment of pragmatist

philosophy is also appropriate for this study because it helps determine the link between both interpretive and positive research philosophies. Moreover, it also suits the use of both inductive and deductive approaches that are linked with mixed-method research design.

It can also be concluded that the application of both primary and secondary data collection methods was also suitable for this study to reach the main objectives of the inquiry. It helps gather both qualitative and numerical data, which is beneficial to present effective research outcomes. Using thematic framework analysis and SPSS software to apply various statistical techniques analysis methods is also beneficial for this study because these allowed the researcher to analyse the data effectively. Lastly, the researcher also followed all the ethical considerations to complete this study ethically.

CHAPTER V

QUALITATIVE FINDINGS

5.1. INTRODUCTION

Qualitative analysis suggests an unstructured investigation approach and allows interviewees to present their interpretations, allowing new knowledge and insight to be added to the existing literature body (Aaker et al., 2001). The analysis of in-depth interviews and focus group discussion to HRM and marketing experts to the following research objectives is presented in this chapter.

The purpose of this qualitative study was to advance the current understanding and gathering more in-depth knowledge of employer branding and its influences on the employer of choice, employee performance, and organisation performance. This chapter presents these findings based on a program of in-depth interviews focus group with middle and top managers in service sector firms (Banks, Insurance companies, Universities, Hospitals, Transports, and Hotels) in Pakistan. Details related to choosing the individual for an interview and the forms of questions asked during the interview process. Chapter IV consisted of the planning, management, and findings of the qualitative phase. Interpretations of interviews and focus groups were part of section 5.2, whereas Section 5.3 consisted of a conceptual model, which was refined after qualitative data analysis.

5.2. FINDING OF THE QUALITATIVE STUDY

Instead of analyzing surface characteristics, the primary purpose of qualitative analysis is to explore a more profound understanding. This segment introduces the observations and the evidence supporting the development of themes for current research into the dimension of

employer branding and its consequences for the employer of choice, employee performance, and organisation performance.

The content analysis done for this study identified four dimensions of employer branding and four elements that impact the relationship to an employer of choice, employee performance, and organisation performance. These dimensions were identified in this study. The researchers and academic scholars acknowledged organisation culture as a dimension of employer branding (Barrow and Mosley, 2005; Robbins, 2001; Rampl L., 2014; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a). The literature recognizes development and Growth opportunities (Berthon et al., 2005; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016i; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016ii; Wilden et al., 2010), Salary and incentives (Rampl, 2014; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019), and Work-life balance (Barrow and Mosley, 2005; Hillebrandt and Ivens 2013; Hudson, 2005; Rampl, 2014; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016b; 2005; Zhen Wang et al., 2014).

Moreover, As highlighted in the literature, all respondents emphasized the value of employer branding. Consistent with the literature, interviewees stressed the importance of employer branding, noted that it influences employee perceptions of the organisation, and uncovered its main influences in attracting and retaining talent in today's competitive market, focusing on employee commitment, satisfaction, retention, and performance.

5.2.1. Employer branding

There are several dimensions of employer branding that determine employee understanding of the employer. While the spectrum of this survey is small, the interview and focus groups adhere to

these dimensions identified from relevant literature. This research follows the previous dimensions generated by previous results.

The analysis of qualitative study pointed out that employer branding is a key predictor of employee retention and performance, which ultimately contribute to an employer of choice and organisation performance, which is wedded to employee decisions when choosing where to serve. In addition, the text-based study of the individuals interviewed shows an emphasis on what the business stands for, connectivity, and distinguishing features of the employer brand. The following statements reflect the review by the manager of this analysis:

According to the respondent of a focus group consisting of university employees:

“According to me, employer branding is a set of processes adopted by the employer to establish its differentiated recognition than his competitors. In order to differentiate and encourage employees, an organisation offers various benefits to employees like lucrative incentives, ideal working environment, career growth and advancement opportunities, and family support benefits. In this way, an organisation not only attracts talent but also triggers employees' satisfaction, commitment, and performance”. (BG)

“Employer branding is a package of monetary and non-monitory benefits offered by the employer to employees. These benefits are different according to different sectors of the economy (manufacturing and services)”. (BJ)

A private bank branch manager had the opinion:

“A process of offering unique benefits and support to employees by the employer. Support may include mental and physical well-being, conducive working environment and competitive salary”.

(HU)

The above quotations are consistent with employer branding authors Ambler and Barrow, who first introduced employer branding and highlighted its importance. Ambler and Barrow (1996) define employer branding as “the package of functional, economic and psychological benefits provided by employment, and identified with the employing company.” Later on, many authors (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004; Biswas and Suar, 2016; Carlini et al., 2019; Dabirian, Kietzmann and Diba, 2017; Rampl et al., 2016; Rampl, 2014; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016b; Tanwar and Prasad, 2017) supported this definition. They believed that employer branding is a package of functional, economic, and psychological benefits. Likewise, analysis of this qualitative study also underlined that EB is a package of various benefits. However, different managers stressed different benefits and added that these benefits also vary according to different industries (Public and private).

Moreover, an employee of the insurance firm stated:

“Employer branding is series of efforts of the employer to create a positive image of organisation in the eyes of employees and the eyes of society for making an organisation an excellent place to join or serve. The general public has different images regarding public and private organisations where the public organisation offers job security but low salary and incentives whereas private organisations offer high salary, but job security is only for those who are best performers”. (AS)

The findings are consistent with the research (Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019; Arijs et al., 2018; Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004; Dabirian, Kietzmann, and Diba, 2017; DeMotta and Sen, 2017; Mölk, 2018; Rampl et al., 2016; Urbancova et al., 2017; Weske et al., 2019). A central theme of the employer branding emerging among employees is the positive image of the employer. Therefore, the first step in launching EB is communicating the organisation's positive image to targeted employees in the labor market. According to researchers (Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019; Arijs et al., 2018; Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004; Dabirian, Kietzmann, and Diba, 2017; DeMotta and Sen, 2017; Mölk, 2018; Rampl et al., 2016; Urbancova et al., 2017; Weske et al., 2019), the employer branding has been seen as a way to express and communicate the value of the organisation in order to create a unique and positive image of the organisation in the minds of employees.

The Dean of business school of a private university had the idea:

“I think employer branding is a strategy of the employer to match organisation with the need and want of talented employees. It means the organisation is the same as what a talented employee wants it to be. A good organisation does much research to understand why any employee prefers a particular organisation. After this understanding, the organisation offers a set of benefits to attract talented employees. This process is employer branding.”. (BS)

Participants referred to employer branding as the organisation's efforts to continuously improve employee's experience at works and offer what employees want and keep an eye on changes in labor market conditions. Time and again, current employees match the rewards offered to him/her with the rewards offered by other organisations in the market. Based on this analysis they decide either they will remain with the same organisation or quit and join the other one. in addition,

employee not only compare rewards but many other factors which include learning and growth opportunities, the status of the organisation, behaviour of the superiors and nature of the job.

The branch manager of a private bank explained:

“To me, my organisation is best to work with because this organisation takes good care of employees, this organisation thinks and assesses the current needs of employees, for example, due to advancement of technology this organisation arranges training for employees. Let me add HR department especially advice managers to look after their teams and adopt kind behaviour and supporting attitudes. If I talk about financial and non-financial benefits, this organisation monitors market salary trends and give employees many bonuses and increments and these increments depends on individual performance and market trends”. (TM)

An employer needs the active involvement of top-level management to be considered up-to-date in the market, and their keen interest in the organisation is of utmost importance. In addition, there is a general awareness that the employer brand is part of interaction and employees' perceptions of organisational culture, which tend to be stronger when they are more reliable. Some respondents indicated, for example, that reliability is linked to the employer branding.

According to Agri finance manager of a private bank:

“My organisation continuously makes changes in rewards and bonuses and considers individual economic, social and emotional/Psychological needs.” (AG)

Another Assistant Vice President of a private bank added:

“My organisation is up-to-date. It is raking and reputation in this market, I am obliged and feel the pride to work here, and we are market leaders, and I happily tell others that I am part of this organisation.” (AA)

It is noted here that working in a particular organisation is a matter of pride for employees. As regional manager of a courier firm believed:

“My organisation is best of all because I am valued here, my changing needs are catered, my organisation offers pregnancy leave, gifts to my newborn baby gave me extra time offs to take care of my family, medical support to my old parents.” (MA)

In contrast on an employee of a public university shared

“working environment is good here, but the salary is not good. Even annual increment is simply nothing. Look at the condition of inflation and package of the university where we are Grade 18 officers (One of the highly ranked officers), almost living hand to mouth. University must do something to keep us with this university.” (FS)

5.2.2 Dimensions of employer branding

This segment exhibits the dimensions of EB in light of the findings of qualitative analysis.

5.2.2.1 Organisation Culture

The organisational culture is critical for retaining loyal employees and establishing a competitive advantage (Gilani and Cunningham 2017). Therefore, many scholars emphasise the importance of organisational culture for maintaining a competitive position in the market (Tanwar and Kumar, 2019), as discussed above in Chapter II. Various studies established organisation culture, a

dimension of employer branding investigated from various approaches (Dabirian et al., 2017; Gilani and Cunningham, 2017; Rampl, 2014).

Moreover, Organisational culture is a system of shared values held by organisational members that differentiate one organisation from another (Robbins, 2001). EB can be enhanced by promoting and highlighting the salient perspectives of the immediate organisational culture (Barrow and Mosley, 2005; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a). Every organisation has a unique work culture that acted as an employee value proposition that differentiates it from competitors. Organisation culture is gradually emerging as a vital dimension of EB.

An employee of a telecom firm believed:

“Compensation is not the only thing an employee works for. The atmosphere in which they work is just as critical.” (TS)

When an employee joins an organisation, he/she looks for the norms and values of the organisation, rules, and regulations of the organisation. The overall environment matters a lot in which employees get opportunities to work. When asked about what they like most about the organisation culture, a manager answered:

“I feel fantastic to work in this organisation. I have many friends here. We work together in a team and share joint responsibility and celebrate the excellent outcome of our work”. (HU)

The bank branch manager shared:

“We live here like a family, help each other, and there is no boss among us. Boss is not here to find our faults but here to support us”. (RTS)

One female bank manager mentioned:

“My organisation provides me with a safe working environment. I usually work night shifts. Commuting back home is not a problem as the organisation provides a pick and drop cab facility. Moreover, my team lead is very understanding and helpful”. (TF)

As can be noticed from the responses, helpful and polite colleagues, a healthy organisation environment, and supervisors' actions are important variables that influence employee decisions about an employer.

Additional registrar of a public university came up with the following points:

“You want to be made to feel welcome and secure in your job. A sense of community or being present for each other is important. I hope for a culture where there are people who include your boss and colloquies, happy to foster you, happy to help you grow, train you, monitor you, and leave you alone to your own devices. In the organisation, there is somebody who would help you. Finally, job security and observance of defined rules and regulations are elements of culture which differentiate organisation from other and help organisation to create attraction of new talent and motivate exiting employees to remain part of the organisation”. (AJ)

5.2.2.2 Development and Growth Opportunities

This aspect has emphasized the importance of development and growth opportunities inside the organisation. This dimension of employer branding extends the “development value” aspect introduced by Berthon et al. (2005). During the evaluation of an organisation, potential employees are more attached to development and growth opportunities (Tanwar and Prasad, 2017). The

current study's findings show that development and growth opportunities as a dimension of the employer branding highlight an organisation unique and competitive characteristics (Arijs et al., 2018; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a). Participants made numerous comments on the offering of development and growth opportunities in the organisation to enhance organisation attraction for employees (Dabirian et al., 2017; Gilani and Cunningham, 2017; Kumari and Saini, 2018).

“In my organisation, every employee has equal opportunities for career advancement and career-building.” (SA)

Another bank manager added:

“I believe that employer branding attracts employees and gives them a clear opportunity to build a career in an organisation and grow with the organisation as they spend more time in the organisation and take the next step in their career. There must be sufficient and equal opportunities to sustain and grow. I mean job promotion. Individual skill development plans should be clear and communicated and must be based on individual competencies building”. (TS)

An employee of an insurance firm believed:

“In my organisation, there is a policy of employee rotation. This offers me the opportunity to grow and develop my skills”. (HA)

A university employee came up with opinion:

“In this university, no opportunity to grow. No career planning. The management is not thinking about employees. They only think about their benefits.”

More practical issues were addressed by the focus group members (representing employees), to which the previous researchers paid significantly less attention. For example, one member of the focus group had the comments:

“An organisation to be more attractive in the market must have a defined promotion policy and career path for certain jobs. Offering an interesting assignment to employee provide employees an opportunity to exert more efforts and desire to enhance skills. Employee development programs enhance employee retention.” (HA)

5.2.2.3 Work-life Balance

Now, organisations have started including strategies of WLB in the employer branding strategy. EB literature recommends that strategies of WLB can assist the organisations for improving the EB that in return leads to enhance the retentions of employees (Barrow and Mosley, 2005; Hudson, 2005; Kumari and Saini, 2018). As recommended by Barrow and Mosley (2005), it is tough for an organisation to introduce EB without including the components of WLB. The study of Hillenbrand and Ivens (2013) and Tanwar and Prasad (2017) has mentioned the significance of WLB for having strong EB.

The employees consider Work-Life Balance activities in the organisation to be an essential tool of employer branding. For example, according to the Manager in telecom firm:

“I work for long hours on weekdays, but on weekends I can spend quality time with my kids and wife. In that way, balance is maintained between my work and family life”. (AAS)

Similarly, the marketing manager of an insurance firm shared:

“I feel energized at work. The important thing is flexibility, and freedom means flexible work hours, and I can work from home as well when I need to stay at home due to family obligations. Moreover, I got an immediate release from the workplace when there is a family emergency”. (AJ)

A dean of private university added:

“In my organisation, I can fully take care of my family, my personal life is not compromised at all, In addition, I was given paternal leave, and every employee has the same facilities to avail.” (HU)

A university employee informed:

“Although this is unique, my organisation has a gym at the workplace. I like this aspect of my organisation and this added advantage to join and serve my organisation” (HA)

However, a bank branch manager shared:

“if you want a bank job, you will have to forget about family. Benefits are good and attractive but long working hours! Oh my God.” (HG)

To understand how workers' view WLB, they have developed a propensity to reflect on personal life and job. The majority of the respondents said that it was balanced as far as their work and personal life were concerned. When questioned about flexible employment, most workers appeared happy as they agreed to switch their shifts with peers if they offered a reasonable excuse. There are also allowed to work at home, where workers can sit and continue to work. Furthermore, The respondents said they could spend plenty of time at home with their family when needed on special occasions. Only at such important meetings at the workplace do they remain unable to meet family requirements, but they are rear in the organisation. Employees can also use a holiday

to popular tourist sites. From the interviews, the workers could remember numerous measures conducted by the organisation to handle the WLB.

5.2.2.4. Salary and incentive

Tanwar and Kumar (2019) emphasize the value of the salary and incentive stressed through the employer branding that managers strongly support. Rewards are critical because organisations have a unique competitive business perception in offering attractive and competitive financial and non-financial rewards, increasing the likelihood of attracting a talented workforce (Arijs et al., 2018; Dabirian et al., 2017; Gilani and Cunningham, 2017). As mentioned by a public university employee during focus,

"Employer branding is the planning of how an organisation can reward an employee differently, comparatively, and attractively for his services at work". The organisation can become appealing to employees who offer attractive salaries and perks. I do not think of reward solely in monetary terms; it also includes various other benefits. Although an employee wants recognition and a challenging job, he counts organisations' response to his efforts through the amount of money he receives at the end of the day. Moreover, every extraordinary effort of an employee at work should be rewarded with a handsome amount, for example, overtime pay, bonus, and annual increment. Medical coverage for self and family, as well as post-retirement benefits, can help a company stand out as one of the market's most unique and best employers." (FC-1)

Another employee added;

“In my opinion, salary and incentives are the main sources of attraction of organisation. If an organisation offers an ideal working environment and many other lavish elements but did not offer a good salary, no one will even think to join it. So, attractive overall compensation is key to employer branding”. (HAJ)

The Agri finance manager of a private bank thought;

“Employer with higher overall compensation has more employees as compare to competitors stands with it.” (AJ)

In particular, Asian culture employees want something extra along with salary, as one of the interviewees from insurance firm claimed;

“We rate employer not only based on salary and other incentive but particularly benefits after retirement, Government jobs are more attractive because it has defined after retirement benefits policy which include gratuity and pension.” (AB)

University employee thought:

“After retirement benefits, is another source of attraction for an organisation.” (HA)

One employee of insurance included family benefits as another source of attraction for organisation, added:

“For me, family benefits like children school fees, pick and drop facility and their medical and financial help at the time of their wedding should be included in overall reward from the organisation.” (SA)

Employees in one focus group from private bank stressed more on retirement benefits as a significant part of overall incentives:

“that organisation is distinctive and attractive in the labor market, which offers good retirement benefits, although this organisation does not currently offer that like many others in the private sector. However, this is a major attraction in government organisations as they offer a gratuity, pension, and other retirement benefits. Due to current economic conditions and high-level inflation in the country, we are almost living hand to mouth and unable to make our own homes, but we think at retirement organisation should give us handsome amount so that we can build/ buy our own home.” (SB)

5.2.2.5 Equality and Justice

A manager needs to be fair and unbiased with all employees in an organisation setting when distributing resources, jobs, and rewards. Organisational justice encourages employees to have a positive attitude and behaviour at work and work harder to achieve the organisation's goals. Broadly, organisational justice is defined as the extent to which members of an organisation are treated fairly. Moreover, justice should prevail in resource allocation and routine procedures, and an organisation should treat employees with respect and dignity (Colquitt et al., 2001; Greenberg, 1990; Thibaut and Walker, 1975). Equality means there should not be any discrimination among employees in an organisation.

According to various studies (Iqbal, 2013; Thomas and Nagalingappa, 2012; Usmani and Jamal, 2013), employees treated relatively at work are more likely to exhibit positive work behaviours like job satisfaction and commitment retention. Similarly, it was reported that justice is vital in an organisation because its lack leads to dissatisfied employees who put in less effort, low morale,

increased absenteeism, and eventually leaving the company. Moreover, high turnover is caused by a lack of perceived organisational fairness.

Public university employee mentioned:

"Employer branding is a tool to keep existing employees with the organisation and make them function and encourage them to do their best at work with complete devotion and dedication. Employer branding is effective if employees are treated politely without discrimination. We are straightforward people. If someone talks with love and respect, we are ready to offer our lives too. Moreover, justice plays a key role here. Working hours and shifts are allocated with fairness and without nepotism. Everyone is ready to work hard and likes to work with an organisation. Like extra hours distribution, in my department, every employee wants extra hours (each extra hour beyond normal workload, is paid), and we distribute them equally, so satisfaction and performance in our department are very high ".(FC-3)

Likewise, a bank manager

"I think my organisation is the best and unique in the industry as there are equal opportunities available for everyone here. If you work well, you will be rewarded accordingly. In my opinion, an organisation can attract and retain talent by its honesty, and justice means fair treatment of all employees. There should not be discrimination based on gender, age, and race".

One more interviewee from a telecom firm added:

"I am happy with the choice of this organisation as I am pleased here. The main reason is the behaviour of colleagues and boss, according to the norm of an organisation to treat everyone with

a smile, not only customers but employees too. Even if he is a person or security guard or office boy/tea boy, every employee will be treated equally and have the same respect as a manager".

On the other hand, one insurance firm employee said:

"If there is no equality and fairness, no satisfaction, no performance, no motivation, no attachment to the organisation, this creates a negative image of the organisation, and nobody wants to work in such a system, and those who are in will seek other opportunities in the market."

Similarly, one employee in the same focus group believed:

"Fair treatment at the workplace helps us to remain motivated. This organisation is not good because of discrimination. Our female colleagues are favourites of my boss, and her schedule is more flexible than mine".

Another in the focus group university employee added:

"I am dissatisfied with this organisation because those who engage in flattery and stay busy buttering managers receive good bonuses and pay raises each year."However, people like me who only focus on their work and do not visit their boss's office unnecessarily are deprived of many benefits and resources".

One employee in another focus group had similar views:

"My immediate boss simply dislikes me because I belong to the SHIA sect (or another sect/religious/ethnic group)."Whenever I need a day off to perform religious obligations, he does not allow it. Even, I bring this to the notice of higher management. They simply say follow your

boss either he is right or wrong as its organisation policy. Where are employees' rights? What is the rubbish policy of this organisation? I shall soon quit this organisation. "

Hence, equality and justice have emerged as one of the new dimensions of employer branding. Organisations with fair practices and justice have a positive image in the market, and employees love to join and work with such an employer. Treating employees without discrimination enhances their motivation and commitment. When employees are treated with respect, they are more likely to perform well and remain with the organisation for a more extended period. In contrast, if there is nepotism and discrimination in an organisation, the organisation will not maintain its talented employees.

5.2.3 Consequences of the employer branding

The evidence revealed from past literature that employer branding might lead to many consequences (Bhasin et al., 2019; Weske et al., 2019; Yadav et al., 2020). Employer branding has yielded positive outcomes such as employee retention, employee performance, commitment, and satisfaction. As stated in earlier sections, the main target of employer branding includes employee attraction and retention and positively affects employee commitment, satisfaction and improves employee performance and organisation performance (Matongolo et al., 2018; Maxwell and Knox, 2009; Tumasjan et al., 2020). There was a considerable debate on employer branding about recruiting and found the preliminary discussion about other important aspects of employee work-life. This segment describes the findings of qualitative analysis on employer branding results.

5.2.3.1. Consequences of the employer branding: Person organisation fit

The person-organisation fit may be defined as a match between an employee's views, values, and culture and the employer's image on the one hand (Lauver and Kristof-Brown, 2001, Tanwar and Kumar, 2019). The person-organisation fit viewpoint has been widely utilized in conjunction with employer brand research to describe the amount of congruence between employers and workers (Christiaans, 2013, Tanwar and Kumar, 2019). According to previous research on the person-organisation fit, potential workers evaluate an employer brand to their own beliefs, needs, and ideas, and a connection between the two generates more robust attractiveness to the organisation for the individual (Schneider, 1987). According to Backhaus and Tikoo (2004), potential workers evaluate the employer brand's image and relate it to their own beliefs and characteristics.

The regional manager of a leading Pakistan telecom firm was of the view:

"In my opinion, when an organisation attempts to match its culture, salaries and other non-monetary incentives to individuals, it generates people organisation fit." (AAS)

Director of Business School of a leading Pakistani university added that:

"Organisational culture is somewhat changed as new employees are added, indicating that culture is adaptive with some core values. I believe the main purpose of employer branding is to attract those people from the market whose values are somewhat similar to those of the organisation."(GAB)

Likewise, a university employee in the focus group thought:

"If we consider an organisation a person having a unique lifestyle, the organisation always needs to search for some other person with almost all characteristics to live. Why is he attracting the

one whose mindset will not match him? I mean to say employer branding helps organisations to attract and retain employees who share common norms and values with the organisation". (SK)

On the other hand, one employee in the same focus group said:

"My boss (Dean) does not care what I think and feel, what my values, what I like and dislike. Although I am not a good fit for this university (Public sector university), I am still working here. I can still work for this organisation if my boss starts thinking for me and tries to match the company's culture with my lifestyle. Very easy if they want. For example, I need flexible working hours, medical coverage for my family, and I want my boss to praise me when I go above and beyond. If an organisation does all of the above (what we call employer branding), I will start thinking that I was made for this organisation and me and my employer think, feel and do in the same fashion (what we call person-organisation fit)." (MK)

5.2.3.2. Consequences of the employer branding: organisation commitment

Employee commitment to the company is essential to enhance job performance and retention of a productive workforce. "The organisational commitment is a psychological condition that binds the person to the organisation," as described by Allen and Meyer (1990). Past literature identified that organisation commitment is one of the major consequences of employer branding (Bhasin et al., 2019; Ito et al., 2013; Yadav et al., 2020). It is essential for management to know the reasons that improve employee commitment and to produce efficient employees. When questioned what determines employee commitment, the pay system and prospects for development emerged as two of the critical drivers of organisational commitment. Most managers said that financial reward influenced their decision to remain with the organisation and, if paid, will be high compared to

other organisations in the market. They would go the extra mile to increase their own as well as organisation performance.

As one Assistant Vice President of a highly reputed bank stated:

“Money matters. Especially when you are working for a prestigious organisation (Bank), your expectations are high. The cost of living has increased over the years. It is not easy to afford the best things in life. So, in order to stay in one organisation for a longer span, a good compensation package becomes a necessity. However, considering how one can leave the organisation that takes care otherwise and its simple one will care you, and you will not want to leave him”. (AA)

The regional manager of a telecom firm answered:

“I intend to stay here for the coming years. Having been voted as one of the best companies to work for, we are getting the relevant exposure. We even get to meet experts from our field. It is quite encouraging. I am glad I chose this firm to work for over other available options. My organisation always remains competitive as the research and development department is powerful here, so this department provides up-to-date information to decision-makers in the HRM department who devise employee benefits. Therefore, our salaries and other incentive are excellent as compare to other organisations in the market”. (AAS)

Moreover, when questioned about their loyalty to employers, many employees seemed satisfied with their job except a few and would unlikely leave current employers soon.

Agri finance manager of a Pakistani bank was of the option:

“I never thought about leaving this organisation because I am getting a lot of monetary and physiological benefits, I have been taking handsome salary with superb career growth opportunities” (AG)

One employee of an insurance firm of the view:

“Even I suggest my friends join this organisation because this is a great place to work, the organisation takes it into consideration that you have a personal life as well, and the top management has taken many initiatives to facilitate employee to take care of their families like paid leaves and paternity leaves” (AN).

If an employee is satisfied with his job and does not want to move to another organisation, his loyalty to the organisation is vital. Organisation commitment can be achieved by presenting the employee with an appealing pay package and better career advancement opportunities. It may also be argued that employer branding tends to build a committed workforce.

5.2.3.3 Consequences of the employer branding: employee retention

Employee retention is the efforts and determination by the organisation to keep desirable employees who contribute towards the success of the organisation (Christopher et al., 2019; Govaerts et al., 2011; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016). Qualitative analysis also confirms this definition as employees defined employee retention as a mindset and intention to see him in the same organisation for many years to come.

A bank employee thought:

“Employee retention is everything due to which staff members wish to stay with that employer and contribute to the organisation's uplift.” (FS)

Another employee in insurance firm believed:

“Keeping an employee for a longer period because the organisation has invested in them for training and have given them training and development and now the employees are with the desired capabilities and desired traits to achieve organisational goals” (TS)

Most people were pleased with their jobs, and the replies favoured their decision to stick with their respective organisations. However, a few employees were thinking of changing their employers. There were very few workers who feel like moving in the near future to other organisations. As one manager replied:

A Regional Manager in a telecom firm claimed:

“Five years down the lane, I see myself progressing in the same company. Even my colleagues do not have such intention”. (AAS)

Additional Registrar of the university explained:

“The committed employees do not leave the organisation even if they get better options so they will be retained, the case is with I never thought about leaving my firm, and I am quite satisfied in this university.” (AJ)

Hence it can be seen from responses that retention is one of the Consequences of EB, as an employee of insurance firms explained:

“Flexible work hours and immense growth opportunities are the two factors that motivate me at work. I see myself working permanently within this firm. I have a strong belief that after five years, I will not be working on the same rank.”. (HK)

Employer branding helps attain high retention levels among employees (Lum et al., 1998; Mitchell et al., 2001; Schields and Price, 2002). Various studies advocated that job satisfaction is one predictor of employee retention (Matongolo et al., 2018; Tanwar and Prasad, 2017; Westlund and Hannon, 2008).

A public university employee was of the views:

“There are obvious reasons when I am here and will be found here in future. Employees who feel that university has met their expectations regarding salary, working conditions, benefits, and the overall environment will like to stay there”. (MA)

“When the employer and employee promises are fulfilled, and fair labour practices are followed, the employees are satisfied and want to stay in these organisations.” (TM)

The female branch manager of a bank shared:

“As per my knowledge and experience, I can say that employees never leave the organisation if organisation look after her. Moreover, it is in the organisation's hand to keep an employee. During my career, I saw people start a job in an organisation, and after more than ten years, they are still there. Of course, there are certain reasons for employee retention. Firstly, incentives and, most importantly and market-based and equal incentives. Secondly, progressive environment where an employee fell she is continuously learning and improving herself. Lastly, organisation support,

like whenever an employee has any problem, she thinks my organisation is standing with me”.
(TF)

5.2.3.4 Consequences of the employer branding: job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is the employees' attitude and feeling towards their job and another job mechanism. Past literature highlights that if an organisation has a strong employer brand, its employees' satisfaction remains high (Bangwal and Tiwari, 2019; Slavković et al., 2018; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016). It is important to understand the needs and wants of employees and offer them with is being expected. At the same time, continuous monitoring and revision of resources and benefit is the key to check either employee is happy with what was offered to them. The qualitative analysis revealed that job satisfaction is one of the key outcomes of employer branding.

The human Resource manager of a hotel replied:

“Job satisfaction is all positive feelings of employees. Good image of employer generates positive emotions, and these positive emotions are job satisfaction” (SB)

Likewise, the Additional registrar of a public university highlighted:

“For me, job satisfaction is motivation and love of any employee for the job in a particular organisation. This love is generated when he is receiving from organisation what he requires”.

(AJ)

A review of the existing literature shows that very few researchers have examined the influence of employer branding on job satisfaction (Lelono and Martdianty, 2013; Schlager et al., 2011; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016). However, qualitative analysis pinpoints that job satisfaction is an essential

element. Managers declared job satisfaction as the primary outcome of EB, even though they stressed that job satisfaction is one of the organisation's main goals to increase employee and organisation performance.

An employee of a public university was of the views:

“Employer branding develops the perception of the company's financial and non-financial. When employees perceive that their company is good in terms of these benefits, they will evaluate it positively and be more satisfied. Currently, my organisation is not offering the right salary and incentives, but the environment is supportive here. I am satisfied with the support I receive in case of any emergency. Moreover, my department's equal treatment regarding workload (Tasks/ Teaching hours) distribution makes me satisfied. I want to add that my job is somewhat flexible too like if I need to leave university due to a family emergency, someone else takes my class, and I am allowed to leave.” (SA)

Moreover, the current study demonstrates that job satisfaction is collecting positive feelings of an employee from various aspects of the job and organisation.

Two bank employees of a focus group seemed unsatisfied with their bank, saying;

“I think, Satisfaction does not come from a single variable but incentives, working environment, and friendly peers and supervisor.” (MA)

“To obtain job satisfaction lot of efforts needed like competitive salary, and support to employee to manage his personal life. Which is currently missing in this bank” (RTS)

The justification of satisfaction with the work was identified as the predicted outcome of employer branding, as it has a strong association with the dimensions of employer branding. When the organisation understands the needs of current employees and is concerned about their satisfaction, It stayed in the market with a high level of employee job satisfaction (Bangwal and Tiwari, 2019; Gaddam, 2008; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016). This satisfaction may reflect in employee behaviour at work.

5.2.3.5. Consequences of the employer branding: employee performance

Employee performance is the outcome of the efforts of employees at the workplace in manufacturing firms. Identifying a worker with the units of products he produced is easy. However, in a service sector firm, it is comparatively difficult to measure performance. Sometimes we measure employee performance in service firms as the devotion and dedication to service delivery or no of customer served by an employee. On the other hand, level of customer satisfaction might also be considered as employee performance. Past literature claimed that employer branding influences employee performance mainly through mediators like job satisfaction, commitment, and retention (Bhasin et al., 2019; Bodderas et al., 2011; Buttenberg, 2013). However, qualitative data analysis revealed that employer branding directly influences employee performance.

A Regional manager of a telecom firm claimed:

“what we expect from employees? Obviously, Superior customer service. I think an employee is also a machine. If you provide with required electricity and lubrication, it will work as desired and expected. I called electricity and lubrication a set of distinctive benefits that you literary people called employer branding. U fone (telecom firm) is now among the top brands and reason

for this is the level of services we are providing to customers. My employee is providing services and what we realize my employees' needs. Let me count them. Competitive salary, excellent work environment, family support, job security, concern for personal life and professional growth, and career management. We provide them, and they perform well.” (AAS)

Likewise, the Agri finance manager of a bank explained:

“Be different and buy differently. I mean, we are different on market-based salary, and my team is differentiated on performance. It is Pakistan! Give more money to an employee and look, he immediately increases performance. one day, I announce extra commission, and the next day my field agent comes with recovery.” (AG)

Similarly, the Director of the business school in a public university thought:

“Employer branding all about becomes a unique employer in the market with excellent benefits and support. Like an employer branding element, work-life balance matters when offered handsome salaries and incentives and, most importantly, fairness. This is employer branding, and it has a direct trigger for employee performance. Employer branding is sufficiently enough to induce employee efforts and delivery (Performance)” (GAB)

The marketing manager of an insurance firm was of the view:

“Employer branding has only one objective, which is employee performance. I think if there is no performance, no employer branding. I support the direct link of employer branding with employee performance.” (GA)

A university employee said in the same way:

“It is simply. Employee performance is directly influenced by employer branding.” (HA)

Based on qualitative data analysis, it can be concluded that employer branding is directly linked with employee performance. Thus, the conceptual model was amended. Moreover, like previous studies, it is also seen in qualitative data analysis that employer branding influences employee performance through various job-related outcomes: job satisfaction, organisation commitment, and employee retention.

Member in a focus group consisted upon employees of insurance firms were thought:

“When we are happy with the organisation, we perform excellently.” (FA)

“employer branding generates satisfaction, and satisfaction leads to best performance.” (ZA)

“Employee satisfaction and commitment certainly leads to superior motivation to perform duties.”

(TQ)

“Employee job Satisfaction certainly can be seen through the number and level of our sales calls (regarded as performance).” (AA)

5.2.3.6. Consequences of the employer branding: employer of choice

An EOC can be an organisation for which a potential employee desires to join and remain with some unique benefits. Employer branding helps position a company as an employer of choice with communication to and from an actual and potential employee. It becomes easy when employees become advocates of the employer. An employee speaks positively about his employer when he is offered the right package of benefits in return for his services. Previous research (e.g., Branham, 2001; Elving et al., 2013; Rampl, 2014; Saini and Jawahar, 2019; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019) suggested that an employer can earn the reputation of employer of choice by providing the right

combination of economic, functional, and psychological, benefits to current and potential employees. To earn the employer of choice status from job candidates, firms use supportive organisation culture, compensation, and work-life balance.

The regional manager of private courier firm was of the views:

“I am very much committed with my firm, and surely this was my first choice and will remain. Because this firm deserves to be. Our HRM department is very good. Policies are employee-focused.”

The assistant vice president of a leading private bank believed:

“I am happy to be a part of this organisation and would love to see many other inspiring people be a part of the family. I always share positive reviews about my organisation with my family and friends. Trust me. It is not an exaggeration. This place is awesome! It is not easy to find such a place to work. I cannot see myself working for some other organisation. Supportive team, host of learning opportunities, and an attractive salary package: What else can one demand? If this is what a brand advocate is called, then Yes! I am one amongst them and would surely recommend this place to other people”. (BJ)

A public university employee shared:

“This university is no more remained my first-choice employer as it is not offering what an employee wants, such as competitive salary, progressive environment, and fairness in the allocation of tasks and responsibilities.” (AA)

5.2.3.7 Consequences of the employer branding: organisation performance

Employer branding helps an organisation in many ways with the ultimate goal of organisation performance. An organisation's survival and growth determine an organisation's life, whereas organisation performance is an indicator of survival and growth. Previous studies have identified that employer branding helps an organisation achieve its organisation performance goal (Biswas and Sour, 2016; Tumasjan et al., 2020). Its explored in qualitative data analysis that employer branding boost employer performance which in turn enhance organisation performance.

Dean of business school of public university believed:

“In service firms, actually organisation is offering services and employees are involved total in providing services to a customer. For example, in a university, a teacher teaches students, and students are considered customers. If we say organisation performance is customer satisfaction and seen in the number of new student number. It is possible because of services provided by employees the teachers. Hence organisation performance may be measured through the sum of all employees' performance.” (BS)

In addition, based on the analysis, employer branding influences organisation performance through job satisfaction.

Moreover, the Branch manager of a bank claimed:

“Employee job satisfaction is an important element for any organisation. Satisfaction means we are happy here, we are being looked after by organisation, we are being concerned by the organisation. When an organisation considers its success (organisation performance)only can be obtained by employee job satisfaction, I support this assumption that it means the organisation is

right. Think One of the many positive outcomes of job satisfaction is organisation performance. In banks, one of the important performance indicators is an increase in employee job satisfaction.”

(HJ)

In addition, the regional manager of a telecom firm thought:

“When setting targets for organisation performance telecom firm specifically mention an increase in satisfaction level of employees is performance. It is our goal, and we will strive for it. ”(AAS)

The regional manager of a private courier firm shared similar thoughts:

“Our employees are not a separate entity. We consider they are our part. You can say part of our body. If employees remain comfortable and happy (satisfaction), our firm is in the right direction, and we have achieved our goal (Organisation performance).”(MA)

Organisation performance is one of the consequences of employer branding. Based on the above analysis, employer branding influences job satisfaction, and job satisfaction influences organisation performance. Thus, the conceptual model of this study was amended by adding new links explore through a qualitative study.

5.3 CONCEPTUAL MODEL AFTER QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

After a qualitative study, it was found that corporate social responsibility is not considered an organisation feature to differentiate it from competitive as perceived employees in service firms. Moreover, organisations do not invest in CSR to attract employees and obtain employee job-related outcomes. Hence, CSR does not include in the package of benefits that constitutes employer branding. Therefore, CSR was excluded from the conceptual model as a dimension of employer branding, and new dimensions (Development and growth opportunities, Equality, and justice) were included while research went for quantitative analysis.

Figure 5.1: Conceptual Model refined after qualitative analysis

Source: Researcher

Table 5.1: Research Hypotheses after qualitative analysis

Hypotheses	
H1	Employer branding has a positive influence on person organisation fit.
H2	Employer branding has a positive influence on organisation commitment.
H3	Employer branding has a positive influence on employee retention.
H4	Employer branding has a positive influence on job satisfaction.
H5	Person organisation fit has a positive influence on the employer of choice.
H6	Organisation commitment has a positive influence on Employer brand advocacy.
H7	Organisation commitment has a positive influence on employee performance.

H8	Job satisfaction has a positive influence on employee performance.
H9	Employee retention has a positive influence on employee performance.
H10	Employer brand advocacy has a positive influence on the employer of choice.
H11	Employee performance has a positive influence on organisation performance.
H12	Employer branding has a positive influence on employee performance.
H13	Job satisfaction has a positive influence on organisation performance.

Source: Researcher

5.4 SUMMARY

The qualitative analysis was done by explaining the compilation of data and the outcomes of interviews and the focus group. The chapter dealt with the qualitative study to achieve the research objectives (to establish a thorough understanding of employer branding and its effects on the employer of choice and organisation performance) and answer the research questions. Next, interviews and focus group data analysis and conclusions were explained. The findings were based on the key concepts described in the relevant literature. The conceptual framework of the dimensions and consequences of the employer branding was built based on the existing literature and analysis of interviews and focus group data.

The first qualitative study, which was exploratory, produced rich data about the phenomena being researched to establish the second quantitative study. In this analysis, the key result was found to support the research questions of the current study (RQ1: What are the key elements of robust employer branding in service firms according to the perception of current employees? RQ2: Does employer branding influence the employer of choice and organisation performance?). The literature review contributed to creating a conceptual framework and provided support to the

development of hypotheses. Consequently, the framework for quantitative study is the output of the literature, which is supported by qualitative analysis.

CHAPTER VI

QUANTITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS

6.1. INTRODUCTION

To accomplish the study goals, this chapter analyses and elucidates the relationships between independent and dependent variables. This chapter discusses the empirical analysis of the developed research hypotheses of the study. Moreover, Section 6.2 illustrates the data preparation, editing, coding, and scanning processes. Section 6.3 discusses the collected data's normality, multicollinearity, and outliers. Section 6.4 demonstrates the stigma associated with non-responses. Following that, the solutions were re-evaluated using confirmatory factor analysis in Section 6.5. Section 6.6 addresses structural equation modeling (SEM), which was used to evaluate the hypothesized relations between the research frameworks and determine the overall goodness of fit.

6.2 MAIN SURVEY

Table 6.1: Demographic characteristics of respondents

	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	323	59.4
Female	221	40.6
Education		
Bachelor	34	6.3
Master or above	502	92.3
Age		
Up to 5 Years	126	23.2
6-10 Years	206	37.9
11-15 Years	161	29.6
16 or more Years	51	9.4
Sector		
Public	354	65.1
Private	190	34.9
Type of organisation		
Distributive services firms	170	31.26

Producer services firms	168	30.88
Social services firms	206	37.86

Source: Quantitative Data.

Table 6.1 presents the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Male respondents were slightly high compared to female respondents, with 59.4 % were males, and 40.6% were females. As far as the age group of respondents is concerned, 51.3 % of the respondents were 25-34 years, followed by 27.4% who were 35-44 years, 11.2 % were 45 years or above, and 9.9 percent were less than 25 years old. In addition, the majority of the respondents were highly qualitative, 92.3 % had a master's degree or above qualification, followed by 6.3 % were having graduate degrees. Furthermore, as per the experience of the respondent, the majority, 37.9 % of the respondents, have experience of 6 to 10 years, followed by 29.6 were having 11 to 15 years. Moreover, 23.2 percent were having up to 5 years, and 9.4 percent were less than 16 years or more, respectively.

Table 6.1 also reveals the sector of the organisation where respondents were currently working. The majority, 65.1 percent, belonged to public sector/government organisations, whereas 34.9 %t was working in private sector organisations. In addition, 31.26 % of the respondents belonged Distributive services firms, followed by 30.88 % belonged to Producer services firms, and finally 37.86 % belonged to Social services firms.

6.2.1. Data preparation

6.2.1.1. Data coding and editing

According to Hult et al. (2014), data editing occurred in the following collection to ensure its completeness and accuracy. First, the data were analysed, and each object was coded and entered into an SPSS data sheet (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). After coding, data were edited to ensure

that the coding process was carried out correctly. Additionally, any values that were outside of the range were double-checked. Data that are missing is referred to as missing values, considered a pervasive issue in the data processing.

6.2.1.2 Data Screening for missing value, outliers, normality, and Non-response bias.

Vetting of the primary data collected is paramount to ensure the overall quality and usability of the data. In addition, data vetting allows treating for irregularities within the data. These irregularities may relate to missing values or errors in the data. Within the academic community, they agree that the data vetting process is an important step that should be carried before performing any statistical analysis (Bryman et al., 2012; Collins et al., 2010). This ensures robustness and accuracy of the data, making it fit for analysis. So, with this in purview, numerous tests were conducted to find and treat missing values, outliers within data, and multi-collinearity.

6.2.1.2.1. Missing data analysis

According to Hair et al. (2015), missing data is a widespread problem while analyzing data for generating research results. There are several reasons for which participants fail to provide accurate information, which generates missing value. First, the length of the questionnaire is a big problem because respondents feel bored answering many questions (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Second, the language problems and timing problems generate a lot of missing data, as Pallant (2013) stated in his book “*SPSS survival manual.*” The present research initially exported the paper-based collected data into SPSS-26 software to check the missing value of the data. The fact is that SPSS-26 software is straightforward to identify and highlight the missing value of the data.

The missing values were replaced with the mean scores to avoid any interruption of the data analysis.

6.2.1.2.2 Outliers

By its very definition, outliers are those data points that lie on the extreme of the scale. Researchers believe that outliers are not a big concern that may be reined with data (Acuña and Rodriguez, 2004). There are statistical methods such as Skewness and Kurtosis to establish what constitutes an outlier. A technique to detect outliers in data through skewness and kurtosis was presented by Groeneveld and Meeden (1984). According to Groeneveld and Meeden (1984), a data set contains one or more outliers if skewness $> \pm 2$ and kurtosis $> \pm 3.5$. As shown in table 6.2, the magnitude of skewness values is less than 2, and the magnitude of kurtosis values is less than 3.5, and there is no significant problem of outliers in the data set. Hence. The researcher retains all data for the next stage of analysis.

Table 6.2: Skewness and Kurtosis of data

	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
OC1	-1.137	.105	3.165	.209
OC2	-.408	.105	.503	.209
OC3	-.783	.105	1.718	.209
OC4	-.653	.105	.905	.209
OC5	-.857	.105	2.416	.209
OC6	-1.202	.105	3.052	.209
DGO1	-1.888	.105	3.612	.209
DGO2	-1.105	.105	1.836	.209
DGO3	-.955	.105	1.747	.209
DGO4	-.955	.105	1.747	.209
DGO5	-.955	.105	1.747	.209
DGO6	-1.386	.105	2.519	.209
DGO7	-1.175	.105	2.176	.209
WLB1	-.612	.105	1.099	.209
WLB2	-.771	.105	1.426	.209
WLB3	-.936	.105	2.176	.209

WLB4	-0.759	.105	.580	.209
WLB5	-0.676	.105	.874	.209
SI1	-0.681	.105	1.614	.209
SI2	-0.793	.105	1.841	.209
SI3	-0.710	.105	1.153	.209
SI4	-1.141	.105	2.735	.209
SI5	-1.218	.105	3.023	.209
SI6	-0.898	.105	1.625	.209
POF1	-1.209	.105	2.601	.209
POF2	-1.221	.105	2.929	.209
POF3	1.418	.105	2.346	.209
POF3	-1.103	.105	2.204	.209
OCM1	-1.335	.105	2.585	.209
OCM2	-1.015	.105	2.339	.209
OCM3	-0.894	.105	1.230	.209
OCM4	-1.576	.105	2.591	.209
OCM5	-1.472	.105	3.970	.209
OCM6	-1.001	.105	1.542	.209
JS1	-1.407	.105	2.983	.209
JS2	-1.391	.105	3.691	.209
JS3	-1.389	.105	3.463	.209
JS4	-0.681	.105	.879	.209
JS5	-1.631	.105	2.857	.209
JS6	-0.852	.105	1.167	.209
ER1	-0.654	.105	1.771	.209
ER2	-1.136	.105	1.875	.209
ER3	-0.742	.105	1.806	.209
ER4	-1.166	.105	3.458	.209
ER5	-0.694	.105	1.344	.209
EBA1	-1.359	.105	3.431	.209
EBA2	-1.776	.105	2.872	.209
EBA3	-1.930	.105	3.585	.209
EBA4	-1.045	.105	2.123	.209
EP1	-0.672	.105	1.155	.209
EP2	-1.199	.105	3.678	.209
EP3	-0.782	.105	1.893	.209
EP4	-1.180	.105	2.770	.209
EP5	-1.034	.105	2.855	.209
EOC1	-1.926	.105	2.680	.209
EOC2	-1.859	.105	2.773	.209
EOC3	-1.963	.105	3.139	.209
EOC4	-1.889	.105	2.660	.209
OP1	1.342	.105	2.341	.209
OP2	-1.962	.105	2.075	.209
OP3	-1.559	.105	3.059	.209
OP4	-1.736	.105	2.287	.209
OP5	-1.734	.105	2.101	.209

Source: Quantitative data

Note: OC = Organisation Culture, DGO = Development and Growth Opportunity, WLB = Work Life Balance, SI = Salary and Incentives, EJ = Equality and Justice, EB = Employer Branding, POF= Person Organisation Fit, OCM =

Organisation Commitment, JS = Job Satisfaction, ER= Employee Retention, EBA = Employee Brand Advocacy, EP = Employee Performance, EOC = Employer of Choice, OP = Organisation Performance.

6.2.1.2.3 Normality

The assumption of normality within the given data is important. Normality refers to the degree to which the data on any given variable follows a bell curve, which could be checked using several different statistical techniques. The normality assumption is essential because it enables the researcher to apply parametric tests instead of non-parametric tests. Parametric test results are considered much more robust and reliable than non-parametric tests (Bryman et al., 2013). Different statistical techniques for checking the normality of any given variable in the dataset include histograms, Quantile-Quantile plots, skewness, and Kolmogorov and Shapiro test coefficients. In this study, to test for the normality of variables (question responses), the coefficient of skewness tests was utilized. To illustrate, Kolmogorov and Shapiro test coefficients were found out to check normality. In table 6.3, it can be seen that the majority of the variables violate the assumption of normality.

Table 6.3: Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	Df	Sig.
OC	.145	544	.000	.917	544	.000
DGO	.175	544	.000	.849	544	.000
WLB	.108	544	.000	.932	544	.000
SI	.154	544	.000	.899	544	.000
EJ	.160	544	.000	.904	544	.000
POF	.163	544	.000	.871	544	.000
OCM	.136	544	.000	.862	544	.000
JS	.133	544	.000	.854	544	.000
ER	.130	544	.000	.907	544	.000
EBA	.151	544	.000	.814	544	.000

EP	.148	544	.000	.881	544	.000
EOC	.223	544	.000	.762	544	.000
OP	.194	544	.000	.860	544	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Note: OC = Organisation Culture, DGO = Development and Growth Opportunity, WLB = Work Life Balance, SI = Salary and Incentives, EJ = Equality and Justice, EB = Employer Branding, POF= Person Organisation Fit, OCM = Organisation Commitment, JS = Job Satisfaction, ER= Employee Retention, EBA = Employee Brand Advocacy, EP = Employee Performance, EOC = Employer of Choice, OP = Organisation Performance.

6.2.1.2.4 Multicollinearity

Multicollinearity is another issue in the data vetting process that needs to be tested. Multicollinearity is said to occur in cases where independent variables are highly correlated to one another, Which leads to a perverse impact on the statistical analysis as apparent differences between cause and impact of independent variables become difficult to establish (Speigelhalter, 2014). Multiple statistical techniques exist to check for multicollinearity within data, including the Pearson-Neymann correlation test, to establish a value between negative one and positive one. Values close to negative indicate a strong negative correlation, whereas values between positive ones indicate a positive correlation between variables. Values close to zero indicate no or weak correlation.

Likewise, Variance inflation factor values must be less than 10 with t-values greater than 0.10 to establish no co-linearity between variables (Hair et al., 2014). This research utilized a simple linear regression model to demonstrate insignificant levels of co-linearity between independent variables.

Table 6.4 demonstrates that there was no issue of multicollinearity.

Table 6.4: VIF and tolerance effect of constructs

Constructs	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
OC	.555	1.802
DGO	.669	1.495
WLB	.638	1.567
SI	.554	1.804
EJ	.685	1.460
POF	.962	1.040
OCM	.529	1.890
JS	.473	2.116
ER	.644	1.552
EBA	.602	1.661
EP	.636	1.572
EOC	.410	2.438

Dependent variable: OP

Note: OC = Organisation Culture, DGO = Development and Growth Opportunity, WLB = Work Life Balance, SI = Salary and Incentives, EJ = Equality and Justice, EB = Employer Branding, POF= Person Organisation Fit, OCM = Organisation Commitment, JS = Job Satisfaction, ER= Employee Retention, EBA = Employee Brand Advocacy, EP = Employee Performance, EOC = Employer of Choice, OP = Organisation Performance.

6.2.1.2.5 Non-Response Bias

Non-response bias occurs in research when respondents' proper response differs significantly from those who did not answer. When the response rate is high, researchers usually do not pay attention to nonresponse bias. Podsakoff et al. (2003) believed that the likelihood of any potential non-response bias was calculated by comparing the means of all variables between early and late responders using the Mann-Whitney U-test. The first 50 observations were classified as early responders, while the last 50 were classified as late responders, based on how survey questionnaires were returned. According to table 6.5, any variable's significance value is more than or equal to 0.5 probability value, which is insignificant; hence, there is no statistically significant difference between early and late responders. As a result, non-response bias was not a concern in this study.

Table 6.5: Mann-Whitney U Test

Variables	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
OC	1018.500	2293.500	-1.614	.107
DGO	1068.000	2343.000	-1.289	.198
WLB	1240.500	2515.500	-.066	.947
SI	1191.500	2466.500	-.407	.684
EJ	1173.000	2448.000	-.549	.583
POF	1032.000	2307.000	-1.526	.127
OCM	1164.500	2439.500	-.593	.553
JS	1119.500	2394.500	-.904	.366
ER	1242.000	2517.000	-.056	.955
EBA	1073.000	2348.000	-1.234	.217
EP	1115.500	2390.500	-.941	.347
EOC	1225.000	2500.000	-.176	.860
OP	1142.000	2417.000	-.750	.453

a. Grouping Variable: GV

Note: OC = Organisation Culture, DGO = Development and Growth Opportunity, WLB = Work Life Balance, SI = Salary and Incentives, EJ = Equality and Justice, EB = Employer Branding, POF= Person Organisation Fit, OCM = Organisation Commitment, JS = Job Satisfaction, ER= Employee Retention, EBA = Employee Brand Advocacy, EP = Employee Performance, EOC = Employer of Choice, OP = Organisation Performance.

6.3. FACTOR LOADING AND DATA ANALYSIS

The statistical technique of factor analysis (FA) was used to find underlying variables that reflect the relationship between a set of observable variables. In data reduction, factor analysis is frequently used to discover a small number of factors that explain the majority of the variance seen in a large number of manifest variables (Bryman et al., 2013).

6.3.1 Exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

Studies involving a cross-sectional questionnaire to collect quantitative data benefit from the exploratory factor analysis (Bryman et al., 2013; Collins et al., 2012; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

EFA allows the researcher to evaluate the individual item (question) essential to the overall construct of the research design and conceptual design. Exploratory factor analysis as a statistical procedure was used to analyse interrelationships among large numbers of variables and describe these variables in terms of their common underlying factors (Hair et al., 2006).

Bartlett’s test is used to establish the adequacy of the sample collected for this study, a. Bartlett’s test helps determine the KMO values used to establish the adequacy of the chosen sample. Bartlett’s tests yielding values below 0.05 are deemed as adequate (Bryman et al., 2013). On the other hand, the KMO value of the test should be well above 0.05 for the sample to be deemed adequate. Upon conducting Bartlett’s test for this study, the KMO values came up well above 0.05.

Initially, EFA was used to look at 66 items to see how they contributed to thirteen theoretically established constructs. The KMO value was 0.891, and Bartlett's test of sphericity (BTS) was significant (BTS = 0.001), indicating that the required conditions were met (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). This study found thirteen factors with an eigenvalue greater than one and items loaded separately in different components. Thirteen items (OC_5, DGO_3, DGO_4, DGO_5, DGO_6, SI_1, SI_2, POF_3, OCM_1, ER_1, ER_3, EP_4, and OP_1) were excluded in the final round of EFA because of cross load or weak factor loadings.

Table 6.6: KMO and Bartlett’s test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.891
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	25296.255
	Df	1378
	Sig.	.000

Source: Survey data

Furthermore, the results reveal that all of the variables kept in the factor loading had communality values over 0.6 (Table 6.7) and that the variables had a wide range of communality values ranging from 0.605 to 0.919. All objects have communalities of at least 0.6 with their components, indicating that they are compatible with other objects in the same component (Hair et al., 2006).

Table 6.7: Communalities shared by individual items

Variable	Initial	Extraction	Variable	Initial	Extraction
OC1	1.000	.919	OCM6	1.000	.859
OC2	1.000	.605	JS1	1.000	.798
OC3	1.000	.804	JS2	1.000	.688
OC4	1.000	.784	JS3	1.000	.705
OC6	1.000	.643	JS4	1.000	.699
DGO1	1.000	.819	JS5	1.000	.671
DGO2	1.000	.679	JS6	1.000	.785
DGO7	1.000	.741	ER2	1.000	.812
WLB1	1.000	.883	ER4	1.000	.795
WLB2	1.000	.728	ER5	1.000	.831
WLB3	1.000	.736	EBA1	1.000	.873
WLB4	1.000	.686	EBA2	1.000	.874
WLB5	1.000	.670	EBA3	1.000	.803
SI3	1.000	.906	EBA4	1.000	.801
SI4	1.000	.759	EP1	1.000	.867
SI5	1.000	.797	EP2	1.000	.850
SI6	1.000	.721	EP3	1.000	.794
EJ1	1.000	.808	EP5	1.000	.764
EJ2	1.000	.832	EOC1	1.000	.813
EJ3	1.000	.818	EOC2	1.000	.780
POF1	1.000	.841	EOC3	1.000	.816
POF2	1.000	.791	EOC4	1.000	.849
POF3	1.000	.835	OP2	1.000	.784
OCM1	1.000	.766	OP3	1.000	.890
OCM3	1.000	.814	OP4	1.000	.803
OCM4	1.000	.780	OP5	1.000	.651
OCM5	1.000	.782			

Extraction method: principal component analysis.

Note: OC = Organisation Culture, DGO = Development and Growth Opportunity, WLB = Work Life Balance, SI = Salary and Incentives, POF = Person Organisation Fit, OCM = Organisation Commitment, JS = Job Satisfaction, ER= Employee Retention, EBA = Employee Brand Advocacy, EP = Employee Performance, EOC = Employer Of Choice, OP = Organisation Performance.

In addition, table 6.8 shows how much of the overall variation is explained by each component. Only those factors with an eigenvalue greater than one were considered significant, while the others were ignored (Hair et al., 2006; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). The presence of thirteen components with eigenvalues greater than one was found using principal component analysis. The maximum variance extracted by items into a construct was found in JS (31.64 percent), while the lowest variance was found in ER (1.98 percent). Thus, the total variation explained by thirteen components was 78.49% (see cumulative column percent), which is greater than the guidelines (Hair et al., 2006; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

Table 6.8: Total variance explained

Component	Initial eigenvalues			Extraction sums of squared loadings			Rotation sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	16.773	31.647	31.647	16.773	31.647	31.647	4.582	8.645	8.645
2	3.826	7.220	38.867	3.826	7.220	38.867	4.267	8.050	16.695
3	2.826	5.333	44.200	2.826	5.333	44.200	3.953	7.459	24.155
4	2.635	4.972	49.171	2.635	4.972	49.171	3.815	7.197	31.352
5	2.537	4.787	53.958	2.537	4.787	53.958	3.446	6.502	37.855
6	2.420	4.567	58.525	2.420	4.567	58.525	3.255	6.141	43.996
7	2.035	3.839	62.364	2.035	3.839	62.364	3.132	5.910	49.906
8	1.851	3.493	65.857	1.851	3.493	65.857	3.000	5.660	55.566
9	1.732	3.268	69.125	1.732	3.268	69.125	2.643	4.986	60.552
10	1.463	2.761	71.886	1.463	2.761	71.886	2.510	4.736	65.288
11	1.292	2.438	74.324	1.292	2.438	74.324	2.503	4.723	70.011
12	1.161	2.190	76.514	1.161	2.190	76.514	2.367	4.466	74.477
13	1.050	1.982	78.496	1.050	1.982	78.496	2.130	4.019	78.496
14	.841	1.587	80.083						
15	.690	1.303	81.386						
16	.669	1.263	82.648						
17	.555	1.048	83.696						
18	.521	.983	84.679						
19	.498	.939	85.618						
20	.471	.889	86.507						

Extraction method: Principal component analysis (A total of 53 items were examined; however, the table presents only 20 observations).

Another criterion used to determine the number of factors was the scree plot. The maximum number of factors was determined using a graphical approach called a scree plot. In the series of

principal factors, the eigenvalues are displayed. The number of components is set when the plot falls into a linear downward trend (Hair et al., 2006). In this study, the first thirteen components explained or captured much more variance than the remaining components.

Figure 6.1: Scree plot

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

According to Hair et al. (2006), it is recommended to determine the appropriate loading for each variable onto each component. According to the sample size (n=544), the suitable factor loading was 0.6, and the 0.05 significant level indicates a significant factor loading (Hair et al., 2006). Items having a factor loading of less than 0.4, according to Churchill (1979), should be deleted (thirteen items were removed from the constructs because of either low factor loading or cross-loadings). The rotational component matrix of the scale is shown in the table, and the results show

that items were loaded on thirteen factors ranging from 0.642 to 0.912 and met the minimal factor loadings requirements (Hair et al., 2006). Cronbach's alpha was measured to show a component's consistency with its related components (Cronbach, 1951; Nunnally, 1978). Based on the EFA, the questionnaire design was finalised with 53 items with further analysis.

Table 6.9: Factor loadings

Items	Component												
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
OC1			.862										
OC2			.693										
OC3			.765										
OC4			.846										
OC6			.650										
DGO1												.778	
DGO2												.760	
DGO7												.774	
WLB1				.881									
WLB2				.762									
WLB3				.707									
WLB4				.748									
WLB5				.733									
SI3								.856					
SI4								.708					
SI5								.718					
SI6								.708					
EJ1												.821	
EJ2												.859	
EJ3												.802	
POF1												.912	
POF2												.882	
POF4												.903	
OCM1		.786											
OCM3		.823											
OCM4		.711											
OCM5		.744											
OCM6		.823											
JS1	.761												
JS2	.685												
JS3	.654												
JS4	.750												
JS5	.646												
JS6	.817												
ER2													.743
ER4													.699
ER5													.831
EBA1						.855							

EBA2														.792
EBA3														.714
EBA4														.808
EP1														.885
EP2														.820
EP3														.818
EP5														.738
EOC1														.657
EOC2														.641
EOC3														.692
EOC4														.714
OP2														.680
OP3														.851
OP4														.795
OP5														.772
Cronbach's α	.906	.926	.889	.885	.912	.917	.888	.892	.926	.888	.883	.820	.844	

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

Note: OC = Organisation Culture, DGO = Development and Growth Opportunity, WLB = Work Life Balance, SI = Salary and Incentives, POF = Person Organisation Fit, OCM = Organisation Commitment, JS = Job Satisfaction, ER = Employee Retention, EBA = Employee Brand Advocacy, EP = Employee Performance, EOC = Employer Of Choice, OP = Organisation Performance.

6.4 STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING – PLS-SEM ANALYSIS

This research used partial least square (PLS) techniques to test the Smart-PLS measurement and structural model (Version 3.2.6). The advantage of this approach is that it allows the formative or reflecting model of the latent construct (Chin et al., 2003). Arvis et al. (2003) concluded that the relationship between I) first-order latent construct and their manifest constructs and (ii) the second-order latent constructs and first-order latent constructs are developed four various types of models used. The following are the four groups. 1) Formative and Reflective. 2) Formative and Formative. 3) Reflective and Reflective. 4) Reflective and Formative.

Moreover, the PLS path model has two sets of linear equations: 1) outer model. 2) the inner model. According to Chin (1998), “the structural or inner model identifies the relationship among unobserved constructs, while the measurement model identifies the relationships among latent variables and their observed variables.” There are two categories of the measurement model, which

are reflective and formative. As far as the reflective measurement model is concerned, a causal relationship forms latent constructs to the observed constructs. At the same time, the formative model has a causal relationship from observed construct to latent construct.

According to Henseler et al. (2015) the decision to use a particular type of model has three considerations: (1) research objectives, (2) knowledge of theory, (3) and empirical conditions. Based on these criteria, the reflective-formative model is considered more suitable for this study. Moreover, most constructs in management survey literature are based on reflective models (Bisbe et al., 2007). As Chin (1998) has shown for the reflective model, both reliability and validity tests are necessary, while the validity test alone is sufficient for the formative model. Henseler et al. (2015) stressed that reliability testing is inadequate and irrelevant in the formative model because of the assumption that indicators do not co-vary and measure without error. In addition, the PLS path model does not include fitness measures (Hulland, 1999; Henseler et al., 2015). PLS also has little to do with the assessment of normality.

Another justification for implementing the PLS technique is reflecting – formative (Type II) constructs. The research uses the PLS approach to test measurement and structural models systematically. Various reliability and validity tests were performed are in the first phase of the measurement model analysis (Vinzi et al., 2010). It is essential to draw any significant relation between the constructs and their respective items to explore the limits of the measurement boundaries. Differentiation between reflective and formative structures is vital in this phase. These systems should not be considered the same in the evaluation of the outer model. The test confirmatory factor's reliability and validity are essential, while the formative constructs do not

relate to reliability except for validity (Henseler et al., 2015). Following previous studies, all first-order multi-item constructs have been conceptualized in this current analysis as reflective.

However, the Employer Branding is modeled as a second-order formative construct with four dimensions: Organisation Culture, Development and Growth Opportunities, Work-Life Balance, and Salaries and Incentives. In the second phase, the analysis of the research model and the validation of the second-order formative construct was carried out. The research model was further evaluated using single and multi-dimensional models, and their findings were eventually compared. In the end, the study model was validated and presented based on these measures. In the next stage, the structural model was tested after finalizing the study model. To assess the structural model, this research analyses the coefficient of determination (R^2), path coefficient (β), and the measure of model fitness (Goodness of fit for the model). The analysis of the measurement model was presented in the next section.

6.4.1 Assessment of Measurement Model

The first step was to evaluate the measurement model using the PLS-SEM technique. It illustrates item loading on their respective variables. The reliability of individual items depends on the composite reliability. Shook et al. (2004) notes that composite reliability is best preferred since this latter method considers standardized loading and measurement errors over the alpha coefficient. The alpha coefficient has limitations; it suggests, for example, that all items are distributed similarly to the reliability, and all are used in this study to determine the degree of reliability. The composite reliability benchmark is 0.70 (Nunnally, 1978).

In addition, the Convergent validity of the constructs examined using the average variance extracted (AVE) and the discriminant validity based on the Fornell-larger criterion and outer loading. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was used to analyse a model measurement for all indicators to understand how the measured indicators logically reflect the constructs in the model (Hair JR, 2006). There are two types of analysis of the PLS-SEM model: formative model analysis and reflective model analysis. The reflective model evaluation focuses on internal consistency, discriminant validity, and convergent validity, while the formative model evaluation is based on the assessment of the collinearity analysis, weight significance, and nomological validity. The following subsections include an evaluation of the measuring model.

6.4.1.1 Reflective Measures Reliability

Chin (1998b) concluded that the indicator loadings should be greater than 0.70, and the level of significance should be at the 0.05 level. A latent variable can explain at least 50 percent of the variance of its indicator at 0.70 loadings. A re-sample method, such as bootstrapping enables us to evaluate the value of significance. Hensler et al. (2009) suggested that researchers should follow the characteristics of PLS during the indicator elimination process and delete the indicator when the reliability value is below 0.70, and the elimination raises the CR value.

Figure 6.2: Research Model with Constructs and Indicators

Note: OC = Organisation Culture, DGO = Development and Growth Opportunity, WLB = Work Life Balance, SI = Salary and Incentives, EJ = Equality and Justice, EB = Employer Branding, POF= Person Organisation Fit, OCM = Organisation Commitment, JS = Job Satisfaction, ER= Employee Retention, EBA = Employee Brand Advocacy, EP = Employee Performance, EOC = Employer of Choice, OP = Organisation Performance.

All loading values are greater than the reference value of 0.707 in this study. No indicator, thus, was excluded from the measure. Figure 6.3 displays the measuring model with the outer loadings of the construct.

Figure 6.3: Research Measurement Model with Factor Loading

Note: OC = Organisation Culture, DGO = Development and Growth Opportunity, WLB = Work Life Balance, SI = Salary and Incentives, EJ = Equality and Justice, EB = Employer Branding, POF= Person Organisation Fit, OCM = Organisation Commitment, JS = Job Satisfaction, ER= Employee Retention, EBA = Employee Brand Advocacy, EP = Employee Performance, EOC = Employer of Choice, OP = Organisation Performance.

The reliability of reflection measurements was then investigated. Composite reliability was used to examine the reliability of reflected measurements. According to the findings, the Cronbach value for all constructs is greater than 0.70, and the composite reliability value for all measures is likewise greater than 0.70 (Nunnally, 1978). As a result, the findings demonstrate that the measurements are internally consistent. The outer loading of all items is shown in table 6.11.

Table 6.10: Reflective Constructs Reliability

Construct	Types	Cronbach Alpha	CR
POF	First order Reflective	0.888	0.896
OCM	First order Reflective	0.926	0.944
JS	First order Reflective	0.906	0.928
ER	First order Reflective	0.844	0.903
EBA	First order Reflective	0.917	0.940
EP	First order Reflective	0.912	0.938
EOC	First order Reflective	0.926	0.947
OP	First order Reflective	0.888	0.922
EB	Second-order Formative	0.885	0.889
OC	First order Reflective	0.889	0.919
DGO	First order Reflective	0.820	0.892
WLB	First order Reflective	0.885	0.916
SI	First order Reflective	0.892	0.926
EJ	First order Reflective	0.883	0.928

Source: Survey Data

6.4.1.2 Reflective Measure Validity

The Validity of reflective measures could be tested using convergent validity and discriminant validity (Phillips and Bagozzi, 1986). Moreover, Convergent validity was tested through The consistency of the various operationalization. The t-statistics values in the current study indicate the significance of the whole factor loading at $p < 0,000$. Table 5.10 shows the findings and confirms that both tests follow the convergent validity guidelines (Gefen et al., 2000). The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is a standard convergent validity measure, and a minimum of 0.50 of the AVE values has been proposed (Hair et al., 2013). It also shows that the latent construct captures at least 50% of the measurement variation (Chin, 1998). All constructs have been assessed for their validity and reliability.

Table 6.11: Outer Loading and AVE for Constructs

Variable	Items	Loadings	p-value	CR	AVE
Employer Branding					
Organisation Culture	OC1	0.951	0.000	0.919	0.695
	OC2	0.722	0.000		
	OC3	0.822	0.000		
	OC4	0.828	0.000		
	OC6	0.829	0.000		
Development and Growth Opportunities	DGO1	0.911	0.000	0.892	0.735
	DGO2	0.796	0.000		
	DGO7	0.863	0.000		
Work Life Balance	WLB 1	0.930	0.000	0.916	0.687
	WLB 2	0.818	0.000		
	WLB 3	0.834	0.000		
	WLB 4	0.775	0.000		
	WLB5	0.780	0.000		
Salary and Incentives	SI3	0.947	0.000	0.926	0.758
	SI4	0.853	0.000		
	SI5	0.864	0.000		
	SI6	0.814	0.000		
Equality and Justice	EJ1	0.889	0.000	0.928	0.811
	EJ2	0.902	0.000		
	EJ3	0.902	0.000		
Person Organisation Fit					
	POF1	0.893	0.000	0.896	0.744
	POF2	0.954	0.000		
	POF4	0.775	0.000		
Organisation Commitment					
	OC1	0.869	0.000	0.944	0.772
	OC3	0.865	0.000		
	OC4	0.872	0.000		
	OC5	0.884	0.000		
	OC6	0.903	0.000		
Job Satisfaction					
	JS1	0.885	0.000	0.928	0.681
	JS2	0.803	0.000		
	JS3	0.836	0.000		
	JS4	0.807	0.000		
	JS5	0.812	0.000		
	JS6	0.806	0.000		
Employee Retention					
	ER2	0.919	0.000	0.903	0.758
	ER4	0.895	0.000		
	ER5	0.795	0.000		
Employer Brand Advocacy					
	EBA1	0.926	0.000	0.940	0.798
	EBA2	0.913	0.000		

	EBA3	0.890	0.000		
	EBA 4	0.842	0.000		
Employee Performance					
	EP1	0.912	0.000	0.938	0.792
	EP2	0.915	0.000		
	EP3	0.867	0.000		
	EP5	0.863	0.000		
Employer of Choice					
	EOC1	0.927	0.000	0.947	0.818
	EOC2	0.860	0.000		
	EOC3	0.921	0.000		
	EOC4	0.908	0.000		
Organisation Performance					
	OP2	0.901	0.000	0.922	0.749
	OP3	0.929	0.000		
	OP4	0.904	0.000		
	OP5	0.711	0.000		

Source: Survey Data.

Discriminating validity is considered a standard measure to assess construct validity. The degree to which various constructions vary from one to another is called Discriminatory validity (Henseler et al., 2015). there are different ways to test discriminant validity: (I) Fornell-Larcker criteria and (II) heterotrait-monotrait analysis (HTMT), and (III) Cross-loading. The first approach is to test discriminant validity by comparing the square root of AVE and its correlations to another factor for each factor (Chin, 1995; Fornell and Larcker, 1981). In addition, the discriminant validity can also be tested by examining the cross-loads, where each indicator should be loaded higher than all its cross-loadings.

Furthermore, In the PLS path model, the purpose of discriminant validity is to ensure that a reflective construct is in the highest correlation to its own indicators relative to any other structure (Hair Jr et al., 2016). The hetrotrait-monotrait correlation ratio (HTMT) is also an alternative method of analyzing the discriminant validity. HTMT value should be less than 0.85-0.90 (Gold et al., 2001; Kline, 2011). The researcher used the hetrotrait-monotrait correlation ratio (HTMT)

to ensure discriminant validity in this study using cut-off values suggested by Gold et al., (2001) and Kline (2011). There is no problem with the negative correlation effects of the HTMT criteria.

Table 6.12 shows the findings Hetrotrait-Monotrait correlation ratio.

Table 6.12: Hetrotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlation (HTMT)

	DGO	EB	EBA	EJ	EOC	EP	ER	JS	OCM	OC	OP	POF
WLB	0.372	0.753	0.437	0.385	0.541	0.351	0.27	0.538	0.412	0.171	0.402	0.072
SI	0.484	0.816	0.407	0.541	0.461	0.368	0.348	0.597	0.522	0.306	0.567	0.062
POF	0.076	0.092	0.076	0.031	0.02	0.055	0.041	0.115	0.066	0.058	0.041	
OP	0.447	0.64	0.477	0.376	0.453	0.387	0.447	0.444	0.451	0.344		
OC	0.237	0.691	0.422	0.265	0.504	0.416	0.598	0.306	0.497			
OCM	0.349	0.686	0.41	0.461	0.614	0.376	0.477	0.5				
JS	0.436	0.69	0.494	0.407	0.654	0.483	0.377					
ER	0.255	0.549	0.422	0.268	0.371	0.277						
EP	0.409	0.572	0.372	0.349	0.595							
EOC	0.466	0.72	0.479	0.367								
EJ	0.352	0.757	0.332									
EBA	0.53	0.64										
EB	0.728											

Note: OC = Organisation Culture, DGO = Development and Growth Opportunity, WLB = Work Life Balance, SI = Salary and Incentives, EJ = Equality and Justice, EB = Employer Branding, POF= Person Organisation Fit, OCM = Organisation Commitment, JS = Job Satisfaction, ER= Employee Retention, EBA = Employee Brand Advocacy, EP = Employee Performance, EOC = Employer of Choice, OP = Organisation Performance.

6.4.1.3 Formative Measure Validity

The validity of formative measures is evaluated differently as reflective measures have been tested (Ringle and Sarstedt, 2016). According to Hair et al. (2014), three distinct methods can be used to analyse the validity of the formative measure. This study used multicollinearity to examine the validity of the formative measure.

6.4.1.3.1 Multicollinearity

The weight and significance level of indicators depends on the collinearity of formative indicators (Aiken and West, 1991; Hair et al., 2014). Moreover, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value helps to verify the degree of collinearity. Thus, The recommended value of VIF is five (Hair et al., 2014), which demonstrates the problems of collinearity if there is a high value. The findings reveal that all VIF values are smaller than the 5.00 benchmark, so multi-collinearity problems did not exist in higher-order construct. The findings of the multi-collinearity of the second-order formative construct (EB) are seen in Table 6.13.

Table 6.13: Formative Constructs Multi-Collinearity

Formative Construct	Dimensions	Tolerance	VIF
Employer Branding	OC	0.904	1.107
	DGO	0.778	1.285
	WLB	0.829	1.206
	SI	0.668	1.496
	EJ	0.711	1.407

Note: OC = Organisation Culture, DGO = Development and Growth Opportunities, WLB = Work-Life Balance, SI = Salary and Incentives, EJ = Equality and Justice, EB = Employer Branding

6.4.1.4 Second-Order Model Assessment

In this study, EB with four dimensions is hypothesized as a second-order formative construct. Such a measurement model is appropriate for multidimensional composite constructs because each dimension emphasizes various aspects of outcomes. One individual second-order measurement model for EB is developed to analyse the significance of its relative fit. This model is proposed based on its dimensions as; EB has five dimensions: organisation culture, development and growth opportunities, work-life balance, salary and incentives, and equality and justice. This model is presented in figure 6.4.

Figure 6.4: Direct relationship between First-order and Second-order Employer branding

Construct

Note: OC = Organisation Culture, DGO = Development and Growth Opportunities, WLB = Work-Life Balance, SI = Salary and Incentives, EJ = Equality and Justice, EB = Employer Branding

Table 6.14 presents the relationship between first-order constructs and second-order construct. All dimensions significantly affect the second-order constructs with T statics > 1.96 and p < 0.05.

Table 6.14: Relationship between First-Order and Second-Order Constructs

Formative Second Order	Reflective First Order	No. of Items	Path Coefficient	T Statistic	p-value	R ²
Employer Branding	OC	5	0.302	7.386	0.000	1.000
	DGO	3	0.213	10.726	0.000	
	WLB	5	0.353	10.816	0.000	
	SI	4	0.360	10.077	0.000	
	EJ	3	0.264	7.176	0.000	

Note: OC = Organisation Culture, DGO = Development and Growth Opportunities, WLB = Work-Life Balance, SI = Salary and Incentives, EJ = Equality and Justice, EB = Employer Branding

6.4.2 Analysis of Structural Model

The key purpose of the structural model is to address research questions by evaluating the proposed research hypotheses. The inner model or structural model can be evaluated until the variables have been reasonably reliable and valid. The analysis of the structural model demonstrates how empirical evidence endorses the hypotheses used in this research. It also allows the predictive capacities and relationships of the model between hypothesized variables to be studied.

Table 6.15 describes the thirteen hypotheses for direct relationship analysis examined in the structural model.

Table 6.15: List of Hypotheses

Hypotheses	
H1	Employer branding has a positive influence on person organisation fit.
H2	Employer branding has a positive influence on organisation commitment.
H3	Employer branding has a positive influence on job satisfaction.
H4	Employer branding has a positive influence on employee retention.
H5	Person organisation fit has a positive influence on the employer of choice.
H6	Organisation commitment has a positive influence on Employer brand advocacy.
H7	Organisation commitment has a positive influence on employee performance.
H8	Job satisfaction has a positive influence on employee performance.
H9	Employee retention has a positive influence on employee performance.
H10	Employer brand advocacy has a positive influence on the employer of choice.
H11	Employee performance has a positive influence on organisation performance.

H12	Employer branding has a positive influence on employee performance.
H13	Job satisfaction has a positive influence on organisation performance.

Source; Researcher

6.4.2.1 Path Coefficients

In the structural model, the relationship between the LV is called path coefficients, and the path coefficients are the overview of all results. The algorithm then determined the construct scores used to test the regression model. In addition, the p-value (probability value) should be below 0.05, indicating positive outcomes. It is also regarded as the level of significance. However, the t-value should be greater than 1,96, which also has a level of significance (Hair et al., 2014).

6.4.2.2 Relevance and Significance of Path Coefficient

The structural model enables the estimation of the level and significance of the path coefficients. Bootstrapping is nevertheless important to test the structural model in PLS-SEM. Using PLS, the hypotheses formed have been checked by investigating the path significance, path coefficient, and variance explained. Convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability are carried out To ensure sufficient validity and reliability checks before hypotheses testing. The structural model with effects is seen in Figure 6.5 after the bootstrapping procedure was executed. Table 6.16 provides the results of the path coefficient, significance, and t-statistics.

Figure 6.5: Structural Model with path coefficients and p-Values

6.4.2.3 Direct Relationship between Independent and Dependent Constructs

Table 6.16 presents a summary of the relationship between independent and dependent variable results.

Table 6.16: Path Coefficients

Hypotheses	Relationship	Path Coefficient	T- Statistics	P-Value	Result
H1	EB → POF	0.023	0.435	0.664	Not Supported
H2	EB → OCM	0.631	11.147	0.000	Supported***
H3	EB → ER	0.495	7.268	0.000	Supported***
H4	EB → JS	0.627	9.944	0.000	Supported***
H5	POF → EOC	0.010	0.178	0.859	Not Supported
H6	OCM → EBA	0.399	5.305	0.000	Supported***
H7	OCM → EP	0.019	0.395	0.693	Not Supported
H8	JS → EP	0.195	4.435	0.000	Supported***
H9	ER → EP	-0.001	0.011	0.991	Not Supported
H10	EBA → EOC	0.451	5.662	0.000	Supported***
H11	EP → OP	0.230	5.119	0.000	Supported***
H12	EB → EP	0.264	5.472	0.000	Supported***

H13	JS → OP	0.244	5.983	0.000	Supported***
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Source: Survey Data

There are thirteen direct relationship research hypotheses, and the result of the structural model presents that nine out of thirteen hypotheses of this research are supported. Moreover, the POF is not significantly influenced by EB ($\beta=0.023$, $p > 0.05$), which does not support the H1. The results show that EB has a significant positive effect on OCM ($\beta=0.631$, $p < 0.000$). Furthermore, ER is significantly influenced by EB ($\beta=0.495$, $p < 0.000$), and EB has a significant positive influence on JS ($\beta=0.627$, $p < 0.000$), which supports H2, H3, and H4. However, POF does not influence EOC ($\beta=0.010$, $p > 0.05$). Hence H5 is not supported.

In addition, EBA ($\beta=0.399$, $p < 0.000$) is significantly influenced by OCM, whereas EP ($\beta=0.019$, $p > 0.001$) was not significance influence by OCM. Hence, this supports the H6 while H7 was not supported. The results also demonstrate that EP is significantly influenced by JS ($\beta=0.195$, $p < 0.000$) whereas ER does not significantly influence EP ($\beta=-0.001$, $p > 0.05$), which Means H8 is supported while and H9 is not supported. Moreover, the results of H10 and H11 present that EBA has a significant influence on EOC ($\beta=0.451$, $p < 0.000$), and EP has a significant positive effect on OP ($\beta=0.230$, $p < 0.000$). Furthermore, the results of H12 and H13 revealed that EB has a significant positive effect on EP ($\beta=0.387$, $p < 0.000$) and JS has a significant positive effect on OP ($\beta=0.324$, $p < 0.000$).

6.4.2.6 Blindfolding

Blindfolding is known as sample reuse, which analytically deletes the data points and gives original values projection (Hair Jr et al., 2016). It helps to calculate the value of Q^2 (Stone-Geisser's) (Geisser, 1974; Stone, 1974), which presents an estimation condition for the cross-

validated predictive relevance of the PLS path model. Furthermore, the Q^2 value also helps the researchers as a basis of predictive relevance other than computing the value of R^2 magnitude as a standard of predictive accurateness. Employing the procedure of blindfolding the value of Q^2 of the latent construct in the PLS path model is attained. The values of Q^2 should be more than zero, either positive or negative. Table 6.17 shows the results of blindfolding.

Table 6.17: Model Predictive Relevance

Constructs	SSO	SSE	$Q^2 (=1-SSE/SSO)$
EB	2720.000	2720.000	
EBA	2176.000	1923.547	0.116
EOC	2176.000	1820.348	0.163
EP	2176.000	1684.634	0.226
ER	1632.000	1306.846	0.199
JS	3264.000	2464.283	0.245
OCM	2720.000	1886.115	0.307
OP	2176.000	1844.264	0.152
POF	1632.000	1635.180	-0.002

Source: Survey Data

The values Q^2 of all endogenous latent constructs except POF are greater than zero that signifies the overall predictive relevance of the PLS path model.

6.4.2.7 Model Fitness Test

According to Hair et al. (2013), the PLS-SEM is tested on a heuristic basis for the theoretical/conceptual prediction capability. Assessment of fitness is the starting point for testing the model. The PLS path modeling does not optimize any large-scale function, so there is typically no index that offers the user a full model validation. The goodness of fit shows an operational solution to this problem, which can be considered an index for validating the PLS model globally. The goodness of fit can be determined by calculating the geometric mean of average commonalities and average of R^2 , as shown in the following equation,

$$\text{GoF} = \sqrt{\text{AVERAGE COMMUALITIES} \times R^2}$$

The indices for R^2 and commonalities are presented in Table 6.18. There is no value of R^2 independent variables as it cannot be calculated. The calculation of goodness of fit is as follows.

Table 6.18: Goodness of Fit

Constructs	AVE	R^2
POF	0.752	0.001
OCM	0.772	0.399
JS	0.681	0.393
ER	0.759	0.245
EBA	0.798	0.159
EP	0.791	0.295
EOC	0.818	0.204
OP	0.747	0.225

Source: Survey Data

$$\text{GoF} = 0.4285$$

According to Wetzel et al. (2009), values of the goodness of fit less than 0.1 indicate that the model is not fit, while values between 0.1 and 0.25 indicate a small fit, values between 0.25 and 0.36 indicate a medium fit, and values greater than 0.36 indicate a significant global validity for PLS models. The goodness of fit in this study is 0.428, indicating that PLS models have much global validity. It demonstrates that the theoretical model can account for 42.8 percent of the possible fit, indicating that the model is satisfactory.

6.4.2.8 Importance-Performance Map

PLS-SEM analyses determine the relative importance of constructs in explaining other constructs in the structural model. The importance-performance map analysis (IPMA) adds to the PLS-SEM results by accounting for the performance of each construct. It is also a beneficial systematic

instrument in PLS-SEM, as it spreads out the standard path coefficient estimations in a more practical way (Ringle and Sarstedt, 2016).

The analysis of IPM maps reveals a contrast in importance constructs. In addition, the ultimate goal of IPM analysis is to identify predecessors with low performance but high importance for the target constructs. Furthermore, the Importance-Performance map offers researchers a fantastic opportunity to improve their PLS-SEM analysis and, as a result, expand the study's results and findings. At the 0.10 level, all total effects (importance) values greater than 0.10 are significant. The bold values denote the highest level of importance (total effect) and performance.

Table 6.19: Importance Performance Map Analysis for Employer of Choice

	Importance	Performances
EB	0.115	68.894
EBA	0.451	79.822
OCM	0.180	75.236
POF	0.009	77.259

Source: Survey data

Firstly, IPMA analysis targets the EOC as the dependent variable, which four predecessors predict: EB, EBA, OCM, and POF. The results are presented in Table 6.19. it is cleared that EBA has maximum importance of 0.451 to EOC, while POF has a significantly less importance value of 0.009 to EOC. Moreover, EBA has the highest performance score as 79.882. However, EB has the least performance score with 68.894 to EOC.

Figure 6.6: Importance Performance Map Analysis for Employer of Choice

Source: Survey data

Secondly, IPMA analysis targets the OP as the dependent variable, which five predecessors predict: EB, EP, ER, JS, and OCM.

Table 6.20: Importance Performance Map Analysis for Organisation Performance

	Importance	Performances
EB	0.318	68.29
EP	0.230	73.85
ER	0.001	75.13
JS	0.372	75.89
OCM	0.003	75.23

Source: Survey data

The results are presented in Table 6.20. The results of IPM analysis show that JS has the highest importance to the OP with the value of 0.372, while ER has the most negligible importance value in the relation of OP with the value of 0.001. In addition, Employee retention has the highest performance score as 76.89, while EB has the least performance score as 68.29 to OP. Figure 5.9 presents the graphical representation of the construct OP importance-performance map.

Figure 6.7: Importance Performance Map Analysis for Organisation Performance

Source: Survey data

6.5 SUMMARY

This chapter explains the data presentation and data analysis. The data presentation was done by employing the SPSS (Version 26), including data coding, screening, missing data handling, Non-Response bias, and demographics analysis. After the data presentation, multivariate analysis was done by conducting the multicollinearity and normality tests. In the next section, PLS-SEM helps to examine the measurement model. Furthermore, PLS-SEM is employed to analyse the data validity and data reliability of formative and reflective measures. Then the proposed structural research model was tested by utilizing the PLS-SEM to analyse the research hypotheses. After PLS-SEM, the final validated model is presented below.

Figure 6.8: Validated structural model

Source: Quantitative analysis

CHAPTER VII

DISCUSSION ON FINDINGS

7.1. INTRODUCTION

The current study aims to investigate the contribution of employer branding in making an organisation an employer of choice and increase organisation performance; the empirical findings were presented in the earlier chapter. According to the earlier chapter, the finding shows that 10 out of 13 hypotheses were supported. Furthermore, the conceptual proposed framework was generally supported. Finally, This chapter has attempted to either corroborate or differentiate the key findings from the current literary discourse. In doing so, the findings have either lent support or contradicted the existing empirical evidence. The literature review is invoked in this chapter as a medium of doing so.

This chapter has the following structure: first, hypothesis testing is revised, and a snapshot of the overall study is presented in Section 7.2. At the beginning of this chapter, the research objective on dimensions of employer branding is discussed, followed by hypotheses related to influence on the employer of choice and organisation performance (H1 to H13) (Section 7.3). Section 7.4 is a discussion of the employer branding scale. Then a discussion on the results of all hypotheses is presented in Section 7.5. In the last, the summary is presented in Section 7.6.

7.2. OVERVIEW OF STUDY

The aim of this study was first, to explore the dimensions of employer brand in service sector context; second, to test the influence of the employer branding on employer of choice and

organisation performance. In order to achieve the first objective, the employer branding concept and its components were explored through in-depth interviews and focus group interviews of employees working in service sector firms in Pakistan. Five dimensions (organisational culture, development and growth possibilities, work-life balance, salary and incentives, and equality and justice) were identified when evaluating the qualitative data, and EFA was used to identify and validate the dimensions. Some of the findings contradict those of prior investigations by Arachchige and Robertson (2011), Roy (2008), and Tanwar and Prasad (2019) as two new dimensions of employer branding explored.

One of the causes for this change in outcomes might be due to cultural and sectoral differences. Another explanation might be that new items have been added to the scale of employer branding. The findings support the importance of development and growth and equality and justice variables in attracting new employees and maintaining excellent employee performance among current employees. Development and growth opportunities items related to defining career development and individual skills development policies of the company. The Salary and Incentives dimension includes items signifying high and attractive incentives for employees with retirement benefits. Equality and justice dimensions include fairness in distributing tasks and resources.

7.3. EMPLOYER BRANDING CONSTRUCT (FOCAL CONSTRUCT)

This research was based mainly on the need to clarify and conceptualize employer branding. Despite the value of employer branding, the marketing literature is not well established about EB (Backhaus, 2016; Berry et al., 2018; Biswas and Sour, 2016; Christopher et al., 2019; Dabirian et al., 2019; Matongolo et al., 2018, Perepelkin and Di Zhang, 2011; Theurer et al., 2018; Tumasjan

et al., 2020). To date, employer branding and its effect on the employer of choice and organisation performance have not been adequately researched in terms of the perception of current employees in the service sector firms (Chawla 2020, Kaur and Shah, 2021; Saini and Jawahar, 2019). This thesis sought to obtain a substantial understanding of the EB construct.

The concept of employer branding was developed as a multi-dimensional construct. The qualitative research findings (interviews and focus groups) were utilized to develop an acceptable scale to quantify employer branding. In addition, quantitative research was conducted to validate the qualitative study's findings. The data backed with the theory and suggested that the measuring device should allow for scale "customization." In service firms, a scale of elements of employer branding was designed and tested. As a result of the findings, the EB was updated and simplified.

7.4. EVALUATION OF THE EMPLOYER BRANDING SCALE

The results of the EFA used in this study differ from those of Berthon et al.'s original employer branding scale, which was developed in 2005. Cultural differences can explain this disparity. In the research of Berthon et al. (2005), they looked into five factors: "interest value, social value, economic value, development value, and applications value." Organisational culture, development and growth opportunities, work-life balance, salary and incentives, and equality and justice are the five dimensions of employer branding highlighted in this study. Berthon et al. (2005) researched with a group of final-year students at an Australian university. However, A sample of current employees working in service organisations in Pakistan, a developing country, was used in this study. Both of the newly discovered factors were shown to be critical in defining employer branding.

“Cultural variations may have substantial ramifications for worldwide brand building,” according to Berthon et al. (2005, p.169). The current study looked at development and growth opportunities, equality and justice as a new dimension of employer branding in Pakistan, and amending items in previously studied dimensions. The findings of this study emphasize the necessity of organisations emphasizing development and growth opportunities as a strategy of attracting and maintaining personnel. Moreover, fairness in resource allocation and equal treatment may generate more job-related outcomes. The reason for this is because Pakistan is one of the world's most diverse countries. The features of the development and growth aspects may differ from one country to the next.

Pakistan's political, cultural, and economic contexts are also different from those of Western countries. Pakistan is attributed to diversity in age, religion, language, and physical disability. Hence, workers have different development and growth requirements. While discussing new items in other dimensions, support from the boss/ supervisor is highlighted as a major element of organisational culture. Economic conditions and social setup have put much pressure on individuals. So, working with peace of mind, the support from the boss matters a lot for employees, especially working in service firms. Moreover, in the service sector, one has to deal directly with customers and offer customized services; therefore, support from the head plays a significant role in offering superior customer services.

The new factors explored in this study can also be attributed to the prevalence of a western work environment. To begin with, let us consider development and growth opportunities. In service firms, employers place a high value on employee development. Indeed, statistics show that in

Asia, countries firmly believe in fostering growth opportunities, compared to a similar percentage in western countries (Deane, 2013). During the focus group interview, employees claimed that development was a key consideration when applying to different firms. Employees prioritize workforce delivering development and growth opportunities during job selection, according to a survey done by Chloe Taylor (2015).

As far as new items in salaries and incentives are concerned, after-retirement benefits emerged. Western countries have many care homes, and old citizen benefits cater to old citizens' social and economic needs. However, Pakistan lacks in this regard. No special attention is made to understand the need of older people. Employees working in government organisations are offered pensions at retirement; however, most private firms do not offer any pension or retirement benefits. Hence, Retirement benefits are considered one of the major elements of the incentive package that organisation offers to employees.

In addition, work-life Balance is one of the new dimensions of employer branding (Tanwar and Prasad, 2019). In the Pakistani Context, this is one of the important components of employer branding. Cultural and social values shaped the different personal life of workers. Workers have to keep all home affairs in mind while at work. Work from home and leave in a family emergency are two new items in the work-life balance dimension of employer branding in the Pakistani context. The population of Pakistan is 224 million, which is ranked 5 in the list of countries in the world by population. One man has families with five or more members (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, 2021). Hence, workers need to reach home in an emergency, and leave from work is needed for medical or other problems at home. In Pakistan, especially in rural areas and small

cities, females are not independent and educated enough to go to hospital appointments and other places, females normally accompanied by male members of the home. So, male workers have to spend time out of the workplace to cater to family needs, and this aspect justifies the addition of new items, i.e., work from home and leave in family emergencies.

Social value was the most important dimension, with the greatest AVE in prior studies on employer branding. The notion of social value examines an individual's attraction to an employer who provides a pleasant working environment marked by fun, cheerful, and collegial relationships as well as a team culture (Berthon et al., 2005). Due to which the majority of Western nations have flat organisational structures and use fewer formal communication methods (Clayton et al., 2008). Whereas in Pakistan, hierarchical organisations have predominance. In Pakistan, businesses need to choose a friendly and collaborative approach to interacting with employees. As a result, due to the aforementioned cultural variances, the dimensions of employer branding studied in this study differ from those previously.

There has been a shift in employee perceptions about their organisation over the last few years. Employees want their companies to allow them to work from home, according to a business study performed by "Global Tolerance," which found that almost half of the workforce in the UK (42%) would prefer to work for a company that shows concern for personal lives of employees as well (Mathew, 2015). Work-life balance also aids in attracting talent by improving employer brand value.

Corruption in Pakistan remained at a high level in the last decade. In every walk of life, people try to get their benefits at the cost of others (Transparency International Pakistan, 2020). In every

department of many government organisations, nepotism is at a boom along with disparity and discrimination. Pakistan is a country where one party came into power in the 2018 general elections with the manifesto to end corruption in the country. Moreover, in the organisation, employees are very much concerned with benefits offers to their colleagues by the organisation. Then they match and those benefits with their own. All employees are motivated to perform well if all are treated equally, but if a specific individual or group is treated differently, it affects other employees' work-related behaviour like satisfaction, commitment, and performance.

In this country, people like to work in an organisation where they see equality, fairness, and justice. Equal treatment of all employees at work regardless of their demographic characteristics and job ranks is a factor that helps to retain current employees. In addition, the reputation of an employer with justice in practice helps an organisation attract talent. In this way, the employer might differentiate themselves based on equality and justice. Hence equality and justice emerged as a new dimension of employer branding.

7.5 OBJECTIVES-WISE DISCUSSION ON FINDINGS

Objective 1: To explore the key elements of robust employer branding in service sector firms according to the perception of current employees.

7.5.1. Elements of employer branding

Based on the finding from the qualitative results – interviews and focus groups with managers and non-managerial employees, the main five factors which confirmed the influences on employer branding (dimensions) were: organisation culture, development and growth opportunities, work-life balance and salary and incentives, equality and justice.

From the marketing perspective, Employer branding is a Process of building a recognizable and distinctive employer identity by offering employment benefits (Functional, economic and psychological) that differentiates it from its competitors (Biswas and Suar, 2016; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019). employer branding is an important tool to attract and retain employees. In addition, employer branding helps employees to picture themselves being a part of the company. Employer branding is associated with talent development, retention, and overall employee performance and organisation performance (Tumasjan et al., 2020).

Concerning the first research question (Q.1: What are the key dimensions of employer branding?), this study examined the five main dimensions from the literature review and qualitative study (see Chapter II and V), which are: organisation culture, development, and growth opportunities, work-life balance, salary and incentives, and equality and justice. The results of follow-up interviews and focus groups supported and validated the employer branding scale. The empirical results demonstrate that all five dimensions have been found to influence employer branding strongly. These findings are relevant to the context of the current study.

Dimension one – organisation culture– represents how an organisation operates having norms and values, which behaviour of employees is acceptable and which is not (Ravasi and Schultz, 2006). Organisation culture motivates individuals to show actions as community members (Dukerich, Golden and Shortell, 2002; Tyler and Blader, 2000). It further guides and encourages employees to behave as a representation of the culture of the organisation (Haslam et al., 2000; Ind, 1997; Maxwell and Knox, 2009). The cultural component of an organisation means employees are feeling good ties between themselves and the organisation. Data show that people are more

inclined to work with an organisation that offers an atmosphere that fits their characteristics (Harinck et al., 2000; Boon et al., 2011).

In terms of the employer branding construct, this dimension identifies a company to increase realization to employees what they should expect and what is being expected from them while they are in an organisation. Items such as OC_1: “My organisation offers good internal training opportunities” (Tanwar and Kumar, 2019; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016), CL_2: “In my organisation friendly relationships exists among individual co-workers” (Dabirian and Diba, 2017; Gilani and Cunningham, 2017; Sedighi and Loosemore, 2012; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019), CL_3: “My organisation follows the rules and regulations” (Dabirian and Diba, 2017; Gilani and Cunningham, 2017; Tanwar and Prasad 2016), CL_4: “My organisation provides recognition/appreciation to an employer who works excellent” (Dabirian and Diba, 2017; Gilani and Cunningham, 2017; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a), CL_6 “In my organisation, Bosses are supportive” (Dabirian and Diba, 2017; Sedighi and Loosemore, 2012; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a).

“You want to be made to feel welcome and secure in your job. A sense of community or being present for each other is important. I hope for a culture where there are people who include your boss and colloquies, happy to foster you, happy to help you grow, train you, monitor you, and leave you alone to your own devices. In the organisation, there is somebody who would help you. Somebody whom you could talk to. Finally, job security and observance of defined rules and regulations are elements of culture which differentiate organisation from other and help

organisation to create attraction of new talent and motivate exiting employees to remain part of the organisation". (AJ)

Consequently, the SEM results in chapter VI show empirical proof that the organisation culture is a significant dimension of employer branding. Moreover, It obtains statistical support as proof for this claim ($b=0.302$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Hence, In a service organisation, the more organisation culture is considered by current workers, the more favourable the employer branding is.

Dimension two – development and growth opportunities– Development and growth are employer branding aspects of promoting candidates onto new capacity building (Cable and Graham, 2000; Lievens, Hoye and Schreurs, 2005; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016). Berthon et al. (2005) also defined development value as an employer brand that offers greater training experiences and personal development for the organisation's workers. Furthermore, Wilden et al. (2010) found that prospective workers' pay greater priority to prospects for growth while a particular employer is considered. In addition, a study conducted by Kucherov and Zavyalova (2012) found that businesses that have a good employer brand invested heavily in HR recruitment and workforce growth systems (Tanwar and Prasad, 2016).

Organisations are more interested in recruitment and growth activities and are perceived to be part of the forum for raising knowledge of organisation and resources among workers (Biech, 2008). Tanwar and Prasad (2016) claimed that corporate preparation and improvement activities often improve the skill of trained employees. Several studies (Choo and Bowley, 2007; Mariani et al., 2013; Traut et al . , 2000; Thacker and Holl, 2008; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016) explored the direct

positive correlation development and growth opportunities within an organisation and employee satisfaction, retention and performance. Armstrong's studies (2009), Wagner (2000), Shelton (2001), and Tanwar and Prasad (2016) have stressed that the development and growth opportunities that employer branding practices regard as a strong predictor of employee satisfaction and commitment.

In terms of the employer branding construct, this dimension guides the organisation that employees always look for opportunities related to personal development and professional growth and promotion in higher ranks in organisation. Items such as DGO_1: "My organisation has good opportunities for career advancement" (Lievens et al., 2005; Lee and Bruvold 2003; Rampl, 2014; Weng and Hu, 2009), DGO_2: "My organisation has good promotion opportunities within the organisation" (Lievens et al., (2005); Rampl (2014); Weng and Hu (2009); Supported with Qualitative study), DGO_3: "My organisation offers the possibility of building a career" (Lee and Bruvold (2003); Rampl (2014); Weng and Hu, 2009), DGO_4: "In my organisation, every employee has equal opportunities for career advancement and career-building" (The qualitative study), DGO_5 "My organisation has a plan for individual (Skills) development." (The qualitative study). DGO_6 "In my organisation, there is the policy of employee rotation to various jobs/roles to grow and develop my skills" (The qualitative study) DGO_7 "My organisation has defined promotion policy." (The qualitative study).

"An organisation to be more attractive in the market must have a defined promotion policy and career path for certain jobs. Offering an interesting assignment to employee provide employees

an opportunity to exert more efforts and desire to enhance skills. Employee development programs enhance employee retention.” (BJ)

"I believe that employer branding attracts employees and gives them a clear opportunity to build a career in an organisation and grow with the organisation as they spend more time in the organisation and take the next step in their career. There must be sufficient and equal opportunities to sustain and grow. I mean job promotion. Individual skill development plans should be clear and communicated and must be based on individual competencies building". (TS)

Consequently, the SEM results in chapter VI show empirical proof that another significant dimension of employer branding is development and growth opportunities. Moreover, It obtains statistical support as proof for this claim ($b=0.213$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Hence, in a service organisation, the more development and growth opportunities are considered by current workers, the more favourable the employer branding is.

Dimension three – work-life balance– Organisations have also integrated their respective employer branding strategies and Work-Life Balance (WLB) practices. According to literature, WLB tactics will help a company boost its employer brand, contributing to improved retention of workers (Barrow and Mosley, 2005; Hudson, 2005). As Barrow and Mosley (2005) suggested, it would be very difficult for an organisation to establish its employer brand without including WLB practices. Research by Hillebrandt and Ivens (2013) has established WLB as an essential component for forming an appealing employer brand.

Over recent years, the work-life balance has gained great attention as an important talent management phenomenon. Organisations have also begun to integrate WLB tactics into their

brands. Work-life-balancing techniques aid workers in managing and combining work-life and non-work dimensions (Felstead et al., 2002). WLB techniques have been proposed in the literature to help a company boost its employer image, contributing to further job satisfaction (Barrow and Mosley, 2011; Hudson, 2005). As Barrow and Mosley (2005) suggested, it would be very difficult for a company to establish its employer identity without including WLB. McDonald et al. (2005) also described WLB as one of the key variables leaving pay and reputation aside in terms of factors that affect employer attractiveness.

In terms of the employer branding construct, this dimension guides organisations to balance employees' personal life and work life. They need more flexibility and support, and mental peace to keep up with other responsibilities apart from the job. Items for this construct are like WLB_1: "My organisation provides flexible working hours"(Kumari and Saini, 2018; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a; Tüzüner and Yuksel, 2009; Supported with Qualitative study), WLB_2: "My organisation provides an opportunity to work from home"(Carlier et al., 2012; Kumari and Saini, 2018; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016a; Supported with Qualitative study), WLB_3: "My organisation provides access to paid parental leave" (Kumari and Saini (2018; Tanwar and Prasad 2016a; Tüzüner and Yuksel, 2009; Supported with Qualitative study), WLB_4: "In my organisatin employees are permitted to leave the workplace in case of family emergency"(Carlier et al., 2012; Kumari and Saini, 2018; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016; Supported with Qualitative study). WLB_5: "My organisation provides on-site sports activities" (Kumari and Saini, 2018; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016.

“I feel energized at work. The important thing is flexibility, and freedom means flexible work hours, and I can work from home as well when I need to stay at home due to family obligations. Moreover, I got an immediate release from the workplace when there is a family emergency”. (AJ)

“In my organisation, I can fully take care of my family, my personal life is not compromised at all, In addition, I was given paternal leave, and every employee has the same facilities to avail.” (HU)

“Although this is unique, my organisation has a gym at the workplace. I like this aspect of my organisation and this added advantage to join and serve my organisation”. (HA)

Consequently, the SEM results in chapter VI show empirical proof that the work-life balance is a significant dimension of employer branding. Moreover, It obtains statistical support as proof for this claim ($b=0.353$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Thus, in a service organisation, the more work-life balance in the organisation is perceived by current workers, the more favourable the employer branding is.

Dimension four – Salary and incentives– Salary and incentives are an important aspect of employment. According to previous research, the performance of a specific organisation can be established by an employee organisation that provides adequate pay and benefits (Cable and Judge, 1994; Noe et al., 2003). Research also shows that workers are well connected to companies with fair salaries and benefits (Cable and De Rue, 2002). When their desires are satisfied through monetary or non-monetary rewards, they know that the corporation truly trusts its workers, which is often a spiritual boost.

In terms of the employer branding construct, this dimension provides direction to an organisation that employees mainly consider their salary and incentives for an organisation to be attractive.

Organisations consider both monetary and non-monetary aspects of the rewards. Items for this construct include SI_1: “My organisation offers above-average compensation and benefits” (Tanwar and Kumar, 2019; Tanwar and Prasad, 2017; Turban, 2001). SI_2: “My organisation offers additional benefits to motivate employees” (Tanwar and Kumar, 2019; Tanwar and Prasad, 2017; Turban, 2001). SI_3: “My organisation offers an attractive overall compensation package” (Berthon et al., 2005; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019; Tanwar and Prasad, 2017; Turban, 2001). SI_4: “My organisation provides overtime pay” (Tanwar and Prasad, 2017; supported by qualitative study). SI_5: “My organisation provides medical and insurance coverage for employees and his/her dependents” (Tanwar and Prasad, 2017; supported by qualitative study). SI_6: “My organisation offers attractive retirement benefits” (Tanwar and Prasad, 2017; supported by qualitative study).

"Employer branding is the planning of how an organisation can reward an employee differently, comparatively, and attractively for his services at work. The organisation can become appealing to employees who offer attractive salaries and perks. I do not think of reward solely in monetary terms; it also includes various other benefits. Although an employee wants recognition and a challenging job, he counts the organisation's response to his efforts through the amount of money he receives at the end of the day. Moreover, every special or extraordinary effort of an employee at work should be rewarded with a handsome amount, for example, overtime pay, bonus, and annual increment. Medical coverage for self and family, as well as post-retirement benefits, can help a company stand out as one of the market's most unique and best employers."(FC-1)

Consequently, the SEM results in chapter VI show empirical proof that another significant dimension of employer branding is salary and incentives. Moreover, It obtains statistical support

as proof for this claim ($b=0.360$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Thus, the more salary and incentives in the organisation are perceived by current workers in a service organisation, the more favourable is the employer branding.

Dimension five – Equality and justice – Broadly, organisational justice is defined as the extent to which members of an organisation are treated fairly. Moreover, justice should prevail in resource allocation and routine procedures, and an organisation should treat employees with respect and dignity (Colquitt et al., 2001; Greenberg, 1990; Thibaut and Walker, 1975). Equality means there should not be any discrimination among employees in an organisation.

According to much research (Iqbal, 2013; Thomas and Nagalingappa, 2012; Usmani and Jamal, 2013), employees treated as equals at work are more likely to demonstrate excellent work behaviours, including job satisfaction and commitment. Similarly, it was observed that organisational justice is vital in an organisation since it leads to unsatisfied workers who leave the organisation shortly.

"Employer branding is a tool to keep existing employees with the organisation and make them function and encourage them to do their best at work with full devotion and dedication. Employer branding is strong and effective if employees are treated politely without discrimination. We are simple and straight people. If someone talks with love and respect, we are ready to offer our lives too. Moreover, justice plays a key role here. Working hours and shifts are allocated with fairness and without nepotism. As a result, everyone is ready to work hard and likes to work with an organisation. Like extra hours distribution, in my department, every employee wants extra hours

(each extra hour beyond normal workload, is paid), and we distribute them equally, so satisfaction and performance in our department are very high ". (FC-3)

Consequently, the SEM results in chapter VI shows empirical proof that the equality and justice is a significant dimension of employer branding. Moreover, It obtains statistical support as proof for this claim ($b=0.278$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Thus, in service organisations, the more equality and justice in the organisation is perceived by current workers, the more favourable is the employer branding.

Objective 2: To investigate the influence of employer branding on the employer of choice and organisation performance.

7.5.2 Consequences of employer branding

The findings disclosed the influence of employer branding on the employer of choice and organisation performance. The findings are consistent with prior studies to confirm the impact of employer branding on the employer of choice (Edwards, 2010; Fulmer, Gerhart, and Scott, 2003; Saini and Jawahar, 2019; Wilden et al., 2010) and organisation performance (Biswas and sour, 2016; Tumasjan et al., 2020).

The literature suggested that person-organisation fit is one of the consequences of employer branding. The H1 (Employer branding has a positive influence on person organisation fit) was supported from the literature review and the information obtained from focus groups and interviews. Employees and managers working in service sectors believed during the interview and focus group that employer branding generates person organisation fit. In past research, employer branding tactics were thought to play a key influence in developing person-organisation fit if

communicated effectively to employees (Boon et al., 2011; Carless, 2005; Wilden et al., 2010). Furthermore, according to previous research, which is the cornerstone of a great employer branding strategy, it significantly impacts the person-organisation Fit (Carless, 2005).

However, Contrary to previous studies (e.g., Bhatnagar and Srivastava, 2008; Memon et al., 2018; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019), this relationship was not supported by empirical analysis (Quantitative analysis). SEM results show that the person-organisation fit does not act as an outcome of employer branding ($b = 0.023$, $p\text{-value} = 0.664$). The SEM results further reveal that the person-organisation fit has no impact on the employer of choice. Hence there is no evidence ($b = 0.010$, $p\text{-value} = 0.859$) to support H5 (Person organisation fit has a positive influence on the employer of choice.). These findings highlight that, while the employer brand aspects are important for better results, they do not always lead to an employer of choice through person-organisation fit. This contradicts past literature (Ashby and Pell, 2001; Herman and Gioia, 2001; Sutherland et al., 2002; Sivertzen et al., 2013; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019), this study did not support H1 and H5.

Person organisation fit has previously been used as a predictive variable in studies of employer of choice, using job seekers or future workers (University final year students) as the research population. Existing workers working in service firms, on the other hand, were the population in this research would be the main reason for contradictory results. In the opinion of existing employees, person-organisation fit does not lead to the employer of choice (Quantitative analysis). Organisations must identify various ways to integrate the person-organisation fit as a central variable in the model of EOC with a positive organisation culture and salary and incentives

dimensions as the central employer branding dimensions. Without the right job fit, an employee will never identify the employing company as his EOC.

Like previous studies (e.g., Bruschi et al., 2018; Erkmen, 2018; Wilden et al., 2010), this study also confirms that organisations may obtain positive results such as employee commitment by demonstrating a strong employer brand. Employee commitment may be facilitated through conveying employer branding values, such as organisational culture, salary and incentives, and work-life balance (Ashforth and Mael, 1996; Schlager et al., 2011; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016b). Furthermore, the outcomes of this study are consistent with earlier research that indicates that employee commitment to their firm varies depending on their career stage (Hess and Jepsen, 2009). Since a result, organisations should consider managing employee experiences throughout different career stages, as workers' perceptions of commitment and value of job opportunities may alter over time (Hess and Jepsen, 2009).

“I intend to stay here for the coming years. Having been voted as one of the best companies to work for, we are getting the relevant exposure. We even get to meet experts from our field. It is quite encouraging. I am glad I chose this firm to work for over other available options. My organisation always remains competitive as the research and development department is powerful here, so this department provides up-to-date information to decision-makers in the HRM department who devise employee benefits. Therefore, our salaries and other incentives are excellent as compared to other organisations in the market”. (AAS)

Thus, analysis of qualitative data and the SEM results show empirical proof concerning H2 (Employer branding has a positive influence on organisation commitment.). Moreover, It obtained statistical support as proof for this claim ($b=0.631$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Hence, there is sufficient evidence available to say that, in a service organisation, employer branding significantly influences organisation commitment. So, it can be believed that If current employees perceive a strong employer brand in service firms, the organisation has more organisation commitment.

Consistent with previous research (Cascio, 2014; Chhabra and Sharma, 2014; Fernon, 2008; Gilani and Jamshed, 2016; Punjaisri et al., 2008; Russell and Brannan, 2016; Sengupta et al., 2015). Strong employer brands can help companies keep and retain employees for a long time. The finding is understandable since employees prefer to work in a pleasant setting where they are supported and concerned. As a result, a company should develop policies that will help it support, attract, and retain personnel. This conclusion is in line with previous and recent research on the influence of employer branding on employee long duration of stay with a company (Ghosh and Sahney, 2011; Kundu and Lata, 2017; Ghosh et al., 2013).

Moreover, Employee retention is positively influenced by supportive organisational culture, career growth, and work-life balance, according to Ghosh and Sahney (2011). Employees are more inclined to stay and remain with a company that recognizes their accomplishments, cares about their work-life balance, and provides a supportive organisation culture (Ghosh et al., 2013; Muduli and Raval, 2018).

As previously said, previous researchers have grasped the notion of EB in boosting employee retention (Randsley de Moura et al., 2009; Vardaman, Allen, and Rogers, 2018; Wegge et al., 2006); this study also brings up the value of EB in retaining personnel in the service sector (Randsley de Moura et al., 2009; Vardaman, Allen, and Rogers, 2018; Wegge et al., 2006). As a result, if workers believe themselves to be a part of their companies and are provided with a favourable work atmosphere as well as possibilities for development and advancement, they will not seek a departure from their existing positions (Akgunduz and Bardakoglu, 2015; Wang, Demerouti and Le Blanc, 2017). Furthermore, the study backs up the claim that workers strongly identify with an organisation's distinctive EB characteristics, which helps them stay with the company (Kashyap and Chaudhary, 2019). Our findings are consistent with earlier research (Carlini et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2020).

“As per my knowledge and experience, I can say that employees never leave the organisation if organisation look after her. Moreover, it is in the organisation's hand to keep an employee. During my career, I saw people start a job in an organisation, and after more than ten years, they are still there. Off course, there are certain reasons for employee retention. Firstly, incentives and, most importantly and market-based and equal incentives. Secondly, progressive environment where an employee fell she is continuously learning and improving herself. Lastly, organisation support, like whenever an employee has any problem, she thinks my organisation is standing with me”.

(TF)

Thus, analysis of qualitative data and the SEM results show empirical proof concerning H3 (Employer branding has a positive influence on employee retention). Moreover, It obtained

statistical support as proof for this claim ($b=0.495$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Hence, there is sufficient evidence available to say that, in a service organisation, employer branding significantly influences employee retention. Thus, it can be believed that If current employees perceive a strong employer brand in service firms, the organisation has more employee retention.

In addition, the findings back up the study hypothesis H4 (Employer branding has a positive influence on job satisfaction) completely. This finding supports prior research (e.g., Backhaus, 2016; Schlager et al., 2011; Slavkovic et al., 2018), which found that employer branding strongly influences employee job satisfaction. Employees talked about how important it is to work in a safe and cooperative atmosphere. The findings add to what we already know about the relationship between employer branding and job satisfaction. The relevance of this study is that management should study the current employer branding strategy to develop various approaches to enhance job satisfaction. A well-designed work environment should be created which fosters job satisfaction due to increase the communication network among employees and the organisation

Furthermore, employees are more likely to be satisfied with their jobs if given opportunities to grow (Kim, 2002). As a consequence, employees are satisfied with these growth programs, which leads to increased job satisfaction. As a result, through various development programs, the employer should provide a good learning experience. Employees' requirements should be adequately analysed, and their professional growth should be encouraged. As a result, organisations should give professional development opportunities to meet their workers' professional needs (Chen et al., 2004).

In addition, work-life balance enhances employee morale and satisfaction dramatically (Lockwood, 2003). It is also tough to strike a WLB in the service industry because of the available positions, which often need individuals to work night hours. As a result, offering employees with alternate work arrangements and flexi-time solutions is critical. As a result, offering employees with alternate work arrangements and flexi-time solutions is critical to enhancing satisfaction.

“Employer branding develops the perception of the company's financial and non-financial benefits. When employees perceive that their company is good in terms of these benefits, they will evaluate it positively and be more satisfied. Currently, my organisation is not offering the right salary and incentives, but the environment is supportive here. I am satisfied with the support I receive in case of any emergency. Moreover, my department's equal treatment regarding workload (Tasks/ Teaching hours) distribution makes me satisfied. I want to add that my job is somewhat flexible too like if I need to leave university due to a family emergency, someone else takes my class, and I am allowed to leave.” (FC-4)

Thus, analysis of qualitative data and the SEM results show empirical proof concerning H4 (Employer branding has a positive influence on job satisfaction). Moreover, It obtained statistical support as proof for this claim ($b=0.627$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Hence, there is sufficient evidence available to say that, in a service organisation, employer branding significantly influences job satisfaction. So, it can be believed that If current employees perceive a strong employer brand in service forms, the organisation has more job satisfaction.

Consistent with the previous studies (Katoen and Macioschak, 2007; Kimpakorn and Tocque, 2009). Highly committed workers should act as brand ambassadors, portraying a real image of the organisation's culture and values to increase the impact of brand advocacy (Katoen and Macioschak, 2007). When it comes to the influence of employer branding on brand advocacy through organisation commitment, Kimpakorn and Tocquer (2009) say that committed workers have to believe that their company is a fantastic place to work, which helps them become brand advocates. According to Kimpakorn and Tocquer (2009), passionate brand advocates may be formed by expressing the actual meaning of an organisation's brands and delivering on brand promises. This study's findings support earlier research that commitment to an organisation aids in developing advocacy for the organisation, among others (Babin and Boles, 1998; Brown and Peterson, 1993; Mowday et al., 1979).

“I am happy to be a part of this organisation and would love to see many other inspiring people be a part of the family. I always share positive reviews about my organisation with my family and friends. Trust me. It is not an exaggeration. This place is awesome! It is not easy to find such a place to work. I cannot see myself working for some other organisation. Supportive team, host of learning opportunities, and an attractive salary package: What else can one demand? If this is what a brand advocate is called, then Yes! I am one amongst them and would surely recommend this place to other people”. (BJ)

Thus, analysis of qualitative data and the SEM results show empirical proof concerning H6 (Organisation commitment has a positive influence on Employer brand advocacy). Moreover, it obtained statistical support as proof for this claim ($b=0.399$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Hence, there is

sufficient evidence available to say that, in a service organisation, organisation commitment significantly influences employer brand advocacy. So, it can be believed that If current employees perceive more organisation commitment in service firms, the organisation has more employer brand advocacy.

The SEM results show that the findings of this study contradict earlier studies (e.g., Allen and Meyer, 1993; Avomleh, 2014; Moady et al., 2012; Shannon, 2002; Richards et al., 2015) with evidence that there is no clear association between high levels of organisational commitment and desirable employee performance. Committed employees in service firms have no encouragement and enthusiasm to meet their performance targets.

The demographics characteristics of the study highlighted that majority of the respondents were from public sector organisations, and a major portion of the respondents belonged to universities. According to Higher education commission regulations followed by all universities, there is no promotion for university lectures in universities. All the time to go in higher scale they have to re-appear in section board with all other candidates, and there is no weighted or preference for working experience in the same university. Incentives are normally attractive, and lecturers enjoy a good status in society. Due to higher job security and less burden of work, employees are found to be committed. At the same time, they have less motivation to perform. Moreover, the performance measurement method is mostly subjective and almost no threat to low performers. Because of the above-said reasons, this found that organisation commitment does not influence employee performance.

Thus, this study shows no empirical proof concerning H7 (Organisation commitment has a positive influence on employee performance). Moreover, it obtained statistical support as proof for this claim ($b=0.019$, $p\text{-value}=0.693$). Hence, there is no sufficient evidence that organisational commitment significantly influences employee performance in a service organisation.

According to key informants' findings, employee performance and efficiency are achieved with a better degree of satisfaction among employees (Alshurideh et al., 2018; Ammari et al., 2017; Chandrasekar, 2011; Judge et al., 2010; Shields, 2006). Because employee satisfaction boosts employee confidence, improves output quality, and boosts productivity, it is a win-win situation (Surujlal and Singh, 2003; Yee et al., 2008). Employees who are satisfied with their jobs are more likely to believe that the company will be more gratifying in the long run, care more about the quality of their work, and are more excited about their jobs, resulting in better task performance (Faragher et al., 2005; Fraser, 2001; Sempene et al., 2002; Yoon and Suh, 2003).

Significant study data suggest a favourable relationship between employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction in the service business (Bernhardt et al., 2000; Wangenheim et al., 2007). Offering an excellent internal working environment for workers is likely to result in pleased staff capable of providing remarkable service to consumers (Chi and Gursoy, 2009). Customers will instinctively recognize and appreciate the outstanding service provided to them, resulting in an outpouring of positive behaviours such as repeat purchases and higher recommendations (Koys, 2003). As a result, service organisations must devote appropriate resources to employee satisfaction programs because satisfied employees are more likely to be the best performers.

“if one is happy with job, salary, environment and overall behaviour of colleagues and manager than there is no question of poor performance. I must say all the elements mentioned above are a motivator. I am satiated with my job means I am ready to do my best at work, and I will put more effort into performing my task. Satisfaction encourages me to come up with my manager’s expectations.”(FC-1)

Thus, analysis of qualitative data and the SEM results show empirical proof concerning H8 (Job satisfaction has a positive influence on employee performance). Moreover, it obtained statistical support as proof for this claim ($b=0.195$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Hence, there is sufficient evidence available to say that, in a service organisation, job satisfaction significantly influences employee performance. So, it can be believed that If current employees perceive more job satisfaction in service firms, the organisation has more employee performance.

Contrary to previous studies (e.g., Kar and Misra 2013; Markos and Sridevi 2010; Susilo, 2013), employee retention does not influence employee performance. In Pakistan, mostly in government organisation, employees are retained with an organisation with greater job security and less motivation to enhance performance. There is not a specific performance management mechanism. Moreover, performance appraisal is necessarily subjective. Therefore, in such organisation settings, retention does not influence employee performance. Moreover, leadership behaviour and the job itself are not challenging employees to perform tasks extraordinarily. Managers should make employees feel proud of themselves for being a senior member of the organisation.

Furthermore, this is critical to those employees who are stick with the organisation for a longer period may be fed up with the routine job and environment (Alshurideh et al., 2020; Alzoubi et al. 2020). According to this study's findings, job satisfaction leads to employee performance, but employee retention could not. In service firms, it is also critical for Top management and decision-makers to carefully assess these requirements of existing employees. As a result, having a good atmosphere encourages employees to engage with one another sufficiently and be glad to connect, supervisors and customers (Alshurideh et al., 2018; Ammari et al., 2017).

Thus, The SEM results show no empirical proof concerning H9 (Employee retention has a positive influence on employee performance.). Moreover, it did not obtain statistical support as proof for this claim ($b = -0.001$, $p\text{-value} = 0.991$). Hence, there is no evidence available to say that, in a service organisation, employee retention significantly influences employee performance. So, it can be believed that employee retention has nothing to do with employee performance as per the perceptions of the current employees.

Consistent with the previous studies (e.g., Howard and Kerin, 2013; Kemp, Childer, and Williams, 2012; Multicultural, 2005; Parrott et al., 2015; Russel and Morgan, 2009; Vishag and Laverie, 2013; Walz and Celuch, 2010) employer brand advocacy helps an organisation to become an employer of choice. To win the war of talent in the current era, an organisation needs to generate some magnetic power for the potential employees. To gain the rank of employer of choice is very important in the context of Pakistan. In one of the growing economies and low labour costs, Pakistan is attractive for local and foreign investors. Many new businesses like to hire employees working in leading firms. This is common practice in the service sector as customers are attached

to employees with excellent customer service. Sometimes, customers also switch from their existing brand with the shift of employees to a new one.

Therefore, to be an employer of choice help organisation to keep their talented employees with them and attract new employees. Through many different channels, employees share positive and negative aspects of their current employers. Good employment practices make an employee an advocate of the employer, and thus this advocacy help organisation to be an employer of choice in the labour market. Thus, analysis of qualitative data and the SEM results show empirical proof concerning H10 (Employer brand advocacy has a positive influence on the employer of choice). Moreover, it obtained statistical support as proof for this claim ($b=0.451$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Hence, there is sufficient evidence available to say that, in a service organisation, employer brand advocacy significantly influences the employer of choice.

Organisation performance can be assessed in two ways, financial performance and non-financial performance. Moreover, Non-financial performance includes increased creativity and innovation, number of customers, customer satisfaction, and employee satisfaction. In the service sector organisation performance mainly depends on employees' performance. According to James Heskett (1994), the underlying principle of marketing is that focusing on meeting consumer requirements and wants may improve organisational performance. The Service-Profit Chain demonstrates how this concept works in a service firm; particularly, it lays out a series of causal relationships showing how employee performance affects financial performance. The reasoning that underpins the service-profit cycle is simple and compelling: treat your employees well, and they will treat your customers well, resulting in increased organisation performance. Employee

performance positively impacts organisational performance, in line with a prior study from Vosloban (2012).

“In service firms, actually organisation is offering services and employees are involved total in providing services to a customer. For example, in a university, a teacher teaches students, and students are considered customers. If we say organisation performance is customer satisfaction and seen in the number of new student number. It is possible because of services provided by employees the teachers. Hence organisation performance may be measured through the sum of all employees' performance.”. (BS)

Thus, similar to previous studies (e.g., Halldorsson, 2008; Kimberlee, 2019; Ogilvie, J., 2006), analysis of qualitative data and the SEM results show empirical proof concerning H11 (Employee performance has a positive influence on organisation performance). Moreover, it obtained statistical support as proof for this claim ($b=0.230$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Hence, there is sufficient evidence available to say that, in a service organisation, employee performance significantly influences organisation performance. So, it can be believed that if employees performance increases organisation performance also increases.

Employee performance is the effectiveness with which job incumbents perform activities that contribute to the organisation's technical core either directly by implementing a part of its technological process or indirectly by providing it with needed materials or services. At the workplace lot of different elements encourage the employee to perform a task. Supportive organisation culture, incentives, justice, and organisation policies to balance employees personal

and work life are few factors affect employee to show an attitude to perform a task and put more effort to achieve performance targets (Bodderas et al., 2011; Davies, 2007; Hendriatta, 2014)

“what we expect from employees? Obviously, Superior customer service. I think an employee is also a machine. If you provide with required electricity and lubrication, it will work as desired and expected. I called electricity and lubrication a set of distinctive benefits that you literary people called employer branding. U fone (telecom firm) is now among the top brands and reason for this is the level of services we are providing to customers. My employee is providing services and what we realize my employees' needs. Let me count them. Competitive salary, excellent work environment, family support, job security, concern for personal life and professional growth, and career management. We provide them, and they perform well.” (AAS)

“Employer branding all about becomes a unique employer in the market with excellent benefits and support. Like an employer branding element, work-life balance matters when offered handsome salaries and incentives and, most importantly, fairness. This is employer branding, and it has a direct trigger for employee performance. Employer branding is sufficiently enough to induce employee efforts and delivery (Performance)”(GAB)

Thus, analysis of qualitative data and the SEM results show empirical proof concerning H12 (Employer branding has a positive influence on employee performance). Moreover, it obtained statistical support as proof for this claim (b=0.264, p-value=0.000). Hence, there is sufficient evidence available to say that, in a service organisation, employee performance significantly

influences organisation performance. So, it can be believed that if employees performance increases organisation performance also increases.

Previous researchers (e.g., Cummings, 1970; Koys, 2001; Obiekwe et al., 2019; Pushpakumari, 2008) believed that satisfaction enhances employee performance which further could lead to higher organisation performance. However, this study identifies the direct link between job satisfaction and organisation performance. Considering the non-financial performance of an organisation, it can be assumed that in a service firm, one of the organisation's goals is to increase employee job satisfaction, and when there is an increase in job satisfaction, it means that organisation has achieved its goals.

“employee job satisfaction is an important element for any organisation. Satisfaction means we are happy here, we are being looked after by organisation, we are being concerned by the organisation. If an organisation success lies in obtaining employee job satisfaction, then it means it is successful. One of the many positive outcomes of job satisfaction is organisation performance. In banks, one of the important performance indicators is an increase in employee job satisfaction.”
(HJ)

“Be different and buy differently. I mean, we are different on market-based salary, and my team is differentiated on performance. It is Pakistan! Give more money to an employee and look, he immediately increases performance. one day, I announce extra commission, and the next day my field agent comes with recovery.” (AG)

“Employer branding all about becomes a unique employer in the market with excellent benefits and support. Like an employer branding element, work-life balance matters when offered handsome salaries and incentives and, most importantly, fairness. This is employer branding, and it has a direct trigger for employee performance. Employer branding is sufficiently enough to induce performance.” (GAB)

“Employer branding has only one objective, which is employee performance. I think if there is no performance, no employer branding. I support the direct link of employer branding with employee performance.” (GA)

Thus, analysis of qualitative data and the SEM results show empirical proof concerning H13 (Job satisfaction has a positive influence on organisation performance). Moreover, it obtained statistical support as proof for this claim ($b=0.244$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Hence, there is sufficient evidence available to say that, in a service organisation, job satisfaction significantly influences organisation performance. So, it can be believed that if job satisfaction increases, organisation performance also increases.

In the context of service-sector firms, this study aims to explain more holistically the link between employer branding, employer of choice, and organisational performance from the perspective of existing workers. In addition, by examining the proposed model of the relationship between employer branding and its dimensions (organisation culture, development and growth opportunities, salary and incentives, work-life balance, and equality and justice) as well as the major consequences (employee performance, employer of choice, and organisation performance) in the context of developing countries like Pakistan. The current research will contribute to a better

understanding of the relationship between employer branding and its dimensions. Although the employee of a Pakistani service organisation may have unique qualities that influence the findings of the study, the findings may be generalised to the manufacturing sector.

The current study identified, adopted, and modified the available measurements of the construct under investigation. Thus, this research supports the researches of scholars who claim that (1) there is a lack of research on the concept and dimensions of employer branding (Backhaus, 2016; Berry et al., 2018; Biswas and Sour, 2016; Christopher et al., 2019; Dabirian et al., 2019; Matongolo et al., 2018, Perepelkin and Di Zhang, 2011; Theurer et al., 2018; Tumasjan et al., 2020; Vercic, 2021); (2) there is a relationship between the employer branding and employer of choice and organisation performance (Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019; Berthon et al., 2005; Collins and Stevens, 2002; Lievens et al., 2007; Maheshwari et al., 2017; Matongolo et al., 2018; Srivastava, 2010; Tanwar and Prasad, 2017; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016; Theurer et al., 2018; Tumasjan et al., 2020).

In addition, to better understand the concept of employer branding and its constructs, some new items were adopted from the qualitative study (interviews and focus groups). Even though the number of measuring items was not the same as in the original, the statistical analyses revealed that each construct had a high level of validity and reliability. As a result, the current study's findings may be applied to a larger population (Churchill, 1991).

Furthermore, this study contributes to the existing literature by refining and testing the employer branding and the construct measurement scales in the study setting. In conclusion, this is one of

the few studies that conceptualize and operationalize employer branding concepts and their effects on employer choice and organisation performance in the service sector. This study is an effort to develop a novel premise with significant managerial ramifications. Because of this study's theoretical contribution, the results should be sufficiently generalizable.

Figure 7.1: Final Model

Source: Researcher

CHAPTER VIII

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

8.1. INTRODUCTION

The primary aim of this research was to identify the dimensions of employer branding and test the influence of employer branding on the employer of choice and organisation performance. To sufficiently address the research aim, the study employed quantitative and qualitative research methods. The qualitative research method allowed the researcher to explore employer branding and its factors through the insights offered by employees (Managers and Non-managerial employees) in service firms in Pakistan. This chapter begins with implications of research findings with theoretical, methodological, and managerial contributions (Section 8.2). Research limitations and future research avenues are presented in section 8.3

8.2. IMPLICATIONS OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

8.2.1. Contribution to the knowledge

The research is a valuable contribution to the marketing and HRM literature as researchers were gradually giving more attention to employer branding (Biswas and Sour, 2016; Dabrian et al., 2019; Kaur and Shah, 2021; Srivastava, 2010; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019). The contribution of this study seeks to achieve a broader viewpoint on the employer branding, and employer of choice. Moreover, this is one of the few studies to empirically confirm the assumption that employer branding influences the employer of choice and organisation performance (Biswas and Sour, 2016; Tumasjan et al., 2020).

This study highlighted the dynamic and interconnected essence of employer branding and it claimed that EB tends to be far subtler and more intertwined than any single human resource management feature. It cannot be deployed as isolated components and is expected to function efficiently on its own, especially in achieving the rank of employer of choice and enhancing organisation performance. To affect employee job-related outcomes, the diverse and numerous interconnected elements of employer branding and applicable moderating conditions may have to be handled and maneuvered in parallel, in a systemic and complementary manner. In addition, overcoming limitations in earlier scale on employer branding this study developed and validate scale on employer branding in the perceptions of current employees in service firms.

Regarding first research objective, this study conferred elements of employer branding highlighted by previous researcher, which are organisation culture (Berthon et al., 2005; Elving et al., 2013; Martin, 2008; Munsamy and Venter, 2009; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019), Salary and incentives(Ambler and Barrow, 1996; Berthon et al., 2005; Elving et al., 2013; Munsamy and Venter, 2009; Rampl, 2014; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019), and work-life balance (Agrawal and Swaroop, 2009; Dabirian et al., 2017; Tanwar and Prasad, 2017). Identification and addition of two new elements (i.e., development and growth opportunities, and equality and justice) in employer branding enhance its essence which is a great contribution of this study to existing knowledge. The scale ("EmpAt") presented by Berthon et al., (2005) to measure employer branding, has a limitation in that it was designed using a sample of potential employees (students) and can only be applied to final-year college students with limited work experience (Alnaçk and Alnaçk, 2012; Hillebrandt and Ivens, 2013; Roy, 2013; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019; Zhu et al., 2014). Development and validation of scale for employer branding using past literature and

qualitative data (Interviews and focus group), was another important contribution of this study to knowledge.

Refer to second research objective, this study presented some unique links of important constructs. Contrary to previous researcher (e.g., Bhatnagar and Srivastava, 2008; Memon et al., 2018; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019), this study highlights that person organisation fit does not hold the impact of employer branding to take it to the employer of choice. While organisation commitment and employer brand advocacy lead to the influence of EB to the employer of choice (Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019; Bruschi et al., 2018; Devina et al., 2016; Erkmen, 2018; Maheshwari et al., 2017; Matongolo et al., 2018; Saini and Jawahar, 2019; Tanwar and Kumar, 2019; Wilden et al., 2010). It means employer rankings based on employees' perceptions are related to employee recommendations (as an employer of choice) indicates that employers are good at signaling employment opportunities to job seekers. Employment experiences are related to employee recommendations, indicating that they are also keeping promises made to employees.

Moreover, Furthermore, this study established a direct link between employer branding and employee performance which is a valuable addition to the existing understanding of the consequences of employer branding. The Finding of this study further offered an empirical evidence on influence of employer branding on organisation performance. This conclusion is significant because academics have repeatedly assured employers about the importance of successful employer branding in maintaining good employee performance and organisation performance, either directly or indirectly (e.g., Bodderas et al., 2011; Davies, 2007; Hendriatta, 2014; Kimberlee, 2019; Nabi et al., 2017; Pawirosumarto et al., 2017; Prophet et al., 2017; Ogilvie,

J., 2006). Because there is a substantial body of HRM research linking specific HRM strategies, systems, leadership, culture, and other factors to improve employee performance, some of which is through the influence of effective employer branding. The assumption that effective employer branding has a positive effect on employee performance is not surprising or unfounded. (e.g., Anitha, 2014; Albrecht, 2012; Aslam et al., 2013; Biswas and Varma, 2012; Guthrie, 2001; Medlin et al., 2008).

Theoretical explanations were given in a previous section of this chapter. This discovery is also a fascinating contribution to the body of science. The exploration and proposal of another way to interpret and treat employment values and rewards offered by an employer is another significance addition of the study results to existing knowledge. It is claimed that an employer can choose incentives from any of these groups (salary and incentives, development and growth opportunities, and equality and justice) to meet the practical desires of their workers. An employer may look at how employment values and benefits influence the company from a human, material, financial, and intended outcome position, whereas a current employee or job seeker would look at how they affect their immediate and long-term requirements goals. How an employer views these employment values and benefits can impact the chosen values and benefits and how they are structured and dispersed.

Employer branding is becoming more common in Pakistan, where this study was performed. With the exponential development of service firms, studies that shed light on how employer branding activities are carried out in service firms are valuable, determining whether the aspects of EB discussed in this study shape these practices or influence the outcome of these practices. This study

was created in response to a request for research into the relationship between employer branding and employee and organisation performance.

8.2.2. Methodological contribution of the study

An in-depth scholarly research work follows a scientific methodological ground to address the aim and objectives. Therefore, the current study employed a strong methodological framework to collect and analyse data for addressing methodological challenges. In the context of Pakistan, mixed-method research on employer branding is not widely common. So, mixed-method research would encourage young researchers to research by incorporating mixed methods. The study justified the methodological choices relating to academic literature and scientific research publications.

Thus, the methodological chapter would provide a powerful insight into understanding the research methods used in contemporary business research. For example, the study provides clear rationality or justification for applying qualitative and quantitative research approaches in a single research. The future researcher may cite this justification to research employer branding. The academic researcher and the industry or business researchers may consider this research work as an example to carry out further research on EB. Moreover, the fruitful explanation of every single paradigm of research, including philosophical considerations, research method, sampling, data collection instruments, data analysis technique, and ethical considerations, would add value for the researcher, companies, consultants, and other stakeholders methodologically.

8.2.3. Managerial contribution of the study

The bulk of scholarly literature on employer branding has concentrated on employee attraction, retention characteristics (e.g., Bhatnagar and Srivastava, 2008; Kateon and Macioschek, 2007; Lievens, Van Hove and Anseel, 2007; McKenzie and Glynn, 2001). Furthermore, the concept and scope of employer branding actions have been restricted to the roles of communicating the job values offered (e.g., Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004; Ewing et al., 2002; Lloyd, 2002;) or employer brand development (D'Arcy, 2003; Kateon and Macioschek, 2007), with very little regard to the impact of EB on the employer of choice and organisation performance.

As a result, the first relevance and contribution of this study to existing knowledge are that it investigates an aspect of employer branding that is outside of the more commonly defined scope, adding to the already limited empirical literature on the influence of employer branding on both employers of choice and organisational performance (e.g., Bodderas et al., 2011; Davies, 2007; Fulmer, Gerhart, and Scott, 2003). The studies, in particular, contribute to current understanding by providing detailed insight into 1) what are the key dimensions of employer branding. 2) How employer branding can affect employer of choice and organisational performance.

The current research looked at antecedent factors that can help an organisation's employer branding. According to the report, an organisation's employer branding can be appealing and recognizable by integrating strong organisational culture, offering ample development and growth opportunities in the organisation, Work-life balance benefits, and providing competitive salary and lucrative incentives, including after retirement benefits. Furthermore, once an organisation develops a strong employer brand, talented employees are more likely to stay with it. The research

also demonstrated how workplace branding aids in the development of employee work-related results and assists organisations in being an employer of choice. Additionally, improving employer branding activities would result in improved organisational performance.

Moreover, adding to scientific knowledge, the results of this research have some significant consequences for employer branding practice. The first premise is that when developing and implementing an employer branding strategy, a company must consider the desired goal of increased employee and organisational performance, particularly in the formulation and fulfillment of employer brand promises. As a result, a company will be reminded and called upon regularly to address the stated performance improvement targets.

Another practical consequence is to approach being an employer of choice with pragmatism and strategy. Employer of choice distinction may not always require having a separate and distinct employer from its competitors, although it is feasible. An organisation can function within a true network of preferred employers, and it can differentiate itself as a superior employer by continuously providing employee-valued benefits. The most important idea is that an employer must focus on aspects of employer branding that are employment values or incentives within its reasonable scope of the provision, as shown by this study.

This study helps a company to get a good idea of what it is to be an employer. What is the organisation's essence? How do one's employer brand and human resource management activities represent this? Since not doing so would make it very difficult for the employer to satisfy its

commitments, there is a need to advertise itself and deliver job propositions that align with the authentic organisational nature, principles, characteristics, and potential to fulfill. Employer branding activities should be tailored to achieve organisation commitment to successfully rank organisation, an employer of choice, and individual and organisation performance improvement.

The idea that any employer branding tactics to be successful or potentially informative at this time will not be so in the future a significant inference to be presented here. What is considered useful now could be less or more effective as they come into action later. Scholars (e.g., Langley et al., 2013; MacKay and Chia, 2013) expressed similar caution. They argued that basic decisions or sequences of actions and events that may contribute to a predicted outcome at one point might not be applicable or even disastrous at a later point when other activities, events, individuals, players, or factors interfere. Finally, performance is subjective rather than objective (Rosenzweig 2007), and to be successful, organisations must be adaptive in their choices and activities.

As a result, simply providing employees with a mix of desirable employment benefits identified in this study, via content or process, to improve employee job-related outcomes like job satisfaction, organisational commitment, and organisational performance is insufficient, as this will likely limit the outcomes of employer branding to ensuring employee attraction and retention. The comprehensive set of employment values or benefits should provide a progressive attachment and engagement plan that provides formal opportunities for employees to intensify their involvement with the organisation over time while still increasing their commitment to the organisation to improve performance and mediators of performance continuously.

Another takeaway from the study's findings was that even the best-of-the-best company does not meet its workers' demands for all of the benefits offered. Does an employer expect it to meet all or even most of its employer brand commitments to the degree that most of its workers consider adequate? Overall, adequacy is a highly subjective concept that can be affected by a variety of variables. The response is probably no, but the more critical question is whether job morale will suffer due to the company's inability to meet any of its employer brand commitments. Despite the modest effect results, the answer to this question may be yes because it suggests an impact on job satisfaction and organisational commitment. As a result, when selecting and coordinating one's employer branding feature, it is critical to be both authentic and selective.

The outcomes of this study reveal that not all work values or rewards are created equal when it comes to increasing individual and organisational performance. Furthermore, because of the numerous elements that influence an organisation, the work values or incentives that may be most advantageous in molding successful behaviours in one type of organisation may differ from those in another. For example, some service industries are more dynamic and volatile, such as telecommunications and medical (hospitals), while others, such as education (universities) services, are relatively stable and steady. The implication here is that employers must investigate and determine the employment values or benefits that work best with their respective organisations to retain talent.

Organisational executives are under scrutiny to employ their tools in a prudent, strategic, and cost-effective way in the age of increased management transparency and accountability. An employer can achieve a higher performance return by allocating more resources to performance-enhancing

values or benefits and less or zero to those that do not, whether those values or benefits improve other employee attributes targeted by the employer. This study shows that investing in employer branding will provide many benefits to an organisation which can be beneficial in the long run. Furthermore, it aids the organisation in achieving the status of the employer of choice in the industry.

8.3. RESEARCH LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

8.3.1. Research limitations

The study has some limitations that should be noted. The first are factors that may influence the findings' validity, and the second are factors that may influence the results' transferability. A variety of factors can influence the significance of a study's results. These factors include, but are not limited to, when and how data is processed, data sources, and data analysis. The self-reporting aspect of survey respondents is one consideration that could influence the validity of the results in this sample.

Respondents were encouraged to anonymously share their thoughts on their company's employer branding efforts as well as their job-related results and levels of performance. Talking about his own performance may lead to some biases as everyone normally rate himself high. Any respondents may be influenced by social desirability bias as a result of such a personal request. If that is the case, these people will provide an unnecessarily optimistic account of how they responded (Mensch and Kandel, 1988).

Although these respondents may have felt secure knowing that their responses would not be checked, there may have been a tendency to give more socially acceptable answers, likely because they genuinely believed their output was better than fact (Fisher and Katz, 2000). Then there is the possibility that certain respondents were concerned with their responses being read by someone in a managerial position. If this happened, the respondents might lie positively or prevent being seen in a negative light. Some respondents might start with motivation and lose interest in the middle of the questionnaire. Thus, they responded half-heartedly and answered without giving much consideration, which could lead to erroneous scores, which could skew the outcomes of the analyses.

Another aspect that may influence the result's validity is how the qualitative evidence is treated. In order to do a qualitative study, the researcher had to analyse information obtained from management interviews and focus group interviews with workers. Some aspects of the employer branding process were not discussed explicitly by interviewees but were mirrored in their explanations of situations, choices, and behaviours. The researcher had to decipher the data and draw conclusions and inferences from it. There will be some subjectivity introduced into the conclusion-making process, which implies that the findings' precision and validity may be questioned.

The study adopted a mixed methodology approach which is often critiqued on the grounds of reliability and validity. Proponents of the mixed methodology approach argue about its suitability for contemporary business research (Bryman et al., 2015). It should be noted that this study has employed suitable statistical methods and presented sound justification for the choice of statistical

methods. It can be argued that appropriate statistical methods are enough for proving the reliability and validity of this research project. The researcher's lack of experience is to some extent compensated for with adopting a mixed methodology approach.

The researcher would urge further study into the domain by considering the following limitations: Resource constraints such as cost and time could limit the interview process and result in bias. The sample size should be statistically representative of the underlying population, limiting Sample for qualitative data should be collected from all different businesses, including manufacturing firms across Pakistan, for better generalizability.

8.3.2. Future research avenues

A wider variety of in-depth studies will be necessary to decide if there are consistencies in establishing employers of choice through employer branding. In doing so, these employers of choice will also certainly show more specific, difficult-to-match tactics that stay distinguishing and retain a competitive edge. The study would enrich our understanding of the types of strategies used, and it would also allow us to decide if there is a similar approach to decision making to make organisation employer of choice.

Furthermore, with a more diverse sample, including manufacturing firm employees, we will be able to re-run the quantitative analysis to see if the pattern in the findings for the effect of employer branding on employee performance stays consistent. If this is the case, it supports our conclusion that employer branding significantly impacts employee and organisational performance. If not, it is crucial to figure out how and when the behaviour changes. When comparing the performance

of employees in deemed-opposite groupings of organisations, the results are usually always considerably different than when comparing the results of individuals in various categories within the same organisation.

Where practicable, performance verification can extend beyond workers' subjective perceptions to more measurable and concrete results. Future studies will examine the financial performance of organisations rather than perceived performance. Additionally, further studies should be conducted to determine the impact of the employer brand image-identity difference on employee performance. Can the degree of disparity between the desired image marketed to workers and the real image promoted to work seekers differ from how employees view the organisation's identity? What may have caused the discrepancy, and how would an organisation close it? What effect does this have on the efficiency of workers with varying levels of tenure within the organisation? Is the image-identity disparity only a problem for new hires, or does it concern long-term workers? These responses will allow organisations to focus their efforts on minimizing both the image-identity divide and its effect on employee job-related outcomes.

8.4. SUMMARY

The study has created new awareness and understanding of when and to what degree there are relationships between employer branding and employer of choice and organisation performance. Moreover, how these relationships are realized and maintained within an organic and dynamic organisational context. Any dynamics inside and surrounding the employer branding had to be known to extract and validate feasible relationship ideas. The researcher explored these dynamics and obtained insight into the significance of the outcomes due to this investigation. Such new

perspectives allow the researcher to examine some of the most important issues that have yet to be addressed, resulting in the advancement of scholarly knowledge.

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APPENDIX I

QUESTIONNAIRE

This research is conducted by Asad Abbas Jaffari, a Doctoral student at the University of the West of Scotland, UK. This study aims to examine the influence of employer branding on the employer of choice and organization performance.

In this study, you will be asked to participate in a survey concerning your thoughts and feelings about a company's employer branding. Thank you for your precious time spent completing this questionnaire as part of this research project. Your kind co-operation is essential to the completion of this project. The success of this investigation depends entirely on the data contributed by employees such as you.

Answering the enclosed questionnaire is voluntary. Your participation and any data collected will be anonymous, and the responses will only be presented in an aggregated form, and no single name will be disclosed. The questionnaire will only take 10 minutes of your time to fill out.

Many thanks in advance for your contribution!

Yours sincerely,

Asad Abbas Jaffari
School of business and creative industries
University of the west of Scotland
London Campus

PART (I)

In this part you are required to provide the answers to the given options.

1. Gender:

- a. Male
- b. Female

2. Age:

- a. Less than 25 Years
- b. 25-34 Years
- c. 35-44 Years
- d. 45 or more Years

3. Experience:

- a. 1-5 Years
- b. 6-10 Years
- c. 11-15 Years
- d. 16 or more Years

4. Education:

- a. Matric
- b. Undergraduate/ Intermediate
- c. Graduate/ Bachelors
- d. Post Graduate/ Masters or above

5. Sector:

- a. Public
- b. Private

6. Organization:

- a. University
- b. Bank
- c. Insurance firm
- d. Forces
- e. Hotel
- f. Hospital
- g. Transportation firms
- h. Telecom
- h. Others _____ (Please Specify)

6. Position:

- a. Manager
- b. Non-manager

7. Designation/ Job Title _____

PART (II)

You have to tick the relevant answers to the best of your knowledge, perception, and experience.

This means how much you agree with the given statements.

	Extremely disagree	Disagree	Slightly disagree	Neutral	Slightly agree	Agree	Extremely agree
Organization culture							
In my organization, exists a friendly relationship among individual co-workers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My organization follows the rules and regulations.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In my organization, managers/ Bosses appreciate employees for their excellent performance.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My organization offers job security	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In my organization, Managers/ Bosses are supportive	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Development and Growth opportunities							
My organization has good opportunities for career advancement	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My organization has good promotion opportunities within the organization	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In my organization, every employee has equal opportunities for career advancement and career-building	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My organization has a plan for individual (Skills) development.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My organization has a defined promotion policy.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Work Life Balance							
My organization provides flexible working hours	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My organization provides opportunity to work from home	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

My organization provides access to paid parental leave	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Employees are permitted to leave the workplace in case of a family emergency	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My organization provides on-site sports activities	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Salaries and incentives							
This organization offers an attractive overall compensation package	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My organization provides overtime pay/compensation	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My organization provides medical and insurance coverage for employees and dependents	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My organization offers attractive retirement benefits	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Equality and Justice							
My work schedule is fair (I am not overburdened at work)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My organization distributes rewards quite fairly	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
When decisions are made about my job, my supervisor treats me with kindness and consideration.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Person-organization fit							
My skills and abilities match the skills and abilities my organisation looks for as an employee	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I feel my organisation suits my style of working	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I feel my values are a good fit for my organisation.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My values match those of current employees in an organisation.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Organization Commitment							
It is my good decision to choose this organization.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I am motivated to remain part of this organization	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

I talk to my friends that this organization is a great organization to work for	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I care about the future of my organization	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I am willing to put more efforts to work for this organization	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Job Satisfaction							
I am satisfied with the amount of pay I receive	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I am satisfied with my colleagues	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I am satisfied with the working conditions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I am satisfied with the my job	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I am satisfied with the feeling of accomplishment I get from the job	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Overall, I am satisfied with this organization	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Employee Retention							
I see a future for myself within this organization.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I will like to work for this organization for the next five years.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My colleagues want to stay with this organization for a longer period	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
If I wanted to do another job or function, I would look first at the possibilities within this organization	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Employer Brand Loyalty							
I have best possible information about my organization	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I talk directly to other people about my experience with my organization.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I suggest to others that they should join this employer.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I speak favourably about my organization	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Employee Performance							

It is not difficult for me to fulfill my work obligations	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I usually meet work deadline	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I usually leave the office after completing my work	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I am an effective worker	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Employer of Choice							
This organization is one of my first choices as an employer	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
This organization is the most attractive employer for me	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I wanted a job with this organization	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
It was my dream to join this organization	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Organization Performance (Compare to last five years)							
Customers' satisfaction increased	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
There is sufficient growth in the number of customers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Employee satisfaction increased	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Quality in products and services increased	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Organizational reputation in the market increased	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

APPENDIX II

06/01/2020

Dear Asad Jaffari,

Your application 9280: Influence of employer branding on employer of choice and organization performance: A study of service sector employees' perception in Pakistan., submission 7798, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean